

A STRUCTURAL DIALECTOLOGY OF ESAN

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DEDICATION

In recognition of the Graces bestowed anew,
this work is dedicated to
the necessary Strengthening
for
the necessary Development....

ABSTRACT

Significant works exist on the phonology of Edoid languages but dialect studies on Esan are rare. Elugbe classified Esan as North Central Edoid using the limited data on the language at that time while Egbokhare identified linguistic and non-linguistic correlates of Northern Edoid features. Although Elugbe and Egbokhare laid out broad phonetic and phonological indices for identifying this group of languages, there is need to further define the internal linguistic relations that may exist within the languages which constitute this linguistic group. This study which is lexicon-based is therefore conducted with a view to providing empirical linguistic evidence to define the dialectal status of Esan.

This study adopted structural dialetology as a framework. This approach considers a variety of a language as a system whose constituents are defined in terms of their mutual oppositions and functions in relation to one another rather than by anything outside the system. Data were collected from twelve adult Esan native speakers, each of whom spoke one of the twelve Esan speech forms identified for this work and located within the five Local Government Areas of Esan, using the Ibadan Word List of 400 Basic Items as the main instrument. Available data which were transcribed using the International Phonetic Alphabet Format were subjected to comparative analysis using the principles of lexicostatistical glottochronology. Phonetic, phonological and tonal as well as micro-grammatical features of lexical items were examined for dialectal indices.

Esan emerged as eight dialects – Ubiaza-Udo-Ugboha; Ewatto-Igueben-Ilushi; Ekpoma; Irrua; Ogwa; Ohordua; Ugbegun; Uromi; – when phonetic features were used as parameters of comparison, whereas three dialects were identified – Ubiaza; Ugboha; Ekpoma-Ewatto-Igueben-Ilushi-Irrua-Ogwa-Ohordua-Ugbegun-Ugboha-Uromi – emerged when phonological indices were used. Two Esan dialects were identified – Igueben; Ekpoma-Ewatto-Ilushi-Irrua-Ogwa-Ohordua-Ubiaza-Udo-Ugbegun-Ugboha-Uromi – when tonal patterning on lexical items was considered in isolation while each Esan speech form emerged as a separate dialect when a combination of segmental and tonal patterning on lexical items was used as the basis for comparison. Ubiaza, Udo and Ugboha showed linguistic peculiarities that revealed them as earlier forms of the language. Phonetic, phonological, tonological and segmental diversities exist within Edoid languages such as Esan. Structural differences between the language and its closest Edoid neighbours of Edo, Etsako and Ora were also shown to be along those spheres of grammar.

A structural dialectology of Esan which reveals the existence of multiple dialects within the Edoid group provides a significant framework for understanding the internal variation within this group of languages and an avenue for the documentation of Esan speech forms. This exercise is relevant for further linguistic research in this area of study. Further research on other aspects of Esan grammar may reveal other linguistic variations within the language.

Key Words: Edoid languages, Nigeria, Esan, Structural dialectology, Lexicon.

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by Evarista Ofure Osiruemu of The Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University Of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria, under my supervision.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

EK -	Ekpoma
ET -	Ewatto
IB -	Igueben
IL -	Ilushi
IPA -	International Phonetic Alphabet
IR -	Irrua
OG -	Ogwa
OH -	Ohordua
UB -	Ubiaza
UD -	Udo
UG -	Ugbegun
UH -	Ugboha
UM -	Uromi

LIST OF SYMBOLS AND DIACRITICS

~ (tilde) – nasality

ˊ – high tone

ˋ – low tone

ˊˋ – rising tone

ˋˊ – falling tone

c - consonant

v - vowel

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

This work is a pioneering effort. It empirically determines the dialectal status of Esan speech forms. The impetus for this study is the dearth of dialect studies of Edoid languages, in spite of the commonly made claim that most of these languages comprise many dialects. Elugbe (1989) and Egbokhare (2003) are seminal works in this regard, as they establish broad frameworks for understanding the relationships which may exist between members of this group of languages. Since then, no empirical studies have been conducted to further identify or define the internal linguistic diachrony that may exist within the languages which constitute the Edoid group. In that regard, this study is conducted with a view to further existing comparative works on Edoid languages, even though the objectives of these studies are not symmetrically coterminous.

Esan is classified by Elugbe as a member of the Edoid group of languages. This work seeks to investigate the often made assertion that Esan is multidialectal. These assertions are credited to linguists and non-linguists alike in works such as Ejele (1982, 1991, 2003); Ejele and Okojie (1987:3); Okoduwa (2001); Kamelu (2003) and Okojie (2005:vi). Ejele and Okojie specifically claim that Esan consists of "varieties" as well as "dialects", while Okoduwa states that 'Esan' "... serves as a generic name for the distinct varieties spoken in the numerous chiefdoms..." However, to date, there are no recorded empirical efforts at ascertaining the value of these claims. This thesis therefore has as its major goal that of making more authentic statements about the claim that Esan is multidialectal.

Moulton (1968b:574) argues that there are three dimensions involved in dialect study: the historical, the geographical, and the structural. Traditional dialectologists concern themselves with a two dimensional historical – geographical approach, while the structuralists concern themselves with a third – the structural – at first in itself, and later with the historical, resulting in a two dimensional approach, the historical – structural. In his view,

The time now seems ripe to combine these two movements and produce a three – dimensional approach to the study of language: historical – geographical – structural.

In the light of Moulton's argument, we present the findings of a dialect study of twelve identified Esan speech forms. Data for this work were largely from Esan lexicon with focus on the phonetic and phonological composition of the lexicon of the speech forms under study. The outcome of phonetic/phonological comparison between identified Esan speech forms provided relevant information for identifying Esan dialects within the structural paradigm of analysis, while lexical comparisons gave historical insights into their relatedness. Non-linguistic parameters such as geographical and socio-economic factors formed the basis for identifying the physical locations where Esan dialects are most commonly spoken. The pioneering status of this research effort dictates its limited coverage of all the probable aspects of a dialect study. In this regard, this work is a starting point for a dialect study of Esan. It is hoped that the findings from this study would give some insight into existing impressions about the dialectal status of Esan. These findings would also provide a basis for conducting further research in this direction in future research efforts.

This chapter contains background information relevant to the present work. This information includes knowledge about Esan and its people, and preliminary statements about the present effort as regards its scope, goal and purpose. It also provides clarifications about most technical terms as employed and understood, within the scope of the present study.

1.2 Esan language and people

Esan is spoken by the people commonly known as Ishans. The speakers call themselves 'Esan'. The language is the mother tongue in five Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Edo State, which is located in the Southern part of Nigeria. These LGAs are Esan West, Esan Central, Esan North East, Esan South-East and Igueben. The total population of native speakers of the language is put at 587,858 out of the 3,218,332 of the entire Edo State (2006 National Population Census, Edo State National Population Commission). Esan is classified as a member of the North Central branch of Edoid (NCE). The Edoid group of languages belong to the New Benue Congo of the Niger Congo (Elugbe 1989). It has as immediate neighbours on the classificatory chart, Edo to the left, and the dialect cluster of Ora-Emai-Iuleha to the right. Records show that

Esanland has an area of about 2,987.52 square kilometers, and is located North-East of Benin City. Earlier topographical studies of Esan divides it into two geographical areas identified as Esan A and Esan B. Esan A is said to be made up of a third of the land mass of Esanland and consists of the water-less Plateau with an average elevation of about 1,000 feet. It consists mainly of Esan towns established early in Esan history – Ekpoma, Ewu, Igueben, Irrua and Uromi. Esan B describes the area rich in water and forests occupied by inhabitants whom Okojie (1994:2) describes as “less sophisticated and hardworking.” Its topography is hilly with valleys, and consists of the settlements called Amahor, Ebelle, Ewatto, Ewohimi, Ewossa, Ewu, Ohordua, Okhuesan and Ubiaja. Esan has as neighbours, Etsako to the North East, Owan to the North West, Orhionwon and Ika to the South West and Aniocha and Oshimili to the South and South East respectively. The River Niger is on her Eastern borders. Figure 1 is a map showing Esanland and its closest environs.

Figure 1: Esan land and its environs

Source: Fieldwork 2007

The Esan people are said to have migrated from Benin with whom they share cultural and linguistic links (Westerman and Bryan, 1970:88). However, Okoduwa's (2001:221) postulation makes this long standing claim about the origin of Esan people worth investigating. He argued that observable similarities in language and custom between both groups is not enough evidence to claim that the Esans came directly or indirectly from Benin. According to him, this claim suggests that Esan origin dates back to just about 500 years ago, when emigrants fled Benin for the jungle to avoid the harsh rule of a Benin Monarch. He stated that the name 'Esan' has other variants, some of which are 'Isa', 'Esa' and 'Ishan', and cited archeological, historical, cultural and linguistic evidence to argue that "...people lived in organized polities in the area by the first century B.C."

Native speakers of the language concede to the occurrence of linguistic similarities between Esan and some of her close neighbouring languages. They wish that the use of the language be sustained. Where communication between native speakers and neighbouring communities becomes a problem, the use of Pidgin English is resorted to except where there is a shared indigenous second language such as Edo, Igala, Igbo and Yoruba language.

Esan has a proposed orthography (Okojie and Ejele, 1989). This writing system, which had the approval of the then National Language Centre (an organ of The Federal Ministry of Education) is the first documented effort to which some professional touch may be alluded. However, personal interactions with literate users of the language revealed that "Esan Orthography" receives no significant recognition. A look at some recent works on Esan also buttresses this position. The language is taught as a subject from primary up to Junior Secondary School levels in both public and private schools in Esanland. This endeavour is however taken more seriously in the later. Students are examined in the subject at those levels of education. The teachers are generally not aware that there is a proposed writing system for the language. These teachers depend mostly on their imagination and texts written by native speakers interested in sustaining the language. The language used to be taught as a course at the State's College of Education, Ekiadolor in Benin but that is no longer the case. It is used for the relay of local news and discussion programmes on the state owned radio and television stations. There is a general tendency for the younger generation of Esan speakers to resort to the use of English language. In some schools visited in parts of Esanland, about 5 out of every 10

pupils and students interviewed said that the English language was the language of communication at home, even where both parents were natives.

1.3 Neighbouring languages and socio-economic activities of Esan people

That languages affect one another when their speakers interact is a known linguistic fact. These interactions and subsequent linguistic changes are made possible by the many situations in which speakers from different linguistic backgrounds meet and communicate with one another. Socio-linguistically, these situations are referred to as "contact situations" (Igboanusi 2005:1). It is solely for the probability of linguistic changes on Esan, through contact situations, that a look is taken here at the closest neighbouring languages, as well as some socio-economic activities of Esan and its speakers, which bring about these contact situations which sometimes result in linguistic changes.

1.3.1 Neighbouring languages

The languages spoken by the closest neighbours of the Esan people include those spoken by the people of Owan East and West Local Government Areas to the North West of Esan, Etsako Central and West Local Government Areas to the North East, Orhionwon and Uhumwode Local Government Areas to the South West, and Aniocha and Oshimili to the South and South East. These languages are the dialect clusters of Emai – Ora – Iuleha (Elugbe 1989), Edo (Adeniyi 2000:2), Yekhee (Schaefer and Egbokhare 1999:1,2), and varieties of Igbo respectively.

1.3.2 Socio-economic activities

A calendar of Esan market days displayed in "Esan Voice" magazine vol. 4, No.1, lays credence to the statement in Okojie (1994:26) that trading in local foodstuff was the mainstay of the Esans. According to Okojie, until the advent of the Whitemen, people hardly ventured beyond the confines of their settlement. Until recently, the only trade in Esan was limited to the sale and buying of local foodstuff in the markets. To facilitate this economic activity of the Esans, trading became so organized that to date, market days are established days known to all and sundry. A study of the market calendar mentioned above reveals that everyday of the week is a market day. On each of these days, trading activities take place in a number of chosen localities in Esanland. There are four such groups of localities:

Group A

Ewatto, Ewossa, Ewu, Illushi, Ugbegun.

Group B

Amahor, Ekpoma, Ekpon, Igueben, Okhuesan, Ugboha, Ugun.

Group C

Ebelle, Egoro, Irrua, Ogwa, Ohordua, Opoji, Ubiaja, Ujogba.

Group D

Emu, Ewohimi, Iruekpen, Uromi.

Trading activities take place on each market day in all the localities listed in a group at a time. These activities are rotated round these groups in an orderly manner, and shifted back to the first group at the end of four days. A look at figure 1 above shows that these trading localities are serviced by roads, a factor which would necessarily enhance socio-economic activities. The contact situations which are thereby facilitated would give rise to opportunities for linguistic interactions between speakers of the identified Esan speech forms under focus in this work. Furthermore, the effects of speech forms spoken by visitors and traders from outside Esanland on Esan cannot be ignored in the search for differences and similarities which may be found to exist between these Esan speech forms.

1.4 Outline of the thesis

In this section, preliminary statements are made. These include statements about its goal and scope, lines of enquiry, and delimitation.

1.4.1 Goal and scope of study

The present work examines twelve Esan speech forms. Despite the claim that Esan is multidialectal, there is no known documented empirical effort towards ascertaining the true position of that claim. This work is therefore a pioneering empirical effort at determining the dialectal status of Esan. Towards this end, the lines of enquiry in this study are as follows.

1. Does Esan consist of more than one dialect?
2. How many dialects of Esan may be identified?
3. What probable levels of relatedness exist between identified Esan speech forms?

4. What levels of mutual intelligibility exist between identified Esan speech forms?

The antecedents stated above suggest that empirical precedence on Esan in this area of study is rare. However, previous similar studies on other languages, particularly African languages such as Brown (1961), Akinkugbe (1978), Ubahakwe (1981), Ebobisse (1989), Oyetade (1995), Udoh (2003) and Osiruemu (2009), would be depended upon, especially where there are shared research peculiarities.

This study is three dimensional comprising structural, historical and geographical aspects of dialect study, with the structural dimension taking precedence over the historical and the geographical. The structural dimension of this work would be guided by principles of structural dialectology as propounded and developed by Trubetzkoy (1931), Wienreich (1954) and other dialectologist – linguists (see chapter three). The historical and geographical aspects of the work would be guided by general traditional principles which have been used to conduct similar linguistic studies over the years. Specifically, principles of lexico-statistical glottochronology would be used to determine the linguistic distances between identified Esan speech forms while their physical locations would be specified on maps and compared with geographical locations as provided on existing maps of Esan. Exceptions to the stated methods would be made where necessary, as dictated by the nature of the present study. Although socio-economic activities of speakers of identified Esan speech forms would be used as peripheral evidence in this study, strictly linguistic parameters and methods would be employed in the analysis of data collected for this work.

The significant role of tone in Esan is given a prominent place in this work. Thus, the semantic distinctions brought about by differences in tonal patterns between lexical items are taken into consideration in the lexicostatistical comparisons conducted in this work. This is a departure from most previous works on Nigerian languages, where the phenomenon of tonal distinctions between lexical items are down played or totally overlooked. In such works, only segmental similarities and differences between dialects are highlighted.

The first part of this work examines the sound systems of these speech forms, in order to determine the parameters along which they may differ phonetically. Phonological processes which bring about variations within Esan are also examined. The outcome of these findings are formalized within the structural paradigm of linguistic analysis to capture these occurrences. The second part of the study conducts lexical

comparisons between identified Esan speech forms, to further determine the levels of relatedness that may exist between them. In this regard, the well-known lexico-statistical glottochronology devised by the American linguists Swadesh and Lees in the late 1940s, is adapted and adopted in this work.

Comparisons of micro-grammatical features are carried out between the pronoun and lexical counting systems of these speech forms for the identification of linguistic relationships, which may enhance the resolution of the research questions posed in this study. The impressions gained from the outcome of the analysis of data for this study are further represented in maps and charts.

It is hoped that findings from this work would provide insights into the common claim about the dialectal status of Esan. The work would also make possible the documentation of probable Esan speech forms as well as Esan dialects. The preparation of work schemes by teachers for the study of Esan in schools could enjoy the improvement which may be provided by the results of this work, when identified dialect areas are taken into consideration in that regard. Ultimately, the results of this work would enhance further linguistic studies on Esan language and other related languages.

1.4.2 Delimitation of study

The Esan speech forms on which the present work is based are presented below by their common nomenclature. Their individual identification for the present work is provided in brackets after the name for each speech form as follows: Ekpoma (EK); Ewatto (ET); Igueben (IB); Ilushi (IL); Irrua (IR); Ogwa (OG); Ohordua (OH); Ubiaza (UB); Udo (UD); Ugbegun (UG); Ugboha (UH); Uromi (UM). Table I contains information about towns and villages where these Esan speech forms are mostly spoken. To this end, information gathered from subjects were viewed against existing maps of Esan showing the positions of these places and people.

Table 1: Main speech areas of identified Esan speech forms

S/N	Identified Esan speech form	Towns		Speech areas	Local Government Areas
		Esan name	Official name		
1.	EK	Ekuma Irujekpen	Ekpoma Irujekpen	Akahia, Ayetoro, Egoro Amede, Eguare, Egoro Eko, Oikhena, Idoa, Igor, Izogen, Uhiele, Ujeme, Ukpenu, Urohi	Esan West
2.	ET	Ebhoato	Ewatto	Okhuesan, Emu, Okhuedua	Esan South East
3.	IG	Igueben	Igueben	Ebele, Uzebu, Uhe, Ebhosa, Ekpon.	Igueben
4.	IL	Ilushi	Ilushi	Oria, Onogholo, Uzea, Ugboha.	Esan South East
5.	IR	Uruwa	Irrua	Egua Ojirua, Atwagbo, Isugbenu, Usenu, Uwesan, Ugbohare, Ibori, Edenu, Ibhiolulu, Opoji.	Esan North East
6.	OG	Ogua Ugiogba	Ogwa Ujogba	Ujogba, Amahor, Ugun.	Esan West
7.	OH	Okhuedua	Ohordua	Ohordua, Ewohimi.	Esan South East
8.	UB	Ubiaza	Ubiaja	Eguare, Kpaja, Udakpa.	Esan South East
9.	UD	Udo	Udo	Udo, Ekpon, Ekekhen.	Igueben
10.	UG	Ugbegun	Ugbegun	Ugbegun, Ugbegun Ebodin, Ekekhen, Ewossa, Ujabhole, Ugbelor.	Esan Central
11.	UH	Owaha	Ugboha	Emu, Oria, Ilushi.	Esan South East
12.	UM	Urhomwun	Uromi	Uzea, Obeidun, Ivue, Ibhiolulu, Awo, Amendokhen, Ebulen, Ekomado, Uwesan.	Esan North East

Figure 2 is a map of Esan showing an approximation of the main locations of speakers of these speech forms.

Figure 2: Map showing approximation of main speech areas of identified Esan speech forms

Source: Fieldwork 2007

This attempt at capturing these locations should be viewed against the background of the pervasiveness of heterogeneity within a given language. These speech areas actually flow into each other. This view of the physical bounding of dialect areas is buttressed by the opinion in contemporary dialectology that "... there are no clear cut dialect areas, only gradual transitions..." Thus language variation is usually not even across a whole area but intensifies at some points and rarefies in others. Literature shows that the earlier notion of traditional dialectology which viewed dialect areas as markedly distinct and well bounded was abandoned for a concept which can be substantiated objectively by statistical methods as soon as serious field studies of dialects began

(Francis 1983:158). What has been done here is to try to identify places where each of the identified speech form is mostly spoken.

1.5 Definitions

Language

The view of language adopted in this work, is that posited by Saussure (1916), and articulated by Uwajeh (2002). In this view, language is characterized as bi-componential consisting of form and meaning, where meaning is represented by form. Thus, according to Saussure, like a sheet of paper, every piece of language constitutes these two parts – the meaning part, which is the same as thought, and the form part, which is the same as symbolization, and which represents the meaning or thought.

For the purpose of the present study, the particular language form which we are concerned with, within the scope of our understanding of language, is speech or the spoken form of language. Thus, our definition of language as adopted in this work is that which describes it as a bi-componential systematic and spoken means of effective communication.

Speech Form

That languages are always in a state of “flux” is well known (Crystal 1987:328). This condition of constant change of a language ultimately affects the way people use a given language. This effect is brought about by changes in the various aspects of the grammar of the language, such as pronunciation, syntax as well as vocabulary. Such changes result a in gradual existence of differing forms of the same language. Thus, over time, a given language would consist of more than one variety. Each identified variety of a language constitutes one speech form among others, of that language. This understanding of the term “speech form” is adopted in this work. Specifically therefore, for the purpose of the present study, any variety of Esan is a speech form until it is confirmed as a dialect of Esan within the analytical framework for this study.

Variety

The term ‘variety’ is used synonymously with ‘speech form’ in this work.

Dialect

The literature reveals that researchers have used the term ‘dialect’ with various intentions and meanings over time. One of such early usages was that in which a dialect was perceived as a form of speech with no corresponding written form, or that used by

uneducated people, (Petyt 1980:11). In some cases, the term 'dialect' was restricted to rural forms of speech while others viewed dialects as substandard varieties of a language (Crystal 1987:24). A more technical use of the term is that which views it as various forms of the same language which may differ in pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary. This view is suggestive of a linguistic situation in which a given language consists of more than one variety. Thus, using a language may involve using one of its dialects.

Francis (1983:1) defined dialects as "... varieties of a language used by groups smaller than the total community of speakers of the language". Crystal (1987) states that the standard practice in linguistics is that dialects are seen as applicable to all languages and all speakers. In this view, all languages are analyzable into a range of dialects. These dialects may reflect the regional and social background of their speakers, but none of them is regarded as superior to any other, in terms of linguistic structure. Since the present study is a linguistic exercise, it defers to this linguistic use of the term dialect. For the purpose of the present study therefore, the term "dialect" describes varieties of Esan which exhibit the linguistic indices and lexico-statistical levels adopted for the present work.

Mutual intelligibility

The term "mutual intelligibility" refers to the ability of speakers of different linguistic entities to understand one another when they communicate using the said linguistic form. Campbell (1998:193) states that this condition is the principal criterion for distinguishing dialects of a single language from being distinct languages. In other words, speech forms totally incomprehensible to speakers of other speech forms are clearly mutually unintelligible and therefore belong to separate languages. Francis (1983:164) emphasizes this truism about the relatedness of dialects when he explains that two varieties of a language whose relatedness is zero cannot obviously belong to the same language. He states that if such varieties happened to share certain structural features, such an occurrence was to be considered either a chance coincidence or the result of language contact leading to borrowing.

In line with this definition and explanation of the phenomenon of mutual intelligibility, Esan speech forms are expected to be mutually intelligible. The question that the study seeks to answer in this regard however is to determine to what extent these speech forms are mutually intelligible.

Lexical item

This term describes a unit of the vocabulary of a given language which may be a word or phrase. It usually has a pronounceable or graphic form, performs a grammatical role in a sentence and bears meaning (Hartmann and Stork 1972:129).

Identical/ unidentical constitution of lexical items

This term specifically describes the nature of the lexical comparisons which were conducted between the twelve identified Esan speech forms under focus in this work. In this regard, the terms 'identical' and 'unidentical' constitution of lexical items refer to similarities and differences between lexical items across these speech forms respectively. Where these show total linguistic similarity in the specified contents, which could be either segmental or tonal or both, they are termed identical otherwise they are termed unidentical. The concept of identity of lexical items in this study embraces both the symbolic and semantic composition of the linguistic units being compared in line with the definition of language adopted.

Cognates

This term refers to a word or morpheme related to another in sister languages, due to sound correspondences between them. This view is based on the assumption that these words/morphemes have been inherited by these sister languages from a common word/morpheme of their proto- language.

Morpheme

This term describes the smallest meaningful unit of sound.

Sister language

Languages which are linguistically related to one another because they are shown to be descendent from the same proto language are referred to as sister languages. In other words, languages shown to belong to the same language group are sisters to one another.

Proto language

This term describes the once spoken language, from which sister languages descended. It also refers to the language reconstructed by the comparative linguist, which represents the ancestral language from which the compared languages descend.

Loan word

When a lexical item, which was not originally part of the vocabulary of a language, is adopted by its users from another language and made part of its vocabulary, such an item is called a loan word, and is said to be borrowed by the language which adopts it.

Isoglos

An isoglos is a line on a map, which indicates the geographical limit of a regional linguistic variant. This term is extended to include the dialect features themselves (Campbell 1998:191).

System

The term "system" refers to language as an organized whole comprising component parts or sub systems. The units of this system are hierarchically ordered on interrelated levels which function according to an overall convention of usage. Thus language is sometimes viewed as a system of systems.

Conclusion

This chapter whose main goal was to examine Esan for probable internal linguistic relations has been largely introductory. It contains preliminary information about the speakers of the language, their primary locations and characteristics. The direction, extent as well as the linguistic principles guiding this study are also identified. It is hoped that this opening chapter provided the requisite background information relevant to this study.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This work falls within the branch of linguistics known as dialectology. Francis (1983:1) defines it simply as the study of dialects, while Crystal (1987:26) states that it is a systematic study of regional dialects. A more rigorous definition of this branch of linguistics also referred to as 'dialect geography' or 'linguistic geography' is

a branch of general linguistics concerned with the analysis and description of regional, social or temporal varieties of a language, showing how they differ in pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary and how they are geographically distributed (Hartmann and Stork 1972:66).

The differences between these definitions, as with most others encountered, is a matter of details. Otherwise, the principle underlying them is the same. The uniqueness and peculiarity of the present study is revealed in its motivating factor and the linguistic criteria by which it is guided. Literature reveals that the motivation and criteria guiding dialectal studies are as varied as the number of existing researches in this area of linguistics. Those factors and criteria relevant to this work would be revealed as the work progresses.

2.2 Previous works on Esan

This section highlights aspects of previous works on Esan. The language has enjoyed some scholarship. Most of such works are those carried out by non linguists. Most other serious works do not adequately reflect the multi-varied status which the speakers of the language claim exists. There is a proposed orthography (Ejele and Okojie, 1987). Ejele (1982) carried out a phonological description of the language. Ejele (1986) examines transitivity, tense and aspect in Esan. Another work by the same author on the language examines contour tones in Esan (Ejele,2003). Kamelu (2003) writes on nasalization in Esan, Ijewere (1984) is a Bachelor of Arts project of a description of the processes of word formation in the language, Osiruemu (2005) examines tone and grammar in Esan while Osiruemu (2009) examines the phenomenon of liquid elision as a dialectal index in Esan.

A foremost classificatory work on Esan is Elugbe (1989) where the language is identified as a member of the "Edoid group" along with Ukue, Ehuen, Uhami,

Okpamheri, Emhale, Oloma, the dialect cluster of Okpe - Akuku - Idosa, Ghotuo, Uneme, Yekhee, the dialect cluster of Ora - Emai, Iuleha, Edo, Uvbie, Urhobo, Okpe, Isoko, Eruwa, the dialect cluster of Epie - Atisa, Egene and Degema. Specifically, Esan is grouped with Edo, Ora - Emai - Iuleha, Yekhee, Uneme and Ghotuo as Proto North Central Edoid (PNCE). The Edoid family three as presented in that work is replicated in figure 3.

Figure 3: The Edoid family tree

Key

- PDE - Proto Delta Edoid
- PSWE - Proto South Western Edoid
- PNCE - Proto North Central Edoid
- PNWE - Proto North Western Edoid
- PSNWE - Proto Southern North Western Edoid
- PO - Proto Osse

The Edoid family tree (Culled from Elugbe, 1989:26)

Elugbe describes Edo, Esan and Ora – Emai – Iuleha as "... the languages of the Central plains, where there is relative homogeneity". Although his comparative work of his Edoid languages includes Esan, he states categorically as follows: "I have unfortunately no data on Esan though I have read Akpamu's (1971) phonology of one of the Esan dialects."

Thus, the absence of illustrations from Esan in that work is obviously a result of the dearth of data on Esan mentioned above. This circumstance notwithstanding, some generalizations made about this phylum of the Edoid group in that work, of which Esan is a member, are presented below.

On the phonetics of the Edoid languages, Elugbe made the following observations among many others:

- (1). Consonants of the Edoid languages fall under the sub-groupings of stops, nasals, fricatives, rolls/trills, taps and laterals, and approximants. There are a total of twenty-two oral stops (including affricates). The stops fall into three groups: plosives, affricates and implosives. Some plosives are voiced and others voiceless. Affricates were identified at two points of articulation: the alveolar and palato – alveolar. In addition to the more common [tʃ] and [dʒ], ... the alveolar affricates [ts] and [dz] occur. The implosives [ɓ] and [ɗ] occur only in Delta Edoid, labial-velar stops were found in all the Edoid languages investigated.
- (2). The typical Edoid language is rich in nasals. In some of the languages, it is usually the case that these are seen as allophones of non-nasal phonemes.
- (3). In the Edoid languages, every language has at least, a rhotic, which may be a trill, a tap or an approximant. There are no non-alveolar trills in the Edoid languages.
- (4). The palatal and the labial-velar approximants [j] (IPA [j]) and [w] respectively are the most common approximants in the Edoid languages.
- (5). The vowel qualities were identified for Edoid languages as follows:

[i, e, ε, ɤ, a, ɔ, o, ɒ, u]

No Edoid language employs less than seven vowels in its oral vowel system. Where the system is a seven-vowel one (as in all of NCE), they are

[i, e, ε, a, ɔ, o, u].

- (6). Vowel nasalisation occurs in all the Edoid languages investigated.
- (9). The issue of the formation of glides from underlying vowels is a very productive process in all the Edoid languages.

(10). The tone system of the Edoid languages ranges from three level tones to two level tones with no down step, and two levels plus down step.

Egbokhare (2003) states that Esan, along with Edo or Benin are typical examples of NCE (North Central Edoid) languages. This deduction is probably based on the linguistics characteristics of this languages as identified by Elugbe.

Ejele and Okojie (1987:3) and Okojie (2005:iv) claim that "the thirty five clans of Esan speak various dialects ..." of the language. These clans are given as Amahor, Ebelle, Egoro, Ekpoma, Ekpon, Emu, Ewatto, Ewohimi, Ewosa, Ewu, Ido, Ifeku, Igueben, Ilushi, Irrua, Iyelen, Ogua, Ohordua, Okalo, Okhuesan, Onogholo, Opoji, Orowa, Oria, Ubiaja, Udo, Ugboha, Ugbegun, Ugun, Ujiogba, Ukhun, Urho, Urohi, Uromi and Uzea. They state further that:

while it is easy to recognize a speaker from each clan, the different varieties of Esan are highly mutually intelligible, such that successful communication between speakers is not affected. Such differences, mostly lexical and sometimes tonal are not enough to blur mutual intelligibility...the phonological processes and phonotactic patterns in all Esan dialects are by and large very simila

According to Ejele (1994:69) Esan phonemic system consists of 25 consonant phonemes. She also identifies 7 oral and 5 nasal vowels. These are presented in tables 2A and IIB.

Table 2A: Phonemic consonant chart of Esan

p	b		t	d		k	g	kp	gb
β	f	v	s	z	ʃ	x	ɣ		h
					tʃ	dʒ			
m			n						
			l						
			r						
			j					w	

Table 2B: Phonemic vowel chart of Esan

The nasal vowels contrast with their oral counterparts in words composed of identical segments. These occurrences are presented in table 3A.

Table 3A: Esan Oral and nasal vowels showing contrasts

	Oral vowels	Nasal vowels
i	[i] tì “to boil”	[ĩ] tĩ “to fly”
ii	[ɛ] hɛ “to pack”	[ẽ] hẽ “to climb”
iii	[a] ta “to say”	[ǎ] tǎ “to be tall”
iv	[ɔ] xɔ “to bathe”	[ɔ̃] x̃ “to have a full stomach”
v	[u] otu “age group/mate”	[ũ] útũ “mushroom”

[e] and [o] have no nasal counterparts.

(Okojie and Ejele 1987:6)

The phonological process of nasalization is attested in Esan, as in some other Edoid languages (Ejele, 1994, Kamelu 2003). It occurs as a secondary feature of articulation, where a vowel segment assimilates the nasal quality when it co-occurs with nasal segments. In this environment, nasality spreads from a nasal segment unto one which is not inherently nasal. This occurrence is illustrated in Table 3B.

Table 3B: Nasalisation in Esan.

- (a) /nò/ → [nò̃] “to grind”
- (b) /mù/ → [mũ] “to carry”
- (c) /jèjè/ → [jè̃jè̃] “to compress”
- (d) /mà/ → [m̃pà] “to measure”

(Okojie and Ejele 1987:5)

The elision of the liquid [l] in word final syllables, is attested in Esan. This occurrence is accounted for as a tense and aspect marker in the language (Okojie and Ejele, 1987:4). Ejele (1994:74) explains it as a gradual loss of [l] in word final syllables

in Esan spoken by the younger generation of speakers of the language. These occurrences are illustrated as follows in Table 3C.

Table 3C: liquid elision in Esan.

Full word forms	gloss	l reduction	l+v reduction
(e). ókpèbhòlò	important people	ókpèbhò	ókpèbhò
(f). ilòlò	thought	ilò	ilò
(g). mànlèn	we	màèn	màn
(h). nàlèn	they	nàèn	nàn
(i). òhięle	a fruit	òhièè	òhiè
(j). íhiènlén	beans	íhièén	íhiě

(Ejele 1984:69)

However, Osiruemu (2009) treatment of the phenomenon of liquid elision in Esan establishes it as a dialect marker in the language. In that work it was shown that liquid elision in Esan went beyond a mere difference between speech forms of younger and older generations of Esan speakers as earlier proposed. The feature was shown to be one which distinguished Esan dialects from, while some Esan speech forms were observed to exhibit the phenomenon compulsorily, others did so optionally while for some other speech forms the phenomenon never occurred, even when the phonological conditions were present. A total of 432 Esan lexical items formed the data pool for that work. Data were analysed by simple sound identification, comparison and statistical methods. From the data pool for that study, lexical items which possessed the phonological description relevant to the speech phenomenon under focus (liquid elision) were selected from each of the Esan varieties under focus in that work. This description required that each of such lexical items comprised a minimum of one instance of the liquid / l / or its deletion. Finally, a total of 37 lexical items bearing identical collocations were compared across the twelve Esan varieties for the identification of instances of the presence or absence of the elision of the liquid. Of the 37 lexical items identified, the total number of items featured by each Esan variety ranged between 35 and 24. These figures and their percentile values are presented in the first column of Table 3D. Some findings from that study were:

- (1) Exhibition of the phenomenon of liquid elision in Esan fell within three ranges:
- a. Compulsory liquid elision – this range of the exhibition of /l/ elision referred to Esan speech forms which featured the phenomenon whenever the phonological conditions were present. In that regard, Ugboha was identified as featuring 100% rate of exhibition.
 - b. Optional liquid elision – this range referred to Esan speech forms which exhibited /l/ elision often (but not always) as well as those which did not do so compulsorily. Ugbegun, Ewatto, Uromi, Udo, Ogua, Ekpoma, Ohordua, Igueben and Ilushi fell within this range of Esan speech forms. The value of this range of exhibition fell below 68%.
 - c. Absence of liquid elision – this range referred to Esan speech forms which nearly never exhibited the phenomenon of /l/ elision. With these speech forms, exhibition of the phenomenon could be regarded as anomalous. Ubiaza speech form was foremost in this group featuring 0% exhibition of the phenomenon.
- The study suggested that liquid elision was a probable index of dialectal variation in Esan. This observation was substantiated with a chart showing the extent of the exhibition of the phenomenon across Esan speech forms identified for that study.

Table 3D – Statistical evidence of /l/ elision across identified Esan dialects.

/l/ elision	Ugboha	Ugbegun	Ewatto	Uromi	Udo	Ogua	Ekpoma	Ohordua	Igueben	Hushi	Ubiaza	Irrua
Total no of lexical items featured	35 (95%)	31 (84%)	32 (86%)	32 (86%)	35 (95%)	32 (86%)	30 (81%)	34 (92%)	24 (65%)	32 (86%)	35 (95%)	35 (95%)
No of items featuring /l/ elision	35 (100%)	18 (58%)	7 (22%)	12 (38%)	17 (49%)	18 (56%)	12 (40%)	17 (50%)	16 (67%)	12 (38%)	NIL (0%)	5 (14%)
No of items not featuring /l/ elision	NIL (0%)	13 (42%)	25 (78%)	20 (62%)	18 (51%)	17 (44%)	18 (60%)	17 (50%)	8 (33%)	20 (62%)	35 (100%)	30 (86%)

Okojie and Ejele (1987:6) identify the following tones for Esan at the systematic phonetic level: high, mid, low, rising and falling tones. These are represented respectively as follow: $\acute{v}$ $\tilde{v}$ $\hat{v}$ $\check{v}$ $\grave{v}$. Stating that the mid tone is an allotone of the low, they observe that only the high and low tones distinguish between segmentally identical words. These tone contrasts are presented in Table 4A.

Table 4A: Tonal contrasts in Esan

(k)	/éǵè/	'rat'
(l)	/èǵè/	'edge'
(m)	/éǵpà/	'vomit'
(n)	/èǵpà/	'punch'
(o)	/ǵǵpá/	'one'
(p)	/ǵǵpà/	'cock'
(q)	/áwà/	'dog'
(r)	/àwà/	'taboo'
(s)	/éni/	'elephant'
(t)	/èni/	'there'

(Osiruemu 2005:xxi)

Ejele (2003) states that the falling and rising glides are derivations from phonological processes such as vowel elision. These gliding tones occur following the disyllabification of the first of two adjacent vowels bearing non-identical tones. A falling glide is formed when the tones on the vowel sequence are HL, while a rising glide is formed when the sequence is LH. These gliding tones are exemplified below in Table 4B

Table 4B: Tonal glides in Esan

(i)	'ǵǵpá	#	ǵǵpa	—————>	'ǵǵpâka
(ii)	'one		one'		'one by one'
(iii)	/éǵá	#	éǵá/	—————>	/è v ê v á/
(iv)	'two		two'		in twos'

- (v). /údò # údò/ → /ú d ũ d ò/
 (vi). 'stone stone' → 'all stones'
 (vii). /áwà # áwà/ → /á w ǎ w à/
 (viii). 'dog dog' → 'all dogs'

(Osiruemu 2005:xxii)

Osiruemu (2005), identifies the high (H), low (L), rising (LH) and falling (HL) tones for Esan, at the systematic phonetic level. It argues that the mid tone (M) postulated by Okojie and Ejele (1987) as "... a free variant of L when it occurs in successive syllables of a word", is in reality, a L tone. When this low occurs in sequence in a steady state, as it does in Esan, it sounds like the M tone. The following evidence led to the conclusions reached in that work about the so called M tone in Esan.

- a. This M tone is never found in combination with another level tone but itself. Examples of the occurrence of this tone as given by Okojie and Ejele include the following.

- (ix). /ɔ̃kpā/ 'cock'
 (x). /ēbē/ 'evil'

(Okojie and Ejele 1987:6)

- b. The true nature of this M tone shows up, when the sequence is preceded by a H. It presents clearly as a L tone.

This happening is illustrated below:

- (xi). /únù # ɔ̃kpā/ → /ú n w ɔ̃ k p à /
 mouth cock → cocks mouth
 (xii). /ɔ̃rià # ēbē/ → /ɔ̃ r j è b è /
 Person evil → an evil person

(Osiruemu 2005:xxiv)

The H and L tones occur word initially, medially and finally on lexical items. There are no instances of the HL and LH tones in word initial position.

The same work reveals that the following lexical tonal patterns occur in Esan.

1. Nouns

Nouns in Esan are mostly bisyllabic and trisyllabic. Bisyllabic nouns exhibit the HL, LL, HHL and LHL tonal combinations in citation. These are exemplified in Table 4C.

Table 4C: Lexical tonal patterns in Esan

	<u>HL</u>	
(xiii).	/únù/	'mouth'
(xiv).	/ṣkà/	'maize'
(xv).	/ájɔ/	'wine'
(xvi).	/ámà/	'a mark'
	<u>LL</u>	
(xvii).	/àmè/	'water'
(xviii).	/òxù/	'sky/up'
(xix).	/èkè/	'sand'
(xx).	/ɔkpù/	'anus'
	<u>LHL</u>	
(xxi).	/àbâ/	'father'
(xxii).	/ìvjê/	'coral beads'
(xxiii).	/òkjà/	'man'
(xxiv).	/ɔgb/	'bottle'
	<u>HHL</u>	
(xxv).	/óxwô/	'women'
(xxvi).	/iYô/	'money'

(Osiruemu 2005:xxiv-xxv)

Five tonal combinations occur in trisyllabic nouns. These are HHL; HLL; HLHL; LLL and LHL as exemplified below.

HHL

- (xxvii) /ékéle/ 'belly'
(xxviii) /ɔ́ xɔ́ x' ɔ́/ 'fowl'
(xxix) /úkparù/ 'cap'
(xxx) /ísixũ/ 'termite'

HLL

- (xxxi) /áràlé/ 'blood'
(xxxii) /ólìlì/ 'cold'
(xxxiii) /ádùdù/ 'shadow'
(xxxiv) /áβìlì/ 'oil'

LLHL

- (xxxv) /émìnâ/ 'cow'
(xxxvi) /ágbàṅɔ́/ 'underwear'
(xxxvii) /ólìyî/ 'confusion'
(xxxviii) /íhìlé/ 'beans'

LLL

- (xxxix) /izàgwɔ́/ 'duck'
(XL) /èràlè/ 'fire'
(XLI) /èdɔ́yíɔ́/ 'mucous'
(XLII) /ixùmù/ 'medicine'

LHL

- (XLIII) /ònógbò/ 'cat'
(XLIV) /òkólò/ 'war'
(XLV) /àgógò/ 'bell'
(XLVI) /èmátɔ́/ 'iron/metal'

(Osiruemu 2005:xxv-xxviii)

2. Verbs and Adjunctives

Verbs, and Adjunctives (words used to extend the meaning of another word e.g. adjectives) both occur as monosyllabic and bisyllabic words in Esan. They also both share the cv syllabic structures. Bisyllabic adjunctives sometimes have a vcv structure. As attested in Edoid languages (Elugbe 1973; Amayo 1975), data revealed that tone on verbs in Esan is determined by tense and / or aspectual factors. Adjunctives exhibit similar characteristics. Words of both lexical categories bear L tones underlyingly, when produced in isolation. Examples are presented in Table 4D.

Table 4D: Other lexical tonal patterns in Esan

A. <u>Monosyllabic Verbs</u>		<u>Monosyllabic adjunctives</u>	
1.	/n è/ 'to defecate'	2.	/m ù/ 'sharp'
3.	/d è/ 'to fall'	4.	/dʒǎ/ 'red'
5.	/l è/ 'to eat'	6.	/f w à/ 'white'
7.	/s ǎ/ 'to jump'	8.	t ǎ/ 'long/tall'
B. <u>Bisyllabic Verbs</u>		<u>Bisyllabic adjunctives</u>	
9.	/hòhò/ 'to winow'	10.	/s ɔ̀nɔ̀/ 'irritating'
11.	/h èh è/ 'to escort'	12.	/rjàlà/ 'bitter'
13.	/lwèyè/ 'to shake'	14.	/lèlè/ 'sweet'
15.	/gbɔ̀ɔ̀/ 'to sweep'	16.	/èsì/ 'good'

(Osiruemu 2005:xxviii)

3. Numerals

Numerals in Esan are either bisyllabic or multisyllabic. The basic cardinal numerals (others are mostly descriptive) bear HL and LH (L) tonal patterns as illustrated bellow in Table 4E.

Table 4E: Tonal patterns on numerals in Esan.

HL

- 17. /èà/ 'three'
- 18. /énè/ 'four'
- 19. /èhà/ 'six'
- 20. /úè/ 'twenty'
- 21. /ɔgbà/ 'thirty'

LH

- 22. /ɔkpá/ 'one'
- 23. /èvá/ 'two'
- 24. /isé/ 'five'
- 25. /igbé/ 'ten'

LHL

- 26. /ihílɔ/ 'seven'
- 27. /elélé/ 'eight'
- 28. /isíli/ 'nine'
- 29. /ùgbólɔ/ 'eleven'
- 30. /igbéà/ 'thirteen'

(Osiruemu 2005:xxix-xxx)

Ordinal numerals (excluding the first / ó k à l ò/ which bears a HLL) bear an all L tone pattern in isolation. Some of these lexical items are:

- 30. /ɔzèvá/ 'second'
- 31. /ɔzèà/ 'third'
- 32. /ɔzènè/ 'fourth'
- 33. /ɔzìsè/ 'fifth'
- 34. /ɔzèhà/ 'sixth'
- 35. /ɔzihlɔ/ 'seventh'

36. /zèlèlè/ 'eighth'
 37. /zìgbè/ 'tenth'
 38. /zùgbòlò/ 'eleventh'
 39. /zùè/ 'twentieth'
 40. /zìgbà/ 'thirtieth'

(Osiruemu 2005:xxx)

4. Deictics

Deictics (words which specify individual persons, things or ideas e.g. personal pronouns, demonstratives and place adverbs) occur in Esan. Personal pronouns bear an all L tone pattern underlyingly. They behave like verbs and adjunctives since this tone pattern may change in different syntactic constructions. They are presented in Table 4F.

Table 4F: Tonal patterns on deictics in Esan

- | | | | |
|-----------|-------------|-----------|--------------|
| 41. /imè/ | 'I/me' | 42. /imà/ | 'us/we' |
| 43. /ùwè/ | 'you (sing) | 44. /ìβà/ | 'you (plur)' |
| 45. /lè/ | 'he/she/it' | 46. /èlè/ | 'they/them' |

(Osiruemu 2005:xxxi)

Other deictics exhibit the LL, LHL and HLHL tone patterns. LL is realized on the first dimension of place adverbs and demonstrative pronouns, LH on the second dimension, while the third dimension bears the HLHL tone pattern.

5. Place adverbs and demonstrative pronouns

LL

47. /nà/ 'this'
 49. /ènà/ 'these'

LHL

48. /nî/ 'that'
 50. /ènî/ 'these'

HLHL

51. /nàkè/ 'the other'
 52. /ènèkè/ 'the others'

(Osiruemu 2005:xxxii-xxxiii)

The examination of the tonal patterns which occur in Esan lexical categories reveals the bisyllabic patterns to be HL, LL, HHL and LHL, and the trisyllabic patterns to be HHL, HLL, LLL, LHL, HLH and HLHL. Like her Edoid neighbours of Emai and Edo, Esan does not exhibit an all H lexical tone pattern. Specifically, Esan lexical items do not exhibit a final H tone. All H tones in final position drop to a HL. This phenomenon is so incisive that it cuts across all lexical classes in the language. This HL however drops the L phase when words bearing it associate with other words. While the HL is retained in final positions of sentences, it disappears in initial and medial positions.

2.3 Other related works

It is commonly claimed that most languages are not monolithic. Oyetade (1995:13) gives expression to this situation when he points out that, diversity exists in any given language at all levels of grammar. In the same vein, Crystal (1987:328) states,

Languages are always in a state of flux. Change affects the way people speak as inevitably as it does any other area of human life. Language purists do not welcome it but they can do very little about it. Language would stand still only if society did. A world of unchanging linguistic excellence, based on the brilliance of earlier literary forms exists only in fantasy.

Langacker (1974:317-318) explains that dialectal variation is a result of incomplete diffusion of linguistic changes. Each point of difference stems ultimately from the failure of an innovation to be adopted by all speakers of the language. According to him, distinguishing between a language and a dialect is one of the most difficult theoretical issues in linguistics. He claims further that the criterion of mutual intelligibility is problematic as records show that dialects which belonged to the same language may not always be mutually intelligible in their spoken form.

The main pursuit of this work is to examine Esan language, with the ultimate aim of empirically determining its dialectal status. An important question that needs to be answered if this aim is to be achieved is, "how may dialects be distinguished one from the other?" There are non-linguistic as well as linguistic criteria for distinguishing between dialects of a given language. The motivating factor for such a study would ultimately determine what criteria to choose. Greenberg (1966:1-4) states that the

principle that only linguistic evidence is relevant in drawing conclusions in these matters is so self evident that it would seem unnecessary to state it. Since the present study is a linguistic one, it would be stating the obvious to say that the criteria as well as its motivation are linguistic. Details of the factors specific to the present study are stated in the following chapter.

Concerning comparative and classificatory studies of languages, Francis (1983:8) observes that the theoretical linguist is often disturbed by dialect variation, as this may disrupt or complicate an overtly abstract view of language structure. In his words.

He cannot overlook the facts, and many modern linguists are trying to find ways to deal with dialect differences as an integral part of language, not as something messy and embarrassing.

Local differences in speech have attracted attention for centuries. The earliest beginnings of this attention are most likely to have been born out of curiosity. Conversations between people from different parts frequently turn on language differences. People often find this topic of discussion interesting and become curious about the origins of these differences and their distributions. The literature has it that the study of dialect received the greatest impetus in the 19th century from the development of Comparative Philology (the history of languages and the relationship between them). Philologists who worked by seeking the most 'pure' data in each language, realized with time that, dialects often preserve older and more regular forms than a standard language (Petyt, 1980).

The most important works in dialectology in modern times are said to have appeared in 1821 in Germany. The work by Johann Adrea Schmeller- "The Dialects of Bavaria"- gave a historical – geographical – grammatical presentation of the German language in that area, and included a social map classifying the Bavarian dialects. The first dialect survey is credited to Liebich (1876). Jost Wintoler published a monograph on the dialects of Kerenzen in Canton of Glarus in 1876. The first Great dialect survey is recorded as that of George Wenker (1876) – a work on a survey of the dialects of Dusseldorf, which he later extended to a survey of the whole German empire. During these periods, records have it that the science of phonetics and systems of phonetic transcription were relatively undeveloped.

The second great national survey is said to have begun in France twenty years after, with a call by Gaston Paris in 1888, for a survey of the local dialects of France to be carried out, before they succumbed to the advance of standard French. Jules Gillieron accepted the task, Edmond Edmont did the field work. The work which was in thirteen volumes was published between the years 1902 - 1910.

The literature reveals that early comparative works on African languages have been geared towards the classification or grouping of these languages into language families according to their perceived relatedness. Bernd (1974:7) lends credence to this observation when he states that:

Most comparative work in the field of African languages have focused on the discovery of genetic relationships, as if there are no other equally interesting goals that language comparison can achieve.

One of the earliest recorded attempts at the study of dialects of any African language is that by Koelle (1954) which comprises an assemblage of words from dialects of some African languages collected from freed and resettled slaves in Sierra Leone. The work is said to have contained a word list of 12 dialects of Yoruba, and was fraught with limitations. These limitations included inaccuracies of transcription that lacked proper planning for dialectological survey (Oyetade 1995). Adetugbo (1967 cf Oyetade 1995) carried out a dialectological study of Yoruba. He classified Yoruba into three major areas - North Western Yoruba (NWY), South - Eastern Yoruba (SEY) and Central Yoruba (CY). Using isoglosses, he was able to show lexical, grammatical and phonological peculiarities of each of these dialect areas. Brown (1968) worked on the dialect situation in Boguisu, an effort which was mainly concerned with consistent phonetic variation. Duitsman, Bertkan and Leasa, (1975) carried out a survey of Kru dialects. Their aim included determining the number of Kru dialects and their locations, determining the nature of their interrelationships and gaining an understanding of the relationships between Kru and the languages adjacent to it.

Akinkugbe (1978), is a comparative work on the phonology of the Yoruba dialects of Isekiri and Igala. Oyetade (1995) made a preliminary statement on the

linguistic varieties in Yoruba. Ubahakwe et al (1975) carried out a comprehensive survey of the Igbo dialects with the following aims:

1. To determine the number and boundary delineations of the dialects
2. To assess the levels of mutual intelligibility and acceptability among the speakers of the dialects.
3. To identify the dialect that stands the best chance of being the most widely acceptable standard literary dialect of the language.

At the end of that survey twenty distinct dialects with clear cut boundaries and without the usual transition zones were identified.

More recent works are Udoh (2003), which is a preliminary report on the varieties of Legbo, an Upper Cross language, spoken by the Agbo community of Cross River State of Nigeria. In that work, comparative data were presented and reconstructed to show that the Leyigha and Lenyima varieties should be numbered among the Legbo varieties. Lewis (2003) examined the controversy in classifying a language group called Okphamheri, situated in the Savannah belt of the North West of Edo State. In that work, linguistic evidence were explored along the lines of phonology and diachrony. The focus of that work was on genetic relationship, cognate percentages, sound changes and sound laws. The role of tones, as a classificatory parameter was not given any consideration.

Literature on most previous researches in dialectology reveals that the approach to this field of study may be separated into two parts as follows:

1. The methods of data collection
2. The methods of data analysis

The mode of data collection may be direct or indirect. The indirect method, which was that used in the earliest dialect surveys, involves collecting samples of speech without the supervision of the researcher or an expert (with the earliest attempts, this process was carried out by sending and receiving completed questionnaires by post) and analyzing them linguistically. The direct method, involves investigation by a field worker, who asked informants questions about their dialects, and collected data thereby (Gumperz 1971; Petyt 1980). Gumperz (1971:2) states further that in the United States, where the great majority of the population speaks English, the result obtained by the two methods

usually agreed, whereas in India, where dialects were many, this was by no means the case. Also important to a study of this nature is the caliber of field workers who collect data. As is to be expected, a skilled phonetician, who is able to use a detailed and unambiguous phonetic transcription, would enhance more accurate data collection, which would in turn enhance a successful analysis of data. Employing one field worker would also ensure uniformity of procedure in data collection, and minimise errors.

The methods used with the French survey are said to have set the pattern for future projects. The main principles of operation in the French survey involved the following steps. A preliminary investigation or pilot survey of the way, usages, and dialects of the language of interest was conducted. This step was followed by a preparation of a network of geographical points in the locality at which fieldwork is to be conducted, depending on financial, manpower resources, and time available for survey. Thereafter, a list of features of investigation such as a list of items to be investigated – is drawn up. These features could be phonetic, phonological, semantic, or syntactic. Field work is then conducted, where one or more trained investigators go to the selected localities and make contact with the people they considered most suitable informants. Data which are collected either in phonetic transcription or tape recordings, are then sorted and put in suitable order for editing and publication.

Present day studies in dialectology appear to involve more rigorous analyses of data. New and various methods of data analysis have also evolved. The comparative method, which is a technique for establishing the genetic relatedness of a group of languages and for reconstructing, to some degree, the proto-language from which they descend, was developed by philologists during the 19th century. It involves the systematic comparison of a series of languages, in order to prove a historical relationship between them. A set of formal similarities and differences between them are identified. Langacker (1974) states that this method was first applied to the Indo-European family of languages. He states that the cornerstone of this method is the notion of sound correspondences, where phonetic or phonological features are checked for degree of relatedness. According to him, this method, while often adequate for demonstrating relationship, is not best suited for investigation of sub grouping.

Lexicostatistical glottochronology is an approach to the study of languages, with the aim of determining their level of mutual intelligibility, and classifying them into types and groups. It was devised in the late 1940s by the American linguists Morris Swadesh and Robert Lees. It is used to work out the length of time which has lapsed since two languages thought to be related began to diverge. The technique is used by counting the number of similar words between the languages in question, using the sample of vocabulary taken from them, with the relevant word list. The lower the number of vocabulary agreement between two samples, the longer the languages have been separated. Thus, two languages which have 60% vocabulary in common would be thought to have diverged longer ago than languages which have 80%.

This approach to language relatedness has met with criticisms because of its perceived shortcomings. Bennett and Sterk (1977), state that although this method of data analysis is useful for preliminary sub-grouping, it is not – if used alone – adequate for indication of fine degrees of relationship. They opine that the nature of this method of analysis is such that geographic and social proximity tend to increase cognacy scores significantly. Hymes (1964) drew attention to the semantic difficulties encountered in using the same test list across cultures. Modifications resulting in the need to surmount such difficulties impede standardization of studies in lexical relationships. Akinkugbe (1978:44-46) explains that lexicostatistics lacks uniform cut-off points and a means of quantifying degrees of similarities among cognates – a measure of reliability which is invaluable to dialectology. Swadesh suggested that speech forms scoring below 86% cognacy relatedness be regarded as belonging to different languages and those scoring above 86% as belonging to the same languages. Williamson (1973b) takes scores below 80% to mean that speech forms “clearly” belong to different languages and between 81% and 85% “arguably” belong to different languages (cf Akinkugbe 1978). The consensus about the use of lexicostatistics is that since the method is not complete in itself, results have to be checked with other types of evidence.

In his dialectal study of Igbo, Ubahakwe (1981) developed a new instrument, which he called Lexico – Semantic Technique (LST), which he says, follows basically the same techniques as employed in traditional dialect geography. The towns with an aggregate 50 percentage agreement and above on the test list of lexical items were taken

as belonging to the same dialect. Sentences and passages were used to assess levels of mutual intelligibility and these were scored. To identify the dialect that promised to gain the widest acceptance among the various dialect groups, two criteria were applied. These were measures of;

- (a) The dialect with the minimum lexical divergence with the rest
- (b) The "priority value" of the dialect

The "priority value" of a dialect is the sum of the weighted values of the intelligibility and acceptability scores.

Ubahakwe 1981:141.

Ebobisse (1989), using a technique termed dialectometry, measured and classified certain languages and dialects spoken within the Coastal region of Cameroun. According to him, the use of the technique helped to reduce the previously overestimated number of Cameroun languages and dialects. Dialectometry is said to be a subdivision of general dialectology, with which it shares the "common" notion of dialect, but from which it differs in aims and methods (Ebobisse 1989:57). According to him, the term dialectometry means the totality of methods and processes permitting the measurement of the proximity or the linguistic distances between languages and or dialects, of a given geographical area, on the basis of linguistic phenomena peculiar to the region concerned. Its principle is that of comparison in pairs. Starting from a corpus presenting necessary similarities and differences, all the dialects of a region are compared between themselves. He gives the following as the dialectometrical formula

$$\frac{DX(D-1) \times E}{2}$$

2

where D represents the number of dialects and E the number of linguistic elements to be compared.

The method was applied for the first time to the African languages in the region of Mount Kenya by Molilig (1974 cf Ebobisse 1989). From Ebobisse's definition of dialectometry, all methods used to measure the linguistic differences between the possible varieties of a given language at a given time, would be called dialectometry. The

following chapter is a presentation of the methodology and theoretical framework within which the current research was conducted.

Conclusion

In this second chapter of this dialect study of Esan, previous relevant linguistic studies were identified and reviewed. These works fell into two groups as follows:

- a. Previous related works on Esan
- b. Other related works.

The first group of reviewed literature included those most closely relevant to the language and subject of study. The second group of works reviewed included earlier dialectal studies, which even though not concerning Esan could contribute to the present study. The aim of this exercise was to create the needed basis and precedence on which the present study could be based and from which it could benefit.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY FOR ANALYSIS OF DATA

3.1 Theoretical framework for analysis

Methods for the study of variation in language have developed from the earliest beginnings from what is termed traditional dialectology, which is primarily concerned with collecting and displaying language variation in as much detail as possible (Francis 1983:145) to theoretical frameworks within which dialectology is perceived as a branch of the field of general linguistics and hence has the additional responsibility of developing theories of language variation and distribution which are contributory to a general theory of language. One of the earliest of such frameworks, and within which the present study was conducted is that of structural dialectology.

3.1.1 Structural dialectology

Structural dialectology is the study of variation in language from the structural viewpoint of modern linguistics termed structural linguistics, which gave rise to the school of linguistic study called structuralism. The central tenet of structural dialectology is that any variety of a language is a system whose constituents are defined in terms of their mutual opposition and functions in relation to one another, rather than by anything outside the system. This hypothesis is illustrated by the analogy of two languages which possess an identical sound inventory, giving the impression of being linguistically related. It is in the examination of the functions of these sounds within each particular language that the differences between them may be revealed for, sounds which are contrastive in one language could be complementary in the other. Therefore, due to differing functions of a given sound inventory, the differences in two languages are clarified.

Ferdinand de Saussure's "Course in General Linguistics" which was post-humorously published by his students in 1916 is usually adopted as the starting point of structuralism. This approach to linguistic study which was carried on by the Prague School in Europe and the American works of Edward Sapir, Leonard Bloomfield and other notable linguists is credited with shifting the emphasis from the individual linguistic elements to the systems of which they are parts, and from the history of the changes

which the individual elements have undergone to the synchronic description of the overall organization of the language or dialect (Francis 1983:159). In other words, it is the approach to the study of language which holds that no element of language can be analysed in isolation from other elements of the same language. It is in this dichotomy between focus on individual linguistic elements and the systems of which they are part that the difference between the traditional and the structural approaches to the study of dialects is to be found.

Structural dialectology as a branch of structural linguistics is therefore defined as "an approach which examines dialect features in relation to their place in the system of their dialects" (Petytt 1980:120). This approach to the study of variation in language was borne out of the difficulty of demarcating important dialect divisions indicated by the network of different isoglosses which traditional dialectologists are accustomed to drawing. The literature reveals that most of these isoglosses which mark speech differences of a language in a given area do not run together throughout their length, a factor which makes it difficult to determine dialect division of the area. In such a situation of a network of isoglosses, dialectologists have had to depend on non-linguistic factors such as political divisions or cultural differences in deciding about dialect areas because their linguistic data did not seem to offer an answer. It was the effort of using linguistic data to identify the more significant dialectal variants of a language which marked the important dialect divisions that gave rise to the birth of structural dialectology.

Trubetzkoy (1931) is credited with the earliest beginnings of this approach to the study of dialects, because he was about the first to expose the problem of identifying significant dialect features and divisions of a language from the structural viewpoint of modern linguistics. However, the later growth and development of structural dialectology is generally associated with Weinreich (1954) and other dialectologist – linguists such as Stankieweiz (1957), Catford, (1957b), Cochrane (1959), Moulton (1960) and Ri-ggard (1965). According to Petyt (1980:117), Trubetzkoy observed that ...

... not all differences of pronunciation are alike in their relation to the sound systems of the dialects concerned. In particular, it is possible to distinguish between phonetic and phonological differences. Phonetic differences can be gradual... But phonology is a more clear-cut matter. A dialect either does or does not make a particular phonemic distinction.

He identified three main types of sound differences as follows:

- (I) Differences of phonological system.
This sound difference is subdivided into two as follows:
 - A. Differences of inventory in which dialects may differ in the types and number of sounds which constitute the phonetic system.
 - B. Differences of distribution which refers to the differences in the rules of the combination of segments in dialects, which may possess identical, sound inventories.
- II. Differences in the phonetic realization of phonemes which refers to the different physical manifestations of a given phoneme across two or more dialects.
- III. Differences in the incidence of phonemes which refers to the occurrence of particular phonemes in particular words across dialects. In other words a different phoneme would occur in the same set of words in different dialects.

Trubetzkoy postulated that a recognition of these different types of differences and a decision on which is most important would simplify the task of the dialectologist.

Weinreich (1954) gave impetus to a series of articles on the subject (Petyt 1980:120). Francis (1980) states that the discussion and amplification which Weinreich's proposals received from other dialectologists - linguists, as well as their application in subsequent dialect studies constitute the structural school of dialectology, which currently dominates linguistic and dialectal theories. Weinreich's major contributions to the development of structural dialectology included an attempt to bridge the gap between traditional dialectology - described as 'item centered' or 'atomistic' because interest is focused on individual facts of the variable distribution of a single linguistic feature without relating them to the overall structure of the dialects involved - and structural dialectology - which holds that individual linguistic items, particularly but not exclusively sounds, are significant not in themselves but in their position in one of the

closed systems of the language. This situation may be illustrated with a language (language x) having three front vowels, / i, e, ae /. A split occurs by which 50% of the words containing /e/ come to have /ε/, resulting in a system of four front vowels. There follows a merger in which the /ε/ words came to have /ae/. The language will again come to have a three front vowel system, but with a different distribution across its lexicon. The difference between the descriptions of the traditional 'atomistic' dialectologist and that of the structural dialectologist is that even though both description would show the hypothetical language as comprising three dialects, (A,B,C,) the former would not reflect the merger between /ε/ and /ae/, whereas the later would.

In this regard, Weinreich, who was both a structuralist and a dialectologist introduced what he termed a "diasystem" and formulated structural descriptions or diagrams for representing dialectal differences in a given language.

3.1.2 The Diasystem

A diasystem is defined as

... a system of a higher level [constructed] out of the discreet and homogeneous systems that are derived from description and that represent each a unique formal organization of expression and content.

(Weinreich 1954:390 cf Francis 1983:162).

By this definition, the diasystem may be perceived as a structural description formulated by the linguist which embodies both the similarities and differences between the individual systems of the dialects of a language. Cochrane (1959) holds that a proper description of a speech community required the setting up of such a higher level system embracing several partially different systems, as a symbol of what actually occurred when members of the community who have different systems converse with one another. This view of the diasystem corroborates Weinreich's that it has a psychological reality for bilingual as well as "bidialectal speakers"

The primary aim of formulating the diasystem was to clarify and expose those linguistic features of the dialects of a language which truly showed them as different

varieties of that language and which were left unattended by traditional dialectology. It is aimed at resolving the dilemma of the dialectologist who is faced with the task of comparing different systems within one system. In his diasystem, Weinreich points out that the differences between dialects are of two kinds-differences of inventory and differences of distribution. He suggested formulaes and diagrams for expressing these two instances of a diasystem. These formulaes which were further developed and improved upon by other structural dialectologists are presented below.

3.1.3 Structural description in structural dialectology

Weinreich (1954) suggested that where two dialects (X, Y) had identical short vowel inventories for example, the situation could be expressed as follows:

$$A^1 \quad x, y \quad // \quad i \approx e \approx a \approx o \approx u \quad //$$

If the two dialects had different sets of front vowels, the situation could be represented as follows:

$$A^2 \quad x, y, \quad // \quad \frac{x/i \sim e \sim a /}{y/i \sim e \sim \epsilon \sim a /} \approx o \approx u \quad //$$

The double slashes enclosed a diasystem and the double tilde showed that more than one system was being described. The single slash and tilde are used when describing only one of the dialects. The single slash also indicates phonemes while the single tilde is also to be read as 'contrast with'.

The diasystem as used by Weinreich was found to be inadequate because it could only account for phonemic inventory and not phonological aspects of the dialects described. It was argued that his diagrams did not reflect the fact that the dialects described belonged to the same language, especially in its failure to reflect different types of pronunciation differences between areas. Stankiewicz (1957 cf. Petyt 1980:123)

suggested that a reflection of pronunciation differences between areas would provide an answer to two problems of dialectologists as follows:

- (1). The problem of defining discreteness which refers to that of deciding which isogloss shows the most important division between a number of dialects.
This problem confronted traditional dialectology and was often resolved arbitrarily or by resorting to extra – linguistic criteria (Petyt, 1980:123).
- (2). The problem of defining continuity or similarity between separate systems.

He suggested that the classification of dialects on the basis of their phonemic inventory would solve the problem of defining discreteness between dialects because dialects either do or do not make the same phonemic distinctions, whether or not phonetic realizations were identical. He also suggested that the problem of continuity could be handled in part through the examination of phonetic realization because a measure of similarity between different phoneme systems was the extent to which they used the same phonetics.

Cochrane (1959 cf Petyt 1980:123) expanded and developed these suggestions by arguing that comparisons at the phonemic level – which he called diaphonemic comparisons – must be kept separate from that at the phonetic level - diaphonic comparisons, which concerned differences in phonetic realization of phonemes across dialects. He suggested that the diasystem could be used to express differences of distribution as follows. If, as in German, a dialect only permits /s + t/ at the beginning of words, where standard German has /ʃ + t/, this occurrence could be represented as in A3.

A3

$$\begin{array}{c} // \\ \frac{X \# \int t}{Y \# s t} \\ // \end{array} \approx \dots //$$

He also pointed out that the question of similarity or differences between two variations could not be handled simply in terms of inventory distribution and realization without reference to ‘lexical correspondences’, which Trubetzkoy termed ‘etymological distribution’, Weinreich, ‘distribution’, and which is also referred to as ‘incidence’. He argued that:

... two varieties could have identical inventories of phonemes, with identical phonetic realizations and identical combinatorial possibilities, and yet ... sound very different because of differences in which phoneme occurs in particular words.

(Petyt 1980:125).

In this regard, Moulton (1960:175 cf Francis 1989:163) argued that there was nothing to show in Weinreich's diasystems that the dialects so described belonged to the same language as they could be perceived as different languages, showing an identical phoneme inventory. He illustrated his argument with two Swiss German dialects which have identical inventories of eleven short vowels. If lexical incidence is disregarded, they are shown to be diasystematically related as well as phonemically identical. When lexical correspondences are taken into account, they shared only one diaphoneme in full. The diagrams are presented below.

A⁴ (1). With lexical correspondences disregarded:

Lu, Ap // i ≈ e ≈ ε ≈ ae ≈ a ≈ ɔ ≈ u ≈ Ü ≈ ö ≈ ɔ //

(2). With lexical correspondences included

Lu, Ap // $\frac{\text{Lu} / i_0 \sim e_1 \sim \epsilon_2 \sim ae_{3,4}}{\text{Ap} / i_0, \sim e_{1,2} \sim \epsilon_3 \sim ae_4} \approx / a_4 / \approx \frac{/ \text{ɔ}_2 \sim o_1 \sim u_0 \sim \ddot{U}_0 \sim \ddot{O}_1 \sim \text{ɔ}_2 /}{/ \text{ɔ}_2 \sim o_{1,2} \sim u_0, \sim u_{1,2} \sim o_{1,2} \sim \text{ɔ}_2 /}$ //

Each subscript number beside a given sound indicates the number of lexical items which feature the sound. Thus for instance, it is clear that the set of words with /e/ in Ap is split between /e/ and /ε/ in Lu, and that the words with /ae/ in Lu are split between /ε/ and /ae/ in Ap. This diagram shows that there has been a split and merger in each dialect, but in different parts of the system.

The question of the diasystem and how it should be formalised has continued and many modern day dialectologists are found to have a structural orientation, whether or not they write diasystems, as most recognize that phonetic differences differ and have

different effects on phonological systems. The formulation of a diasystem would be determined by the interest of the dialectologist.

Francis (1983) points out that in a structural study of two or more 'lects' considered as dialects of the same language, the relationship between them is a function of the two factors of linguistic relatedness and distance which are complementary and each of which may range from zero to unity. Therefore, two lects whose relatedness is zero cannot belong to the same language. The aim in this dialect study of Esan is to satisfy and provide information about these two complimentary factors of relatedness and distance between Esan speech forms in determining their dialectal status. The method employed for the analysis of data in this work makes provision for fulfilling these two factors of relationship.

The pioneering nature of the present study dictates its limited coverage of all the probable aspects of a structural study as outlined thus far. It focuses mainly on the phonetic and phonological level of comparison between Esan speech forms as a starting point for a structural study of Esan dialects. In this regard, the resulting diasystems from this study would be diaphonic rather than diaphonemic

3.2 Methodology

3.2.1 Data and instrumentation

The main instrument with which data were elicited for the present study, was the "Ibadan Word list of 400 Basic Items". This word list, which is a standardized document for studies of this nature, is a product of the Department of Linguistics and African Languages of the University of Ibadan. The list comprises three main sections. Section 1 consists of personal information about the informant, including name and age. Information about the language and the particular Esan variety spoken by the informant is also supplied in this section. Section 2 contains a list of 400 basic lexical items in English language, whose Esan equivalents were provided by the informant. These items cover the lexical domains of body parts, food items, body wastes, plant and animal names, objects and implements, the elements, emotions, the professions, titles, human relations, numerals and human activities. Section 3 comprises 32 pronouns, made up of both the personal and interrogative. The total number of items on which this work is based comes

to 432. Not all the identified Esan speech forms recorded 100% returns of this number of lexical items. However, none of them recorded less than 400 lexical items. Phonological processes, which were observed to accompany the production of lexical items by subjects, were taken into consideration in the transcription of these items. This engendered the capturing of linguistic similarities as well as differences between these speech forms. The final analysis were based on available data. All informants were adult native speakers of the twelve Esan speech forms, which were identified from preliminary oral investigations about the informants impressions in that regard.

The researcher, who was the sole fieldworker, adopted the direct interview method of investigation in collecting data for this study. This strategy was to ensure uniformity, and a minimal degree of error. Data were collected in phonetic tradition using the IPA format of transcription. Tones were compulsorily marked on all speech forms collected.

3.2.2 Methods of data analysis

The first part of this survey examined the sound inventories, as well as phonological processes found to be indicative of the dialectal status of each of the twelve Esan speech forms under study in this work. For this aspect of the study, simple sound discovery procedures were employed. Discovery procedures in this study entailed the identification and isolation of all sounds in use in each identified Esan speech form as obtained from available data. At the end of the exercise, a phonetic inventory emerged for each speech form. This inventory provided the input for a diaphonic description of Esan dialects. The second part of this study comprised a lexical comparison across identified Esan speech forms, for which principles of lexicostatistical glottochronology were employed. For the third part of this study, which compared micro grammatical markers in the lexicon of Esan speech forms, simple regular morpheme identification and comparison were employed.

3.2.2.1 Lexicostatistical glottochronology

This long standing approach to the historical study of languages was devised by the American linguists, Morris Swadesh and Robert Lees in the late 1940s (Crystal 1987:331). It's main aim was to determine the length of time which had elapsed since two languages, thought to be related, began to diverge. It works by the comparative

method, which is a way of systematically comparing a series of languages, in order to prove a historical relationship between them. A set of formal similarities and differences are identified between the languages in question. The outcome of these comparisons form the basis for reaching conclusions about the relatedness of these languages.

The terms "glottochronology" and "lexicostatistics" are usually used interchangeably. However, the literature reveals that there is a distinction between them. Glottochronology is the name of the study lexicostatics, the name of the technique it uses (Crystal, 1987). Glottochronology has the goal of assigning a date to the split up of some languages into daughter languages, whereas lexicostatistics is the statistical handling of lexical material for historical inferences, which may not necessarily be associated with dates (Campbell, 1998:177).

The distinction stated above makes it necessary to identify which aspect of this approach to the comparative study of language is relevant to, and adopted in this work. The present effort is a study in dialectology. Its goal is the determination of dialectal composition of Esan language, rather than that of proving a historical relationship between it (Esan) and another language or languages. In other words, the historical time of branching of Esan speech forms or dialects is not part of the goal in this study. The focus in this study is the degree of relatedness between the identified Esan speech forms. The present study is therefore purely synchronic and not diachronic. For this reason, the approach of lexicostatistical glottochronology will not be relevant, in its entirety, to the present study. For further clarifications about the choice of approach for this work, a further look is taken at the historical background, some basic assumptions, strengths and weaknesses of lexicostatistical glottochronology, as recorded over time.

i. Historical background

Morris Swadesh began his approach to language sub-grouping, by trying to determine the trends involved in vocabulary change within particular language families. He discovered that, not only were there constant trends within particular language families, but that the rate of change was the same across languages, irrespective of family affiliations (Campbell, 1998:179). He began with a basic vocabulary of 500 words. This was reduced to 250, to 200, and finally to the 100-word list. In developing

glottochronology, he examined 13 test cases, where vocabulary change could be checked against written evidence. According to Campbell, in these cases, he compared modern versions of English, Germanic and Swedish (Germanic languages) with older attested stages of each language. The fact that only 2 of these 13 languages are non Indo-European, has raised doubts about the method.

ii. Basic assumptions

Lexicostatistical glottochronology is hinged on 4 basic assumptions, all of which have been faulted. These assumptions as presented.

1. Basic vocabulary – There exists a core vocabulary which is universal, relatively culture free, and is therefore less subject to change or replacement than general vocabulary. In this regard, Swadesh (1955) compiled a 100-word list, while Gudschinsky (1956) also compiled a 200-word list (Sammarin 1966:219). The most natural and neutral translations of these concepts are assembled and compared in two or more languages thought to be related. Forms which are perceived as cognates are given a check mark; the dates when these languages separated from one another is calculated, based on the number of shared cognates. The lower the number of vocabulary agreements between languages, the longer the languages are assumed to have been separated. Swadesh and Lees found that on average, 2 languages would have 86% vocabulary in common, after 1,000 years of separation (Crystal 1987:331). Thus they suggested that, speech forms scoring below 86% resemblances be regarded as belonging to different languages, and those scoring above 86% as belonging to the same languages (Akinkugbe 1987:44).
2. Constant rate of retention through time – The rate of retention of items of basic vocabulary is relatively constant through time. Thus, a language would retain about 86% of the words of the 100 – word list each 1,000 years, and 81% of the 200 – word list, which was replaced by the 100 – word list, because it was found to be insufficiently culture free.
3. Constant rate of loss cross – linguistically – The rate of loss of basic vocabulary is relatively constant for all languages. Thus, it is assumed that all languages lose about 14% of the 100 – word list each 1,000 year period in their history.

4. Calculation of the date of divergence – The number of years since languages split from an earlier ancestor can be computed, when the number of cognates in the basic vocabulary list shared by related languages is known.

iii. Criticisms

The literature revealed that lexicostatistical glottochronology as an approach to the historical study of languages, is a controversial one, which has met with several criticisms over the years. Some linguists still recommend its use, not because of the validity of its claims, but because it is the most widely known (Samarin, 1966:219). Other historical linguists have rejected it because, for them, it has proven misleading and should be avoided (Campbell, 1998:177). Some of these criticisms are presented below.

Crystal (1987), states that it has been argued that it is impossible to construct a word list that shows no cultural bias. For example, the items 'sun' and 'moon', which appear on the list, have great religious significance in some cultures. In this regard, Campbell (1998:180) states that, many of the items on the list are not culture free, but are borrowed for cultural reasons in a number of languages. She exemplifies this argument thus:

In the case of (21) 'dog', while native peoples of Central America had dogs before the coming of the Spanish, their dog was small, hairless and barkless, and served as a food item. The big hairy noisy dogs which arrived with Europeans, were not easily equated with the native dogs... many groups borrowed the foreign name for 'dog' and eventually came no longer to have a native term for dog.

She rejects the assumption of this approach that there will be a direct one to one matching between each numbered notion in the word list, and a word of each language, as according to her, this is not very often the case. Languages very often have more than one neutral equivalent. Also, some languages make no distinction between two separate items on the list. She states, as examples, that the items (17) 'man' and (18) 'person' are homogenous in many languages. Also, some languages do not distinguish (27) 'bark' from (28) 'skin', or (36) 'feather' from (37) 'hair', pointing out that results of analysis with such inputs could be skewed.

Dixon (1997) argues that there is no universal principle that core vocabulary is less likely to be borrowed than non core items, and thus cannot be taken as an axiom for the postulation of genetic relatedness. It is also argued that the rate of change may not be equal for all languages, and that the analysis of more known language histories was necessary for the 86% figure to be truly convincing. Crystal states that:

... the method becomes less definite the further back in History it goes and the slightest of errors in compilation of the word sample could result in great inaccuracy...

Campbell describes as unrealistic the notion of attaching a precise date to the split – ups of language families, since these processes are not usually sudden, but gradual. The literature reveals that Swadesh was fully aware of the limitations of the procedure but argued that there must be a balance between the forces which maintain uniformity in language, and those which encourage fluctuation, pointing out that it is possible to obtain ancillary evidence from archeology.

In spite of the controversies generated by this approach to comparative studies of languages, several scholars still employ it in their work, with the common excuse that no suitable alternative technique has been devised. The position in this work however is that the reason for the continued patronage of this severally criticized approach to the study of sub-grouping of languages goes beyond the absence of a 'suitable alternative technique'. Samarine (1966:219) recommends the word lists to the field worker, not because of the validity of the claims of glottochronology, but because they are the most widely known, and for the desirability of having as much uniformity as possible in comparative studies. He however opines that:

For other purposes – for example, in the determination of dialect differences – one will certainly want to add other words, because one's goal is as much to measure change in cultural vocabulary, as it is to measure retention of the basic vocabulary.

It is with the insight gained from the knowledge of the shortcomings of lexicostatistical glottochronology that its use in the present work has been adjusted to suit its main goal of identifying Esan dialects. To ensure that these shortcomings do not totally mar this goal

therefore, other grammatical and methodological considerations are introduced and adopted in this study and considered legitimate.

For the reasons explicated above, which among other things show that a total adoption of lexicostatistical glottochronology, in its entirety, would not adequately address the aims and goals of the present study, we deviate in methodology for the purpose of this work thus:

- (a) The 'Ibadan Word List of 400 Basic Items', rather than Swadesh's 100-word list is adopted as the main instrument for data elicitation.
- (b) The lexicostatistical method for the analysis of data is adopted as well as the cut off levels (86%) for determining relatedness between speech forms.
- (c) Lexical items on the word list would be compared on the basis of complete similarity and dis-similarity, rather than cognation, across the identified Esan speech forms under focus.
- (d) Consideration would be given to micro grammatical forms in Esan in the identification of Esan dialects.

3.2.3 Research procedures

The researcher conducted analysis of available data in five stages as follows:

- (1). Diaphonic Analysis
- (2). Lexico-statistical and tonostatistical Analysis
- (3). Comparisons of micro grammatical markers across Esan speech forms.
Other research consideration of Esan speech forms included the following
- (4). Levels of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms
- (5). The Esanness of Esan: Structural differences between Esan and her closest neighbours

3.2.3.1 Diaphonic analysis

Sound inventories which emerged for each identified Esan speech form were compared one with the other. This comparison, formed part of the diaphonic analysis for this work. Extents of the occurrence of phonological processes of glide formation and liquid elision were compared, as these were found to be prevalent and most relevant to

the goals of the present study. The outcomes of these comparisons were formalized and provided input for a diasystem for identified Esan dialects.

3.2.3.2 Lexicostatistical and tonostatistical analysis

At this level of analysis, lexical items were compared across the identified Esan speech forms to further determine their levels of relatedness.

This comparison was conducted between a pair of Esan speech forms at a time until all twelve speech forms were compared with one another. In this regard, only strictly identical, and non identical linguistic forms were relevant for determining relatedness in this work. To this end, the relevant linguistic forms were counted. The resulting sums were subsequently converted to percentile values, using the following simple statistical formulae:

Lexicostatistical formulae

The statistical formulae by which the analysis of available data were conducted for this work were as follows. Three variables – y, x, z – were introduced to capture the lexical relationships between Esan speech forms under study. The values of these variables are:

- A. y $\longrightarrow$ total number of items compared between two given speech forms at a given time.
- B. x $\longrightarrow$ total number of identical items between two given Speech forms at a given time.
- C. z $\longrightarrow$ total number of unidentical items between two given speech forms at a given time.

To calculate the value of each given variable, the following formula was used.

D. $x + z = y$

This formula taken for each variable would translate into the following two simple formulae.

(i). $x = y - z$

(ii). $z = y - x$

To calculate the percentile values of these variables, the following formula was applied.

$$E. \quad \frac{(x,z) \times 100}{y} = \frac{(x,z)\%}{y}$$

Taken simply for each variable, this formula would read as follows

$$(iii) \quad \frac{X \times 100}{y} = \frac{x\%}{y}$$

$$(iv) \quad \frac{z \times 100}{y} = \frac{z\%}{y}$$

With these formulae, percentage scores between the speech forms under study were generated.

Besides phonetic, phonological and segmental considerations, tonal permutations on lexical items across the Esan speech forms formed the basis for tonostatistical analysis in the work. The researcher conducted comparisons between the lexicons of the Esan speech forms along the following three sub-parameters:

- (1). Relatedness between Esan speech forms considering both segmental and tonal constitution of lexical items.
- (2). Relatedness between Esan speech forms considering only segmental constitution of lexical items.
- (3). Relatedness between Esan speech forms considering only tonal patterning on lexical items.

This exercise resulted in close to 70 comparisons, and about 410 calculations to arrive at the statistical evidence presented in this work. Each comparison yielded statistical values which formed a major criteria for determining the linguistic relatedness between Esan speech forms. Percentile limits for determining levels of linguistic relatedness between Esan speech forms in this work were as prescribed by the lexicostatistics of Swadesh and Lees:

- (1). Percentage values showing linguistic relatedness of 86 and above would suggest that Esan speech forms were close enough to be regarded as belonging to the

same dialect. Such linguistic relatedness are considered insufficient to mar mutual intelligibility.

- (2). Percentage values showing linguistic relatedness below 86 would suggest that Esan speech forms were distant enough to be considered separate dialects.

3.2.3.3 Comparison of micro-grammatical markers in pronoun and lexical counting systems

Data analysis included identification and comparison of grammatical markers in the pronoun and lexical counting systems across Esan speech forms. A comparison of the identified grammatical markers served as a further parameter for identifying the relatedness of the identified speech forms to ameliorate the shortcomings of lexicostatistical glottochronology as earlier enunciated (see 3.2.2.1).

3.2.3.4 Determinations of levels of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms

Esan speech forms were also examined for the levels of mutual intelligibility which may exist between them. In that regard, speech forms showing linguistic relatedness of percentage values of 86 and above were regarded as highly mutually intelligible while those showing linguistic relatedness below percentage value of 86 were regarded as linguistically distant enough for mutual intelligibility to be marred.

3.2.3.5 The "Esanness" of Esan

An attempt was made to determine structural differences which may exist between Esan and her closest linguistic neighbours as a way of identifying some structural peculiarities of Esan which distinguish her from the latter. In this regard, only the parameters of sounds and tones were used as points of reference, as this information was not basic to the main focus of the present study.

Conclusion

This third chapter of this dialect study of Esan outlines the theoretical framework within which the study was conducted – that of structuralism. It also highlighted the methodology by which data were elicited and analyzed in this work. The selection of the theoretical framework as well as the methodology ensure that the research goal of a

three dimensional approach to current dialectal studies as mentioned in the introductory chapter of this work (- structural - historical - geographical -) was achieved. This chapter therefore placed this study in proper perspective for the achievement of all its set goals.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.0 Introduction

In the following sections, we present the outcome of analysis of available data for the present work. As stated in the previous chapter, the study was carried out at three basic levels of comparison.

- (1) A comparison of the sound systems of Esan speech forms.
- (2) A lexical and tonal comparison of Esan speech forms.
- (3) A comparison of micro grammatical markers in the pronoun and lexical counting systems of Esan speech forms.

Other levels of comparison included:

- (4) Determination of levels of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms.
- (5) Identification of structural differences between Esan and her closest neighbours

4.1 Diaphonic comparison of Esan speech forms

The following findings emerged from a comparison of the sound inventories of Esan speech forms.

i. Vowel sounds

Available data revealed that the twelve Esan speech forms under focus in this work exhibit the vowel sound inventory of Esan as reported in Ejele (1994:69). All twelve speech forms under study exhibit seven oral and five nasal vowel sounds. Elugbe's postulations about the vowel system of a typical Edoid language were also confirmed (see chapter 2). While the oral vowels occur word initially, medially and finally, the nasals do not occur in the initial position of lexical items. In Table V, examples of the occurrences of these vowel sounds in lexical items from each Esan speech form are presented.

Table 5: Vowel sounds in lexical items across Esan speech forms

S/N	Vowel sound	UB	UH	UD	ET	OG	EK	IL	UR	IG	OD	IR	UG
1.	i	iri rope	iri rope	iri rope	iri rope	ibi charcoal	ikèkè back	ikeké back	ikéké back	ijeké back	igbè thorn	ikèkè back	ikeké back
2.	u	ukpùdù heart	ùdù heart	udù heart	ùdù heart	udù heart	ùkpùdù heart	ùdù heart	ùdù heart	ùdù heart	ùdù heart	ùdù heart	ùdù heart
3.	e	ebàlè food	ébàè food	ebàè food	ébàè food	ebàè food	ébàè food	ébàlè food	ébàlè food	ébà food	ébà food	ébàlè food	ébàlè food
4.	o	ófè fear	ófè fear	ófè fear	ófè fear	ofè fear	ílò song	óbᵛ hand	ófè fear	óhā fear	ófè fear	óbᵛ hand	óbᵛ hand
5.	ε	ekélè stomach	ékéè stomach	eké stomach	éké stomach	eké stomach	éké stomach	éké stomach	ékélè stomach	ékò stomach	éké stomach	éké stomach	ékélè stomach
6.	ᵛ	ᵛkà maize	ᵛtà speech	ᵛtà speech	ᵛkà maize	ᵛkà maize	ᵛtà speech	ᵛkà maize	ᵛtà Speech	ᵛkà maize	ᵛkà maize	ᵛkà maize	ᵛtà speech
7.	a	awà dog	awà dog	awà dog	áwà dog	awà dog	áwà dog	áwà dog	áwà dog	áwà dog	áwà dog	áwà dog	áwà dog
8.	ī	asī horse	èsī horse	èsī horse	èsī horse	asī horse	àkàsí horse	èsī horse	èsī horse	èsī horse	èsī horse	èsī horse	èsī horse
9.	u	unù mouth	akù waist	unù mouth	únù mouth	unù Mouth	únù mouth	únù mouth	únù mouth	únù mouth	únù mouth	únù mouth	únù mouth
10.	ē	igè wing	igè wing	ígè wing	ésè saliva	asè saliva	igè feather	ésè saliva	ésè saliva	àsè saliva	ésè saliva	ésè saliva	àsè saliva
11.	ᵛ̃	u×ᵛ navel	ù×ᵛ navel	ù×ᵛ navel	ù×ᵛ navel	àkᵛ tooth	ù×ᵛ navel	ù×ᵛ navel	ù×ᵛ navel	a×ᵛ navel	ù×ᵛ navel	à×ᵛ navel	à×ᵛ navel
12.	ā	agbā chin	àgbā chin	agbā jaw	árā blood	íᵛā yam	àgbā jaw	àgbā jaw	àgbā chin	igā father	àgbā chin	àgbā chin	àgbā chin

ii. **Consonant sounds**

Identification procedures revealed that 28 consonant phones occur across the twelve Esan speech forms. Esan's consonant sound inventory did not feature the alveolar affricates [ts,dz] as postulated in Elugbe(1989) (see 2.2). These consonant phones are presented in Table 6.

Table 6A: Consonant sound inventory of Esan speech forms

p b		t d		k g	kp	gb
β	f v s z		ʃ ʒ	x ɣ		h
			tʃ dʒ			
m	ɱ	n	ɲ			
		l				
		r				
			j			w

Data also showed that not all the speech forms under study possessed the 28 consonant phones identified. The consonant phones possessed by each speech form are shown in Table 6B. Possession of a given consonant sound by each speech form is indicated with a plus (+) sign, and non possession with a minus (-) sign.

Table 6B: Identified consonant phones by each Esan speech form

S/N	Consonant phone	Ewatto	Ugbegun	Uromi	Udo	Ogwa	Ugboha	Ubiaja	Ekpoma	Ohordua	Igueben	Irrua	Ilushi
1.	p	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2.	b	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
3.	t	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.	d	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
5.	k	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
6.	g	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
7.	kp	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
8.	gb	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
9.	b	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
10	f	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
11	v	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
12	s	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
13	z	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
14	ʃ	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
15	ʒ	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

16	s	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
17	ʎ	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
18	h	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
19	ʃ	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
20	ʈʂ	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
21	m	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
22	ŋ	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+
23	n	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
24	ɲ	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
25	l	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
26	r	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
27	w	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
28	j	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Total consonant phones	27	25	27	28	26	28	28	26	26	27	26	27

Examples of lexical items in each speech form which bear the identified consonant sounds are presented in Table 6C.

Table 6C: Identified consonant sounds in lexical items across E:am speech forms

S/N	consonant sound	UB	UH	UD	ET	OG	EK	IL	UM	IB	OD	IR	UG
1	ɔ	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet	ɔpià matchet
2	b	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build	bɔ build
3	l	lɔnɔ dig	lɔ dig	lɔ dig	lɔ dig	lɔ dig	lɔ roast	lɔ dig	lɔ dig	lɔ dig	lɔ dig	lɔ dig	lɔnɔ dig
4	d	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy	dé buy
5	k	kànɔ carve	kɔ sew	kɔ sew	kɔ sew	kɔ sew seeds	kɔ sew seeds	kɔ sew seeds	kɔ sew seeds	kɔ sew seeds	kɔ sew seeds	kànɔ carve	kànɔ mortar
6	g	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover	gwè cover
7	kp	kpè wash	kpè wash	kpè wash	kpè wash	ɔkpà one	ékpà bag	kpè wash	kpè wash	kpè wash	kpè wash	kpè wash	kpè wash
8	gb	gbé to beat	gbé to beat	Gbé to beat	gbé to beat	gbé to beat	gbé to beat	gbé to beat	gbé to beat				
9	ɸ	ɸbà you	ɸbà you	ɸbà you	ɸbà you	ɸbà you	ɸbà you	ɸbà you	ɸbà you	mɛɸɔ myself	ɸbà you	ɸbà you	ɸbòjé to dream
10	f	fò finish	fò finish	fò finish	fò finish	fò Finish	fò finish	fò finish	fò finish	fò finish	fò finish	fò finish	fò finish
11	v	òvɔlé sun	òvɔé sun	òvwé sun	òvé sun	òvézè sunshine	òvɔé sun	òvézè sunshine	òvɔlé sun	èvá two	òvé sunshine	èvá two	òvɔé sunshin
12	s	swilóló sing	swiló sing	swiló sing	swiló sing	swiló sing	swiló sing	swiló sing	swiló sing	swihwá sing	swiló sing	swilóré sing	Swiló sing
13	z	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè

		choose	choose	choose	choose	choose	choose	choose	choose	choose	choose	choose	choose
14	f	כפ friend	כפ friend	f á walk	f i pull	כ פ friend	—	כ פ friend	—	כ פ friend	f i pull	f á walk	—
15	ʒ	óʒi thief	óʒi thief	óʒi thief	óʒi thief	—	óʒi thief	óʒi thief	óʒi thief	óʒi thief	óʒi thief	óʒi thief	óʒi thief
16	x	axè waterpot	axè waterpot	axè waterpot	áxámè waterpot	axè waterpot	áxè waterpot	Áxè waterpot	áxè waterpot	áxámè waterpot	áxámè waterpot	áxè waterpot	Áxè waterpot
17	ʎ	ʎ álá divide	ʎ àè divide	ʎ è divide	ʎ álo divide	ʎ àlè divide	ʎ áé divide	ʎ á divide	ʎ á divide	ʎ á divide	ʎ á divide	ʎ áléá divide	ʎ ù break stick
18	h	hòhò blow air	hè refuse	hè refuse	hòhò blow air	hòhò blow air	hè refuse	Hè refuse	hè refuse	hòhò blow air	hè refuse	hè refuse	hè hè blow air
19	ʃ	fí ʃé return	fíʃéré return	fíʃéré return	—	—	íʃésùdʒé	—	ʃéváé return	—	—	—	—
20	ɖ	òɖ è king	ɖjè laugh	òɖjè king	ònòɖjè king	ɖjè laugh	òɖ è king	òɖ è king	òɖjè king	íɖj áɱ charcoal	—	òɖjè king	òɖj è king
21	m	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould	mà mould
22	ɱ	כמ soup	כמ Soup	כמ soup	כמ soup	כמ Soup	—	כמ soup	כמ soup	umje salt	úmje salt	—	—
23	n	eni lephant	eni elephant	eni elephant	éni elephant	eni Elephant	éni elephant	éni elephant	éni elephant	èní elephant	éni elephant	éni elephant	éni Elephant
24	ɲ	á ɲ wine	á ɲ wine	á ɲ wine	á ɲ wine	á ɲ wine	é ɲ wine	á ɲ wine	á ɲ wine	á ɲ wine	á ɲ wine	é ɲ wine	é ɲ wine
25	l	l ù make	lù make	l ù make	l ù make	l ù make	l ù Make	l ù make	l wè learn	l ù make	l ù make	l ù make	l ù make

26	r	erā fire wood	erā fire wood	erā fire wood	érālé fire	erā fire wood	érā fire wood	érālé fire						
27	w	uwāwā cooking pot	uwāwā cooking pot	ewā mat	éwā mat	ewā mat	ewā mat	ewā mat	éwā mat	éwā mat	ewā mat	ewā mat	ewā mat	uwāwā cooking pot
28	j	jɔ put on	jā stink	jā stink	jā stink	wjā stink	jā stink	jā stink	jā stink	jā stink	wjā stink	jā stink	jā stink	jā stink

4.1.1 Diaphonic relatedness of Esan speech forms

In this section, the diaphonic relatedness which emerged between Esan speech forms by sound systems are presented.

The twelve Esan speech forms under study were shown to possess identical vowel sound inventories. That occurrence indicates the possibility of a close linguistic affinity between them. The parameter of vowel sound inventory did not therefore identify more than one Esan variety. This observation suggests that the language does not consist of more than one variety. This impression could be misleading because differences of distribution of these sounds within the language were not taken into consideration.

The results of the diaphonic analysis of the consonant sound inventories of Esan speech forms gave credence to the claim that the language consists of more than one dialect. This deduction is drawn from the observation that the twelve speech forms exhibited differences in consonantal sound inventory. 23 consonant sounds were common to the twelve Esan speech forms while five were not. Details of these findings are presented below.

- A. The 23 consonant sounds common to Esan speech forms under study were as follows.
- (i). The plosives [p, b, t, d, k, g, kp, gb];
 - (ii). The fricatives [β, f, v, s, z, x, ʃ, h];
 - (iii). The nasals [m, n, ŋ];
 - (iv). The liquid [l];
 - (v). The trill sound [r]
 - (vi). The approximants glides [w, j].
- B. Five consonant sounds not common to Esan speech forms under study were as follows.
- (vii). The fricatives [ʃ, ʒ];
 - (viii). The affricates [tʃ, dʒ]
 - (ix). The labio-dental nasal [m]
- (C). Esan dialects which emerged by consonantal sound inventories are presented in

TABLE 6D: Esan dialects by sound inventory

S/N	Esan dialect	missing Sound
1.	Udo, Ugboha, Ubiaza	Nil
2.	Ewatto, Igueben, Ilushi	[ɸ]
3.	Ugbegun	[ʃ, ʧ, ŋ]
4.	Uromi	[ʃ]
5.	Ogwa	[ʒ, ʧ]
6.	Ekpoma	[ʃ, ŋ]
7.	Ohordua	[ʧ, ɖʒ]
8.	Irrua	[ʧ, ŋ]

As shown above, eight Esan dialects emerged from a diaphonic comparison of the twelve Esan speech forms thus:

- (1). Udo- Ugboha- Ubiaza (UD, UH, UB)
- (2). Ebhoato- Igueben- Ilushi (ET, IB, IL)
- (3). Ugbegun (UG)
- (4). Uromi (UM)
- (5). Ogwa (OG)
- (6). Ekpoma (EK)
- (7). Ohordua(OH)
- (8). Irrua. (IR)

These occurrences are as explained:

- (1). Udo, Ugboha and Ubiaza, featured the five uncommon consonant sounds, [ʃ, ʒ, ʧ, ɖʒ, ŋ] as well as the 23 common to all the Esan speech forms. This linguistic characteristic did not always reflect in total similarity in lexical items across these speech forms. That situation was observed to be due in part to the occurrence of phonological processes, such as liquid elision, and glide formation which sometimes resulted in sound changes. The total number of consonant sounds in the sound inventory of this dialect group numbered 28. This was the largest number for any of the identified dialects.

- (2) Ewatto, Igueben and Ilushi did not feature the consonant sound [tʃ]. The sounds common to them were [dʒ, ʃ, ʒ, m], as well as the 23 common to all Esan speech forms. This group featured a total of 27 consonant phones in its sound inventory.
- (3) Ugbegun lacked the phones [ʃ, tʃ, m] and featured [ʒ, dʒ], as well as the 23 common consonant sounds. Its sound inventory comprised a total of 25 phones. That occurrence made it the dialect with the fewest consonant sounds and probably a more recent form of Esan.
- (4) Uromi did not possess [ʃ] in its sound inventory which contained 27 consonant sounds. It possessed the phones [ʒ, tʃ, dʒ, m] of the five uncommon sounds.
- (5) Ogwa was the only dialect which lacked [ʒ]. It also lacked [tʃ] and featured [dʒ, ʃ, m], along with the 23 common consonant sounds. This brought its total number of consonant phones to 26.
- (6) Ekpoma did not feature the phones [ʃ, m] in its sound inventory. It featured [tʃ, dʒ, ʒ] bringing the total consonant phones to 26.
- (7) Ohordua lacked the sounds [tʃ, dʒ] and possessed [ʃ, ʒ, m]. It was the only dialect which lacked [dʒ]. Its consonant sound inventory comprised 26 consonant phones.
- (8) Irrua lacked [tʃ, m] and featured [dʒ, ʃ, ʒ]. Its sound inventory comprised a total of 27 consonant phones.

These occurrences are formalized diastematically as follows:

Figure 4A: Diasystem of Esan by consonant sound inventory

The diasystem in in figure 4A is a diaphonic representation of Esan dialects by sound systems. It reflects the findings from this study that Esan consists eight dialects by sound inventory of the identified speech forms. (see table 1D). These eight dialects are listed on the left side of the first set of double bars, while each speech form or group of Esan speech form constituting a dialect is situated within the double bars. The sound inventory peculiar to each Esan dialect is specified beside it in single slashes while the sounds common to the eight Esan dialects are listed thereafter. A second double bar encloses this phonic information.

Figure 5 is a map showing the isolation of Esan dialects by sound systems.

while for others, it was non-existent, and yet for others, it was optional (see table III D in chapter three). The patterns of occurrence of this phenomenon across Esan speech forms under focus in this work are as highlighted:

1. /l/ elision in Esan was not restricted to word final syllables but sometimes occurred in penultimate ones as illustrated below.

A. /l/ elision in word final syllables

(i)	[émjilì]	[émjì]	
			something
(ii)	[ébàlè]	[ébàè]	
			food
(iii)	[óxwàlè]	[óxwàè]	
			basket
(iv)	[óxɔlè]	[óxɔ]	
			fight/war
(v)	[ɲèlè]	[ɲè]	
			dwell
(vi)	[árálè]	[árá]	
			blood

B. /l/ elision in penultimate syllables

(vii)	[élàmjè]	[éàmjè]	
			meat
(viii)	[ègbòlisé]	[ègbòisè]	
			one hundred

2. Lexical items in some Esan speech forms lost the entire syllable introduced by the liquid /l/. This occurrence is illustrated in data presented in A above.

Data revealed that the phenomenon of elision of the liquid [l] was totally non-existent in Ubiaza, while in Ugboha, it occurred almost whenever the phonetic conditions were present. Udo, Igueben, Ebhoato and Ekpoma featured this phonetic feature averagely, while Ilushi, Irrua, Uromi Ohordua, Ugbegun and Ogwa did so sparingly. A diaphonic representation of the phenomenon of liquid elision in Esan is presented as follows.

Figure 4B: Diaphonic representation of liquid elision across Esan speech forms

In figure 4B the various levels of occurrence of liquid elision across the identified Esan speech forms are represented. On the left of the first set of double bars are the three groups into which the speech forms fall in this regard. Within the two sets of double bars, Ubiaza is shown to feature the liquid / l / with no elision (o) occurring while Ugboha is shown to feature this phenomenon both at syllable final and penultimate positions. Udo, Ewatto, igueben, Ilushi, Ugbegun, Uromi, Ogwa, Ekpoma, Ohordua and Irrua speech forms are shown to feature all the three positions of /l/ elision. These are the non elision of the liquid, its elision in word final and penultimate positions.

Data presented in Table 7A provides more examples of lexical items illustrating this phenomenon across identified Esan speech forms

TABLE 7A — Liquid elision in lexical items across Esan speech forms.

SN	UZ	UD	UH	ET	OG	EM	IS	UM	IB	OD	IR	UG	Gloss
1	élólò	élò	èò	élò	élò	élò'	élò	élò	élò	élò	élólò	akpélólò	eye
2	ébàlè	Ebae	ébaè	eba	ébaè	ebaè	ébàlè	ébàlè	ébà	ébà	ébàlè	ébàlè	food
3	ékélè	éké	ékéè	eké	éké	ké	éké	ékélè	ékò	éké	ékélè	ékélè	belly
4	èhélè	èhé	èhé	èhé	èhé	èhé	Èhé	èhélè	èhé	èhé	èhélè	èhélè	fish
5	égélè	égélè	—	—	—	—	égè	égè	—	—	—	—	cooking pot
6	—	—	—	òlú	—	òlú	—	òlú	òlú	òlú	—	òlú	cotton
7	òvɔlè	òvwè	òvɔè	òvè	òwé	òvɔè	Òè	òvɔlè	òwé	òélè	òvɔlè	òhélè	sun
8	ìlòlò	ìò	ìò	ìlò	ìlò	ìlò	ìlò	ìlò	—	ìlò	ìlòlò	ìlòlò	song
9	àkìlè	akìe	àkìe	akìe	àkìe	akìe	àkìlè	àkìlè	àkìe	àkìlè	àkìlè	àkìlè	toad/frog

An impressionistic representation of the extent of the exhibition of this phonological phenomenon across Esan speech forms is presented in the map in figure 6.

Figure 6: Map showing an impression of the exhibition of liquid elision across Esan speech forms

Source: Fieldwork 2007

4.1.2.2 Glide formation

In Esan, this process involved the vowel sounds [i,e,o,u]. [i] and [e] are sometimes realized as [j], while [o] and [u] became [w] when preceded by a consonant and followed by a non-identical vowel sound, bearing an identical tone height. This phonological process, is attested in other Edoid languages including Iyie, (Masagbor 1989); Emai, (Egbokhare 1990). It operates in two specific environments in Esan, especially in rapid speech. These environments are

- (a) word internally
- (b) at word boundaries.

Since data for this work was lexicon based only the environment in (a) above was relevant. In the specified environment, only [i] and [u] were affected. Examples are provided below from our data to illustrate this condition.

C. [i] → [j]

	[i]	→	[j]	Gloss
(i)	[ɔpiá]		[ɔpjá]	cutlass
(ii)	[ɔriá]		[ɔrjá]	person
(iii)	[dié]		[djé]	to tie
(iv)	[óhiá]		[óhjá]	shoe
(v)	[éyiá]		[éyjá]	enemy

D. /u/ → /w/

	/u/	→	/w/	Gloss
(vi)	/ígùè/		/ígwè/	bone
(vii)	/ígùè/		/ígwè/	village
(viii)	/óhùè/		/óhwè/	hunter
(ix)	/tùè/		/twè/	to greet/pray
(x)	/ihùè/		/ihwè/	nose
(xi)	/ihùè/		/ihwè/	feather

The process of glide formation across Esan speech forms may be explained as follows. Available data showed that the vowel segments [i, u] form the glides [j, w] respectively. These occurrences are obvious instances of change in class membership, from the class of vowels to that of glides. The phonological conditions under which these changes take place may be summarized as follows.

- (i) The glides [j,w], share the features [+sonorant] and [- consonantal] with the vowel segments [i, u]. The difference between these two classes of sounds is in the fact that while the vowel segments are [+ syllabic], the glides are [- syllabic].
- (ii) The segments [u] and [w] share the feature values [-low, +back] which makes them [+round], while [i] and [j] have the feature values [-low, - back] in common, making them [-round].
- (iii) The segments preceeding the vowel segments which become glides, share the feature [- syllabic] with the glides. Thus, the resulting sounds can be said to

have assimilated this feature from this preceding segment. Also, the vowel segment that forms the glide must be followed by another vowel segment.

(iv) In summary, the process of glide formation in Esan may be captured in one of two ways as follows.

- (1) The vowel segments which formed the glides may have been deleted, allowing the lengthening of the preceding consonant segments unto the empty positions formerly occupied by these vowel segments, making it a case of compensatory lengthening. This would then result in germination. This view is however flawed as glides are not pure consonants, and cannot form germinate with the latter.
- (2) The glide forming vowel segments have dropped their inherent [+syllabic] feature value to make them look more like the preceding consonant segment, thus preventing their being totally deleted. Glide formation appears to be more economical. This view is considered more tenable and presented here as the true position.

Observations revealed that all Esan speech forms under study exhibited the phonetic characteristic of glide formation. Udo and Ebhoato exhibited the phonetic feature to a higher extent than the others. It was also observed that a glide was most easily formed, where the glide forming vowel sound and that following it bore identical tone levels. Thus, a LL or a HH sequence formed glides more easily, whereas, a LH or HL sequence did not. Tables 7B and C contain illustrations of these occurrences.

Table 7B: Glide formation in lexical items across Esan speech forms

S/N	UB	UH	UD	ET	OG	EK	IL	UM	IB	OD	IR	UG	GLOSS
1	ihùè → ihwè	ihùè → ihwè	nose										
2	ígùé → ígwé	ígùé → ígwé	úgùé → ígwé	úgùé → ígwé	úgùé → ígwé	ígùé → ígwé	ígùé → ígwé	ígùé → ígwé	—	úgùé → ígwé	ú gùé → ígwé	úgùé → ígwé	bone
3	ɔpià → ɔpjà	ɔpià → ɔpjà	matchet										

Table 7C: Tonal effect on glide formation in lexical items across Esan speech forms

S/N	UZ	UH	UD	ET	OG	EK	IS	UM	IB	OH	IR	UG	GLOSS
1	ihie → ihie	ihie → ihje	ihie → ihie	éhie → éhje	ikpéhíéóǎ → ikpéhjóbǎ	úkpihié → úkpihjé	ihieóǎ → ihjǎǎ	ihie → ihie	ihie → ihje	ihie → ihie	íkpihié → ikpihié	ihie → ihie	fingernail

A diaphonic representation of the phenomenon of gliding in Esan is presented as follows.

Figure 4C: A diaphonic representation of the phenomenon of gliding in Esan

This diasystem reflects the observation from available data that all identified Esan speech forms exhibit the phenomenon of gliding with [i] forming the glide [j] and [u] forming the glide [w]. The map in figure 7 presents an impression of the extent of this linguistic feature of glide formation across Esan speech forms.

Figure 7: Map showing an impression of the exhibition of gliding across Esan speech forms

Source: Fieldwork 2007

Observed differences between identified Esan speech forms, due to phonological processes, as highlighted above, revealed that, while all exhibited the gliding phenomenon, not all of them featured the elision of the liquid segment [l]. For this reason, the process of liquid elision is more relevant to the goal of the present study. In that regard, the hypothesis is that Ubiaza, which, as available data revealed, did not exhibit the phonetic characteristic of the elision of the liquid [l] and, or that of the vowel segment following it which sometimes accompanied this process, was probably an earlier speech form of Esan. This evidence combined with that of its possession of the 5 doubly articulated consonant phones, which were not common to most other speech forms gave credence to the possibility stated above. This summation is based on the linguistic notion

that older forms of languages tended to retain longer and more complicated linguistic forms (Lewis 2003).

Summary

In this section, the findings from a structural analysis of twelve Esan speech forms along the parameters of sound systems and phonological processes were presented. These findings laid credence to the commonly made claim that Esan comprises more than one dialect, as eight dialects were identified.

We deduced from available data that the dialect group comprising Ugboha, Udo and Ubiaza speech forms predate the others. This possibility was strengthened by their possession of all 28 consonant phones of Esan, a characteristic which the other speech forms did not exhibit. In addition, 5 consonant phones not common to the others, featured in the sound inventory of this group. The five phones in question are doubly articulated and are thus more complicated linguistic forms. By linguistic principles, the exhibition of these features serves as empirical evidence for making that deduction. Further in this regard, Ubiaza, a member of this possibly older group of speech forms, exhibited characteristics which suggested that it may be an earlier Esan variety. This characteristic was its non exhibition of the liquid elision process which featured in all the other Esan speech forms under focus in this study. A diasystem was constructed to formalize the diaphonic comparisons which were conducted across the twelve identified Esan speech forms. (see figure 4A), while two diaphonic representations, one each for the phonological processes of liquid elision and glide formation respectively found to be prevalent across Esan speech forms under focus formalized those observations (see figure 4B and 4C).

4.2 Comparative Lexicon and tonology of Esan speech forms

A Comparative lexicon and tonology of Esan speech forms were conducted along 3 lines of inquiry (see chapter three). The values and deductions accruing from the application of statistical formulae to available data are presented below.

4.2.1 Relatedness of Esan speech forms considering both segmental and tonal constitution of lexical items

At this level of comparison, dichotomy was between lexical items which bore identical segmental and tonal constitution and those which did not. Statistical values of forms were as follows.

Table 8A: Statistical values of lexical items with identical segmental and tonal constitution across Esan speech forms

Key: ET= Ewatto, UG = Ugbegun, UM = Uromi
 UD= Udo, OG = Ogwa, UH = Ugboha,
 UB= Ubiaza, EK = Ekpoma, OH = Ohordua
 IB= Igueben, IR = Irrua, IL = Illushi

ET												
32	UG											
39	50	UM										
45	41	50	UD									
39	36	38	46	OG								
36	35	47	42	31	UH							
42	46	53	47	37	48	UB						
32	53	46	39	41	33	38	EK					
61	36	44	51	38	41	46	33	OH				
20	18	19	20	27	15	18	20	21	IG			
32	51	52	44	35	35	50	52	34	19	IR		
44	41	55	47	38	59	52	40	46	20	41	IL	

Shared lexicostatistical values between paired Esan speech forms are highlighted in Table 8B.

Table 8B: Shared statistical values of paired Esan speech forms with identical and tonal constitution

ET/UG 32	UG/UM 50	UM/OG 38	UD/EM 39	OG/IL 38	UB/IL 52
ET/UM 39	UG/UD 41	UM/UH 47	UD/OH 51	UH/UB 48	EK/OH 33
ET/UD 45	UG/OG 36	UM/UB 53	UD/IB 20	UH/EK 33	EM/IB 20
ET/OG 39	UG/UH 35	UM/EK 46	UD/IR 44	UH/OD 41	EM/IR 52
ET/UH 36	UG/UB 46	UM/OH 44	UD/IL 47	UH/IB 15	EK/IL 40
ET/UB 42	UG/EK 53	UM/IB 19	OG/UH 31	UH/IR 35	OD/IB 21
ET/EK 32	UG/OH 36	UM/IR 52	OG/UB 37	UH/IL 59	OH/IR 34
ET/OH 61	UG/IB 18	UM/IL 55	OG/EK 41	UB/EK 38	OH/IL 46
ET/IB 20	UG/IR 51	UD/OG 46	OG/OH 38	UB/OD 46	IB/IR 19
ET/IR 32	UG/IL 41	UD/UH 42	OG/IB 27	UB/IB 18	IB/IL 20
ET/IL 44	UM/UD 50	UD/UB 47	OG/IR 35	UB/IR 50	IR/IL 41

Based on the statistical levels adopted for this work, which is 86% (see chapter 3), Esan speech forms exhibited relatedness along the parameter of segmental and tonal constitution of lexical items thus:

- (i) Each of the twelve identified Esan speech forms attained below the adopted value of relatedness when compared with one another. By this analysis at this level of comparison, all Esan speech forms under focus emerged as autonomous dialects of Esan.
- (ii) Data revealed that the comparison between Ewatto and Ohordua showed the highest level of relatedness (61). The justification for this occurrence cannot be alluded solely to the relatively high number of consonant phones common to these speech forms, (27) and the shared phonetic processes of gliding and liquid elision, since others (Udo, Ugboha, Ubiaza) share a higher number of consonant phones (28). The explanation for this level of relatedness may also be due to geographical proximity, a situation which would necessarily engender socioeconomic activities, and subsequent linguistic contact between speakers of both speech forms. Both

speech areas are adjacent to each other (see figure 2). They obviously merge into each other, and, are spoken within the same LGA (Esan South East).

- (iii). Our statistical evidence showed that Uromi shared a value of 50% and above with five of the twelve Esan speech forms (Ugbegun, Irrua, Udo, Ubiaza, Ilushi). A probable deduction from this evidence is that, Uromi dialect shares a closer linguistic affinity with more Esan dialects than any of the others. A combination of factors such as, socioeconomy and geography, resulting in language interaction would account for this linguistic situation. Conversely, Ewatto and Ugboha attained that level of relatedness with the fewest number of speech forms (one each).
- (iv) Although identical sound inventory and location favoured highlinguistic relatedness between Udo, Ugboha and Ubiaza speech forms, this did not occur. This situation may not be unconnected with the phonetic evidence of liquid elision (see 4. 1.2). While Ubiaza nearly never exhibited this phenomenon, Ugboha did so compulsorily, whenever the phonetic conditions were present, while Udo sometimes did.
- (v). Ogwa and Igueben attained below 50% relatedness with the other (ten) Esan speech forms, as well as with each other. This occurrence isolated them from the others, and from each other. The deduction from this situation is that linguistic relatedness between these two Esan speech forms, on the one hand, and between them and other Esan speech forms, on the other, is low. Igueben attained below 30% statistical value with others, while Ogwa attained below 50%. This seeming isolation of Ogwa and Igueben may be readily traceable to their geographical location, away from the others at the Western boarder of Esanland, towards Benin, speech area of Edo language. This isolation occurs inspite of evidence of identical sound inventory and shared phonetic processes with other Esan speech forms. It is important to note that the past geopolitical status of Igueben could be relevant to this deduction. Untill only a few years ago, Igueben was politically affiliated to Benin.

Table 8C contains examples of data illustrating lexical items in this category of comparison across the Esan speech forms.

Table 8C: Lexical items with identical segmental and tonal constitution across E-san speech forms

S/N	ET	UG	UM	UD	OG	UH	UZ	EM	OD	IG	IR	IS	GLOSS
1.	ákɔ	tooth											
2.	ámé	water											
3.	ɔká	maize											
4.	iyóyó	Íyóyó	iyóyó	iyóyó	iyóyó	iyóyó	smoke						
5.	òɔ	ground											
6.	úki	moon											
7.	ɔkpá	cock											
8.	évá	two											
9.	gwá	to hoe											
10.	xwǎ	heavy											

4.2.2 Relatedness of Esan speech forms considering only segmental constitution of lexical items

At this level of comparison, dichotomy was between lexical items which bore identical segmental constitution and those which did not. Tonal constitutions of lexical items were ignored. Statistical values of lexical items which bore identical segmental constitution only across Esan speech forms were:

Table 9A – Statistical values of lexical items with identical segmental constitution only across Esan speech forms

ET											
36	UG										
42	54	UM									
48	45	53	UD								
42	40	40	50	OG							
39	38	49	44	34	UH						
44	48	55	50	39	51	UB					
39	58	51	45	46	37	42	EK				
64	40	48	55	42	43	48	38	OH			
38	32	34	36	47	29	33	35	38	IB		
35	55	55	48	37	28	52	56	39	30	IR	
46	42	57	50	40	60	53	41	49	36	44	IL

Shared lexicostatistical values between paired Esan speech forms are highlighted in Table 9B.

Table 9B: Shared statistical values of paired Esan speech forms with identical segmental constitution only

ET/UG 36	UG/UM 54	UM/OG 40	UD/EK 45	OG/IL 40	UB/IL 53
ET/UM 42	UG/UD 45	UR/UH 49	UD/OH 55	UH/UB 51	EK/OH 38
ET/UD 48	UG/OG 40	UM/UB 55	UD/IB 36	UH/EM 37	EK/IB 35
ET/OG 42	UG/UH 38	UM/EK 51	UD/IR 48	UH/OD 43	EK/IR 56
ET/UH 39	UG/UB 48	UM/OH 48	UD/IL 50	UH/IB 29	EK/IL 41
ET/UZ 44	UG/EK 58	UM/IB 34	OG/UH 34	UH/IR 38	OH/IB 38
ET/EK 39	UG/OD 40	UM/IR 35	OG/UB 39	UH/IL 60	OD/IR 39
ET/OD64	UG/IB 32	UM/IL 57	OG/EM 46	UB/EK 42	OH/IL 49
ET/IB 38	UG/IR 55	UD/OG 50	OG/OH 42	UB/OH 48	IB/IR 30
ET/IR 35	UG/IL 42	UD/UH 44	OG/IB 47	UB/IB 33	IB/IL 36
ET/IL 46	UM/UD 53	UD/UB 50	OG/IR 37	UB/IR 52	IR/IL 44

The following deductions were made based on the statistical values from the analysis presented above.

- (i) All twelve Esan speech forms exhibited below the 86% lexicostatistical value adopted for this work. This analysis confirmed the verdict from the preceding one that the identified speech forms under focus are autonomous Esan dialects.
- (ii). One observable difference between this level of comparison and the preceding one was that only Igueben failed to attain relatedness value of up to 50% with any Esan speech form, where previously, Ogwa was also affected. Ogwa attained this relatedness value with Udo, with which it shared geographical boundaries.
- (iii) A notable increase in statistical values from comparison between Esan speech forms emerged at this level of analysis. With the lowering of the number of linguistic features used as parameters of comparison, statistical values increased. The previous highest value of 61% rose to 64%.

(iv) The number of Esan speech forms with which Uromi attained above 50% relatedness value rose from 5 to 6, Ewotto's remained 1, while Ugboha's rose from 1 to 2. The deductions and explanations for these observations remain the same, except that which concerned the exclusion of the linguistic feature of tone from the parameters of comparison.

Table 9C illustrates lexical items in this category of comparison across the twelve Esan speech forms.

TABLE 9C:

Lexical with identical segmental constitution only across Esan speech forms.

S/N	ET	UG	UM	UD	OG	UH	UB	EK	OH	IG	IR	IL	Gloss
1.	etò	etò	étò	étò	etò	étò	etò	étò	étò	etò	étò	étò	hair
2.	óbɔ	obɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	obɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	obɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	hand
3.	unù	unù	únù	únù	unù	únù	unù	únù	únù	unù	únù	únù	mouth
4.	ɔpjà	matchet											
5.	ewà	ewà	èwà	èwà	ewà	èwà	ewà	èwà	èwà	ewà	èwà	èwà	mat
6.	úkɔɔ	cloth											
7.	iyò	money											
8.	eni	eni	éni	éni	eni	éni	eni	éni	éni	eni	éni	éni	elephant
9.	igbé	ten											
10.	kpà	to vomit											

4.2.3 Relatedness of Esan speech forms considering only tonal constitution on lexical items

At this level of comparison, dichotomy was between lexical items, which bore only identical tonal patterning, and those which did not. Statistical values of lexical items in this category across Esan speech forms were:

Table 10A: Statistical values of lexical items with identical tonal patterning only across Esan speech forms

ET											
96	UG										
97	96	UM									
97	96	97	UD								
97	96	98	96	OG							
97	97	98	98	97	UH						
98	98	98	97	98	97	UB					
93	95	95	94	95	96	96	EK				
97	96	96	96	96	98	98	95	OH			
82	86	85	84	80	86	85	85	83	IG		
97	96	97	96	98	97	98	96	95	89	IR	
98	99	98	97	98	99	99	99	97	84	97	IL

Shared tonostatistical values between paired Esan speech forms are highlighted in Table 10B.

Table 10B: Shared tonostatistical values of paired Esan speech forms

ET/UG 96	UG/UM 96	UM/OG 98	UD/EK 94	OG/IL 98	UB/IL 99
ET/UM 97	UG/UD 96	UM/UH 98	UD/OH 96	UH/UB 97	EK/OH 95
ET/UD 97	UG/OG 96	UM/UB 98	UD/IB 84	UH/EK 96	EK/IB 85
ET/OG 97	UG/UH 97	UM/EK 95	UD/IR 96	UH/OD 98	EK/IR 96
ET/UH 97	UG/UB 98	UM/OH 96	UD/IL 97	UH/IB 86	EK/IL 99
ET/UB 98	UG/EK 95	UM/IB 85	OG/UH 97	UH/IR 97	OH/IB 83
ET/EK 93	UG/OH 96	UM/IR 97	OG/UB 98	UH/IL 99	OD/IR 95
ET/OH 97	UG/IB 86	UM/IL 98	OG/EK 95	UB/EK 96	OH/IL 97
ET/IB 82	UG/IR 96	UD/OG 96	OG/OH 96	UB/OH 98	IB/IR 89
ET/IR 97	UG/IL 99	UD/UH 98	OG/IB 80	UB/IB 85	IB/IL 84
ET/IL 98	UM/UD 97	UD/UB 97	OG/IR 98	UB/IR 98	IR/IL 97

At this level of analysis, the following observations were made.

- (i). All twelve Esan speech forms exhibited formidable relatedness values (80% - 99%), when only tonal patterning on identical lexical items formed the parameter of comparison.
- (ii) The twelve Esan speech forms under focus fell into 2 dialect groups, by the cut off point adopted for this study, as follows.
 1. Igueben – Irrua – Ugbegun – Ugboha
 2. Ewatto – Uromi – Udo – Ogwa – Ubiaza – Ekpoma – Ohordua – Irrua - Ilushi – Ugboha – Ugbegun.

By this grouping, Igueben shared above the cut off value of relatedness (86% and above) with Irrua Ugbegun and Ugboha, while with all others, relatedness was below the adopted statistical level for determining dialectal status in this work. Irrua, Ugbegun and Ugboha however, shared above 90% relatedness value with all the other Esan speech forms, an evidence suggestive of a closer linguistic relatedness with them, than with

Igueben. On the basis of the argument stated above, a finer verdict would be that which classified Igueben as a separate dialect from the other eleven Esan speech forms, on the basis of tonostatistical evidence. The emergence of the three speech forms of Irrua, Ugbegun and Ugboha as members of the two identified dialects in 1 and 2 confirm the opinion in contemporary dialect study that dialect areas are usually gradual transitions, rather than clear cut boundaries – (see 1.3.2). These three speech forms have exhibited what may be called a transition between two dialects. That occurrence may be explained in either of two ways as follows:

- (i). Irrua, Ugbegun and Ugboha are in a process of becoming more like Igueben with which they share a lower percentage of resemblance by a process of gradual transition through socio-linguistic processes like language contact.
- (ii). Irrua, Ugbegun and Ugboha have, over the years gradually transitted to become more like the other members of the second dialect group with which they share above 90% level of resemblance. The probability of their total disappearance as members of the first dialect group in future is high. Igueben had, thus far, maintained its earlier observed linguistic distance between it and the other Esan speech forms.
- (iii) Tonostatistical values between Esan speech forms, as revealed at this level of comparison, suggested that the larger majority of Esans spoke the same form of the language.

Table 10C illustrates lexical items at this level of analysis, across Esan speech forms.

Table 10C: Lexical items with identical tonal patterning only across Esan speech forms

S/N	ET	UG	UM	UD	OG	UH	UB	EK	OH	IB	IR	IL	Gloss
1.	ítàbà	ítàbà	ítàbà	tàbà	ítàbà	ítàbà	ítàbà	ítàbà	ítàbà	ítàbà	tàbà	tàbà	tobacco
2.	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	íxjàḅḅ	okro
3.	émátḅ	úkpeḅmḅ	émátḅ	eḅmḅ	emátḅ	émátḅ	émátḅ	émátḅ	eḅmḅ	émátḅ	eḅmḅ	eḅmḅ	iron
4.	òlù	òlù	òlùlù	kpeḅéḅe	íkpirjagbèdè	òwù	òwù	olù	olù	òlù	úkpeḅòlù	òwù	thread
5.	eere	èḅeḅe	èḅeḅe	èḅeḅe	eḅeḅe	èḅeḅe	èḅeḅe	eḅeḅe	erere	èḅeḅe	èḅeḅe	èḅeḅe	eight
6.	isiri	isili	isili	isili	isili	isì	ihili	isili	isili	ihili	isili	isili	nine
7.	sà	sà	sà	sàòxù	sàyòxù	Sà	sà	sà	sà	sà	sàòxù	sà	jump
8.	Yàḅḅ	gbèyáé	Yà	Yà	Yalè	Yàè	Yàlá	Yàè	Yǎ	Yǎ	Yàlèá	Yà	divide
9.	hāsà	hāsà	hāsà	hāsà	hāsà	hàè	hāsà	hāsà	hāsà	hāsà	hāsà	hà	to pay

SUMMARY

Lexicostatistical and tonostatistical analysis of available data across the twelve identified Esan speech forms under focus in this work, confirmed the claim that Esan is multidialectal. The statistical values which emerged from our analysis of data, within the parameters identified in this section of the work, provided evidence to substantiate this claim as follows.

1. When both segmental and tonal constitution, on the one hand, and only segmental constitution of lexical items, on the other, were used as parameters for determining linguistic relatedness, each Esan speech form emerged as an autonomous Esan dialect.
2. When only tonal constitution on identical lexical items formed the parameter of comparison, Esan speech forms fell into 2 dialect groups.

4.3 Comparison of micro - grammatical markers across Esan speech forms

An examination of micro – grammatical markers in the pronoun and lexical counting systems of Esan speech forms, gave further evidence of their linguistic relatedness thus:

4.3.1 Pronoun systems across Esan speech forms

4.3.1.1 Personal pronouns

Three Esan speech forms, Ogwa, Igueben, and Ekpoma, showed non resemblances with the other 9 (Ewatto, Ugbegun, Uromi, Udo, Ugboha, Ubiaza, Ohordua, Irrua, Ilushi) in their plural personal pronominal forms:

1. Ogwa featured a 1st person plural pronominal form unidentical with those of other Esan speech forms.
2. Igueben featured a 2nd person plural pronominal form unidentical with those of other Esan speech forms.
3. Ogwa, Ekpoma and Igueben, each featured 3rd person plural pronominal forms different from one another and from those of the other nine Esan speech forms.

Relatedness between all twelve Esan speech forms in other personal pronoun forms, showed above 70% resemblances. Data presented in Table 11A revealed the observation specified above.

Table 11A – Personal pronoun forms across Esan speech forms

Form	Ewatto	Ugbegun	Uromi	Udo	Ugboha	Ubiaza	Ohordua	Irrua	Ogwa	Ekpoma	Igueben	Illushi	Gloss
1 st person singular	imé	imé	imé	imé	imé	imé	imé	imé	mé	mé	mé	mé	I
2 nd	uwé	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	wé	wé	wé	wé	you
3 rd	ɔlè	ɔlè	ɔlè	ɔlè	ɔè	ɔlè	ɔlè	ɔlè	ɔ	ɔlè	ɔlè	ɔlè	he/she/it
1 st person plural	mjà	imà	imàè	imjà	imà	imjà	imjà	imàlè	màβɔ	mà	imà	imjà	we
2 nd person Plural	ifà	ifà	ifà	ifà	ifà	ifà	ifà	ifà	βà	βà	ùwà	ifà	you
3 rd person Plural	àlè	è	èlè	èlè	è	elè	àlè	èlè	jà	nàì	irà	èlè	they

Some cases of partial resemblances, one of which was the occurrence of [m] and [ŋ] in analogous environments, were attributable to absence of some segments in the sound inventories of affected speech forms (see Ugbegun). Segment deletion was observed to be a most common source of non resemblance in this group of pronouns, across Esan speech forms. In that regard, Ogwa, Igueben and Ekpoma were observed to be more prone to segment deletion processes. The linguistic distance between Ogwa and Igueben on the one hand, and other Esan speech forms which reflected in the lexicostatistical comparison in the preceding section (see 4.2.1, 4.2.2), was maintained in the examination of personal pronoun forms across Esan speech forms. Some 3rd person pronominal forms in use in neighbouring Benin - / wà, irã / - were suspected to be probable explanations for these differences.

4.3.1.2 Reflexive Pronouns

Two speech forms – Igueben and Ugbegun – marked the reflexive forms of personal pronouns differently from the other ten Esan speech forms. With the latter, a grammatical marker, [t òbɔ], was infixes between a personal pronoun and its reflexion. Segment deletion processes seemed to have altered the resulting structures of these pronouns in some of the identified speech forms, as shown in Table 11B.

Table 11B: Reflexive pronoun forms across Esan speech forms

Ewatto	Udo	Ohordua	Ugbegun	Uromi	Ughoha	Ogwa	Ubiaza	Ekpoma	Irrua	Ilushi	Igueben	Gloss
Imetobimé	imetobimé	imetobimé	ménà	imetobimé	imetobimé	metobimé	metobimé	metobome	metobime	metobimé	méβ	Myself
uwetobuwé	uwetobuwé	uwetobuwé	uwénà	uwetobé	uwetobé	wetobé	uwetobuwé	wetobé	wetobé	wetobé	wéβ	Yourself
ɔletoba	ɔletobalé	ɔletobalé	ɔlénà	ɔletobalé	ɔletobé	ɔletoba	ɔletobalé	ɔletoba	ɔletobalé	ɔletoba	ɔréβ	him/her/itself
Imátobimà	imátobimà	imátobimà	imánà	imátobimà	Imátobimà	maβɔtobɔma	imátobimà	mátobimà	Imálétòbɔ mà	imátobimà	màβ	ourselves
Ibátobíβà	ibátobíβà	ibátobíβà	ibánà	ibátobíβà	ibátobíβà	βátobɔβà	ibátobíβà	βátobɔβà	βátobɔβà	ibátobɔβà	wàβ	yourself
Alétobálè	elétobálè	alétobálè	èlénà	elétobélè	etòbè	íátòbíá	elétobélè	nátòbɔnàì	elétobélè	elétobè	iràβ	themselves

An examination of the forms presented above showed that Igeuben's linguistic distance from other Esan speech forms, thus far, had remained consistent. The same deductions may not be applicable to Ugbegun, which showed closer relatedness to other Esan speech forms, prior to this area of comparison. The source of this difference in reflexive pronoun forms between Ugbegun and the other speech forms, was not immediately obvious. An explanation may be found in lineage history of the speakers of the speech form.

4.3.1.3 Possessive pronouns

Available data revealed an identical grammatical marking system – that of affixation - for the possessive pronoun across Esan speech forms. An associative marker which is semantically contrived to mean “belonging to” was affixed to a personal pronoun to derive its possessive case. This marking system was however realized in three different forms of grammatical markers as employed by the twelve Esan speech forms:

(i).	[ɔsɛ̀],	(ii).	[ikɛ̀],	(iii).	[ɔʋɛ̀]
	Ewatto		Ugboha		Igueben
	Ugbegun		Illushi		Ogwa
	Udo				
	Uromi				
	Ubiaza				
	Ugboha				
	Ohordua				
	Irrua				

Data presented Table 11C illustrated these usages across Esan speech forms.

Table 11C: Possessive pronoun forms across Esan speech forms

Ewatto	Ubiaza	Ohordua	Irrua	Ekpoma	Ugbegun	Uromi	Udo	Ogwa	Igueben	Ugboha	Illushi	Gloss
ṣ̀s̀imè	ṣ̀s̀imè	ṣ̀s̀imè	ṣ̀s̀imè	ṣ̀s̀imè	ṣ̀s̀imè	ṣ̀s̀imḡè	ṣ̀s̀imḡè	ṣ̀mè	ṣ̀mè	ìkèṣ̀mè	ìkèṣ̀mè	mine
ṣ̀s̀ùwè	ṣ̀s̀ùwè	ṣ̀s̀ùwè	ṣ̀s̀è	ṣ̀s̀è	ṣ̀s̀è	ṣ̀s̀è	ṣ̀s̀ùwè	ṣ̀wè	ṣ̀wè	ìkè	ìkè	yours
ṣ̀s̀lè	ṣ̀s̀lè	ṣ̀s̀lè	ṣ̀s̀lè	ṣ̀s̀lè	ṣ̀s̀	ṣ̀s̀lè	ṣ̀s̀lè	ṣ̀ṣ̀lè	ṣ̀ṣ̀	ìkè	ìkè	his/hers/its
ṣ̀s̀imḡà	ṣ̀s̀imḡà	ṣ̀s̀imḡà	ṣ̀s̀émálè	ṣ̀s̀ema	ṣ̀s̀émáè	ṣ̀s̀émḡáè	ṣ̀s̀émḡá	ṣ̀ṣ̀ómáè	ṣ̀mà	ìkámḡà	ìkámḡà	ours
ṣ̀s̀iḡà	ṣ̀s̀iḡà	ṣ̀s̀iḡà	ṣ̀s̀éḡà	ṣ̀s̀éḡà	ṣ̀s̀éḡà	ṣ̀s̀éḡà	ṣ̀s̀éḡà	ṣ̀ṣ̀oḡà	ṣ̀wà	ìkàḡà	ìkàḡà	yours(plural)
ṣ̀s̀alè	ṣ̀s̀elè	ṣ̀s̀alè	ṣ̀s̀elè	ṣ̀s̀énàì	ṣ̀s̀è	ṣ̀s̀elè	ṣ̀s̀elè	ṣ̀ṣ̀iḡà	ṣ̀ṣ̀iḡà	ìkè	ìkèlè	theirs

Details of relatedness exhibited by Esan speech forms in possessive pronoun markers were as follows.

- (i). The form of the possessive pronoun marker in use by Ogwa and Igueben were more identical with those of the nearby Edo language are as presented:

Table 12A: Possessive pronoun forms in Ogwa, Igueben and Edo

	Ogwa	Igueben	Edo	Gloss
1.	ᵛmè	ᵛmè	ᵛóᵛᵛè	mine
2.	Ówε	ᵛwε	ᵛóᵛᵛè	yours
3.	ᵛᵛlé	ᵛᵛ	ᵛᵛíjè	his/hers/its
4.	ᵛᵛómáè	ᵛmà	ᵛᵛímã	ours
5.	ᵛᵛᵛβa	ᵛwà	ᵛᵛúwâ	yours
6.	ᵛᵛíã	ᵛxírà	ᵛᵛírã	theirs

- (ii). The possessive marker in use in Ugboha and Ilushi share segmental identity with those in use by speakers of Ibo, who occupy the area locatedted across the Niger river, which borders Esanland on the Eastern part The latter is the main speech area of these Esan speech forms. Data in Table 12B illustrate these occurrences.

Table 12B: Relatedness of possessive pronoun forms between Ugboha, Ilushi and Igbo

	Ugboha	Illushi	Ibo	Gloss
7.	ìkémε	ìkémε	ṅkémí	mine
8.	ìkε	ìkε	ṅkègí	yours(singular)
9.	ìkᵛé	ìkᵛé	ṅkèyá	his/hers
10.	ìkàmâ	ìkàmâ	ṅkèápì	ours
11.	ìkàβâ	ìkàβâ	ṅkè únù	yours(plural)
12.	ìkè	ìkèlé	ṅkèhá	theirs

Interactions arising from socio-economic activities are the more obvious explanations for the identified similarities between the aforementioned Esan speech forms, and the neighbouring Edo and Ibo languages respectively. Other explanations may be found in the history of the origins of the primary settlers in these speech areas.

4.3.1.4 Interrogative pronouns

A comparison of micro grammatical markers of three interrogative expressions across Esan speech forms emphasized some relatedness patterns which emerged from the preceding comparisons. The interrogative expressions which were compared were:

- a. What is it?
- b. Which is it?
- c. Who is it?

The relatedness patterns which were emphasized were:

- (i). Igueben and Ogwa were isolated from other Esan speech forms, as earlier shown (see 4.2, 4.3.1.3), and showed consistence in their affinity with Edo language in their forms for items (b) and (c).
- (ii). The relatedness exhibited by Udo, Ugboha and Ubiaza in their forms for item (c) above, re-echoed that shown in their identical sound inventories (see 4.1), which led to the deduction that these speech forms were probable earlier forms of Esan.
- (iii). Besides the observations made in (i) and (ii) above, Esan speech forms under focus exhibited close relatedness in their forms for the interrogative expressions under focus in this sub section.

The relationships highlighted in (i), (ii) and (iii) above are illustrated in table 13.

Table 13: Interrogative pronoun forms across Esan speech forms

Language	Interrogative form	Gloss
Ewatto	Ugbeḡun	Who is it?
bɔxi	bèxi	Which is it?
enèlâ	nèlâ	Who is it?
ɔlâ	hɔlâ	Who is it?
	Uromi	
	bèlâ	
	bɔxi	
	enèâ	
	ɔlâ	
	Ekpoma	
	bèlâ	
	enèlâ	
	ɔβɔlâ	
	Irrua	
	bèlâ	
	enèlâ	
	ɔβɔlâ	
	Igubeben	
	bâxi	
	denɔxi	
	ɔβɔnɔ	
	Udo	
	bèxi	
	nèlâ	
	knɔ	
	Ugboha	
	bènɔ	
	enèâ	
	knɔ	
	Ubiaza	
	Bèxi	
	enjà	
	Knɔ	
	Ilushi	
	bé	
	nèlâ	
	kalɔ	
	Ogwa	
	bèxi	
	denɔxiβɔ	
	denɔxiβɔ	
	Edo	
	βɔxi	
	denɔxi	
	ânɔ	
	Gloss	
	Who is it?	
	Which is it?	
	Who is it?	

4.3.2 Lexical counting systems

4.3.2.1 Numerals

A comparison of forms for the ordinal numerals 1 – 22, and for the terminals 30 – 100, revealed an additive rather than a subtractive counting system across Esan speech forms. Observed differences in this regard were reflected in the forms of the additive markers. Three forms of markers were identified across Esan speech forms as follows:

- (i) [βí, bí] 'and'
- (ii) [ɲâ] 'on top, plus'
- (iii) Accumulative (zero marker)

The use of the identified numeral markers across Esan speech forms are as illustrated:

1.	[igbé βísè, igbé bí sè,]	[ɔ kpá ɲá igbé]	[igbéá]
	ten and five	one on/plus ten	Ten, three
	"fifteen"	"eleven"	"thirteen"

Table 14 features these occurrence across Esan speech forms.

Table 14: Grammatical markers of lexical counting systems across Esan speech forms

S/N	Ogwa	Udo	Igueben	Ewatto	Ubiaza	Ohordua	Irrua	Ugboha	Illushi	Uromi	Ugbegun	Ekpoma	gloss
1.	ጋkpáñáìgbé	ùgbólጋ	òwጋጋ	ùgbóvò	ùgbólጋ	ùgbólጋ	ùgbólጋ	ìgbólጋ	ìgbólጋ	ìgbólጋó	ùgbólጋ	ùgbólጋ	eleven
2.	èvāñáìgbé	ìgbèvā	ìwévā	ìgbévā	ìgbèvā	ìgbèvā	ìgbèvā	ìgbèvā	ìgbèvā	ìgbèvā	ìgbèvā	ìgbèvā	twelve
3.	èāñáìgbé	èāñáìgbé	ìwérā	ìgbérā	ìgbéā	ìgbéā	ìgbéā	ìgbébéā	ìgbébéā	ìgbéléā	ìgbéléā	ìgbéléā	thirteen
4.	ènèñáìgbé	ènèñáìgbé	ìwéné	ìgbéné	ìgbéné	ìgbéné	ìgbéné	ìgbébéné	ìgbébéné	ìgbéné	ìgbéné	ìgbéné	fourteen
5.	ìsèñáìgbé	ìsèñáìgbé	ìkìèsùgìé	ìgbéhé	ìsèñáìgbé	ìgbéhé	ìgbìlìné	ìgbéβìsè	ìgbéβìsè	ìgbéhé	Ìsèñáìgbé	ìfèsùdጋé	Fifteen
6.	èhāñáìgbé	èhāñáìgbé	èhāñáìgbé	èhāñáìgbé	èhāñáìgbé	ìgbéhā	ìgbéhā	ìgbéβèhā	ìgbéβèhā	ìgbéhā	èhāñáìgbé	ìgbéhā	sixteen
7.	ùdጋé	ùdጋé	ùgጋé	ጋgbጋ	ùé	ùé	ùdጋé	ùé	ùé	ùdጋé	ùdጋé	ùdጋé	twenty
8.	ùdጋéጋkpá	ùdጋéጋkpá	ጋkpáñáùgጋé	ጋkpáñáጋgbጋ	ጋkpáñáùé	ጋkpáñáùé	ùdጋéጋkpá	uèβጋkpá	ùéβጋkpá	ùdጋéጋkpá	ùdጋéጋkpá	ùdጋéጋkpá	twentyone
9.	ùdጋéጋìvā	Ùdጋéጋìvā	èvāñáùgጋé	èvāñáጋgbጋ	èvāñáùé	èvāñáùé	Ùdጋéጋìvā	ùéβèvā	ùéβèvā	ùdጋéጋìvā	ùdጋéጋìvā	ùdጋéጋìvā	two
10.	ጋgbā	ጋgbā	ጋgbā	ጋgbìyó	ጋgbā	ጋgbìyó	ጋgbā	ùéβìgbé	ùéβìgbé	ጋgbā	ጋgbā	ጋgbā	Thirty
11.	ጋgbጋèvā	ጋgbጋèvā	ìjévā	ìjévā	égbጋìvā	ጋgbጋèvā	ጋgbጋèvā	égbጋèvā	égbጋèvā	égbጋèvā	égbጋèvā	égbጋèvā	Forty

Available data revealed that Esan speech forms exhibited a lack of consistence in the use of anyone form of additive marker. A general drift from one to the other of the three identified forms of additive markers was observed.

An explanation for this characteristic in the lexical counting system across Esan speech forms may be found in the market based economy of the Esan people highlighted in the introductory chapter of this work (see 1.2.3). Records revealed that the net work marketing system, which obtains in Esanland dates several years back. Such regular economic activity, which constituted a source of livelihood for participants, would enhance language contact situation and ultimately result in this linguistic characteristic.

The observations identified above account only for the specified numeral categories as provided by the main instrument for this work. They do not account for other numeral categories which may exist across Esan speech forms under study.

Summary

Findings from a comparison of micro-grammatical markers in pronoun and lexical counting systems across Esan speech forms are summarized thus:

- (i) Igueben and Ogwa showed a closer affinity with Edo language, than other speech forms, in pronominal forms. This occurrence is attributable to geographical proximity of these speech areas to those of Edo. In this regard, the fact of Igueben LGA's geographical and political affiliation, in the recent past to Benin, the main speech area of the Edo language, is worthy of note. The location of Ogwa's speech areas is just as relevant.
- (ii) Similarities in pronominal forms observed between Ugboha and Ilushi, on the one hand, and Ibo language located closest to their speech areas across The River Niger, on the other, points to socio-economic activities as probable explanations for that occurrence.
- (iii) The linguistic affinity shown to exist between Ubiaza, Ugboha and Udo, as revealed in the comparison of their sound inventories, re-echoed in their forms for the interrogative 'who is it?', a form which as shown from available data, was peculiar to these three (see Table 13). This observation further substantiated the probability of their being earlier forms of Esan. The location of their speech areas in the more naturally endowed part of Esan land (Esan B - see 1.1) is a possible explanation for earlier settlement.

- (iv) Comparison of micro grammatical markers in numerals across Esan speech forms revealed a general bias to an additive counting system. All twelve varieties showed a lack of consistence in the use of the identified forms of grammatical markers.

4.4. Other research considerations of relatedness of Esan speech forms

The extent to which the twelve Esan speech forms were mutually intelligible, as well as structural peculiarities between Esan and her closer neighbours were examined to further strengthen findings about the dialectal status of Esan. Our observations are as presented:

4.4.1 Levels of mutual intelligibility across Esan speech forms

As earlier explained in the initial chapter of this work (see 1.4), two varieties of a language can only be adjudged dialects of that language on the condition that both are mutually intelligible otherwise, they are two different languages. By this principle, the fact that the twelve Esan speech forms under focus in this work are mutually intelligible is not in doubt. The question addressed here whose answer is one of the goals of the present study is that of the extent of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms. To this end, the 86% lexico-statistical value for identifying Esan dialect was adopted (see 3.2.3.4). Lexico-statistical values between Esan speech forms as presented earlier (see 4.2) reflected levels of mutual intelligibility between them thus:

- (1). When both segmental and tonal constitution of lexical items were compared across Esan speech forms, each of them scored below 86% resemblance with one another. The deduction from this occurrence was that based on this parameter of comparison, mutual intelligibility between the twelve Esan speech forms was low. The same observation of low level mutual intelligibility was recorded when only segmental constitution of lexical items across these speech forms were compared, as no two Esan speech forms showed upto 86% linguistic resemblance. In both cases of comparison, Ewatto and Ohordua recorded the higher levels of resemblances – 61% and 64% respectively.
- (2). A comparison of lexical items across Esan speech forms with tonal constitution of lexical items as parameter revealed a higher level of mutual intelligibility between them as follows.

- (a) Igueben, Irrua, Ugbegun and Ugboha were revealed as exhibiting a high level of mutual intelligibility as they showed linguistic resemblances of between 86% and 89%.
- (b) Ewatto, Uromi, Udo, Ogwa, Ubiaza, Ekpoma, Ohordua, Ilushi, Ugboha and Ugbegun recorded a very high level of mutual intelligibility – above 90% linguistic resemblances, whereas Igueben recorded below 86% linguistic resemblances with all except Irrua, Ugbegun and Ugboha as stated in (a).

The correlation between levels of mutual intelligibility shared by Esan speech forms and their qualification as dialects of the language emerged in this study and is worthy of note. The relationship is stated thus:

- (3) The higher the level of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms, the lower the probability of their qualifying as autonomous dialects of the language.
- (4) Conversely the lower the level of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms the higher the probability of their qualification as autonomous dialects of the language.

These conditions are clearly illustrated by the results of lexicostatistical analysis (see 4.2) as well as those of the assessment of the levels of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms in this section.

4.4.2 The “Esanness” of Esan – Structural differences between Esan and her closest linguistic neighbours

The aim in this section was to identify some structural features which distinguish Esan from her closest linguistic neighbours and which gave the language that peculiarity that differentiates it from her immediate linguistic environment. As this was not the main goal of this study, only the sound and tonal inventories of these linguistic neighbours available from previous studies were examined against the background of data on Esan.

4.4.2.1 Esan's Closest Linguistic Neighbours

Elugbe's Edoid family tree (see figure 3) classified Esan among others as Proto North Central Edoid (PNCE). By that classification, the closest linguistic neighbours to Esan are Edo, (Bini) to the left (henceforth Edo) and the dialect cluster of Ora – Emai – Iueleha (henceforth Ora) to the right. The sound and tonal inventories of Edo and Ora from recent previous studies are presented below to enable a comparison between these linguistic forms and those of Esan as provided in this work (see 4.1).

(I) Sound and tonal inventories of Edo

(a). Sounds

Recent works such as Omozuwa (2003) proposed the following sound inventory for Edo.

p	b		t	d		k	g	kp	gb
β		f	v	s	z		x	ɣ	h
m		ɱ		n		ɲ		ŋw	
				l					
				r					
				ɹ		j			w
						r			

(b). Tones

Previous studies (Omozuwa 1993, Adeniyi 2000) revealed the distinctive tones of Edo as high (H) and low (L) which occur freely to form the patterns in disyllabic nouns: HH, LL, LH, HL.

Omozuwa states that in larger utterances, the language features the downstep phenomenon where a sequence of low tones with or without an intervening high drifts down in pitch. Similarly, a sequence of high tones with intervening lows drifts down in pitch. Adeniyi explains that this downstepped high [H!H] is regarded as a sequence of HLH in the language. Omozuwa also states that "a phonological low tone is realized as a falling tone [Λ] when it immediately follows a high tone.

(2) **Sounds and Tonal Inventories of Ora**
 (a) **Sounds**

For linguistic information on Ora (Ora – Emai – Iuleha), this work depends heavily on Emai which appeared to be the most studied of the dialect cluster. Schaefer & Egbokhare (1999) identified the following sound inventory for Emai.

Sound inventory of Emai

p b		t d		k g	kp	gb
β	f v s z	ʃ ʒ	x ɣ			h
			tʃ dʒ			
m		n	ɲ		ɲw	
		l				
		r				
			j		w	

(b) **Tones**

Emai tones were given as high (H), downstepped – high (!H) and low (L). These tones combined within lexical nouns, adjectives and post-verbal adverbs to form the following patterns.

LL, LH, HL, HHL, H!H, HL!H,

4.4.2.2 Structural differences between Esan and her closest linguistic neighbours

(a) Differences in Sound inventories

Available data revealed that Esan shared an identical vowel sound inventory with Edo and Emai comprising seven oral and five nasal vowels (see 4.1). The difference in sound inventories between these linguistic groups emerged in their consonant sound inventories thus:

- (i) Where Emai and Esan (see 4.1) possessed 28 consonant phones each, Edo featured 27.
- (ii) Emai lacked the labio-dental nasal [ɱ] which Edo and Esan featured.
- (iii) Esan lacked the voiced labio-velar nasal [ɲw] which Edo and Emai featured.

- iv) The palatal fricatives [ʃ, ʒ] and their affricate counterparts [tʃ, dʒ] which featured in the sound inventories of Esan and Emai were conspicuously absent in Edo.
- v) Unlike Esan and Emai which featured only one type of alveolar approximant, [r], Edo featured three [r, ɹ, r̥].

Tonal differences

- (b) Tonal differences between Esan (see 2.1.1) and her linguistic neighbours were revealed thus:
- (i) Previous studies and available data on tones in Esan did not reveal the downstep phenomenon which is prevalent in Edo and Emai.
- (ii) Available data showed that where Esan tonal system did not feature an all high tonal patterns or a final high on lexical items, Edo and Emai did so. Specifically, all high tones in final position drop to a HL in Esan (Osiruemu 2005).

The linguistic differences between Esan and her linguistic neighbours highlighted above underlines the fact of the linguistic peculiarity of Esan when compared with Edo and Emai. The differences in sound inventories and occurrence of a tonal phenomenon in Edo and Emai not recorded for Esan are obvious explanations for the linguistic dichotomies which classified them as different languages. It is in these differences and peculiarities that the Esanness of Esan may be identified, for although Esan showed greater structural resemblances with Emai than Edo as far as their sound inventories were concerned, the tonal structures of Emai and Edo distanced them further from Esan linguistically.

4.5. Highlights of data analysis

Findings from analysis of data presented in this chapter were highlighted as follows. Examination of available data confirmed the postulation that Esan consists of more than one dialect. This verdict is a function of linguistic evidence which emanated from the results of the comparisons between twelve Esan speech forms, along the parameters selected for this study. The Esan speech forms were Ewatto, Ugbegun, Udo, Uromi, Ogwa, Ugboha, Ubiaza, Ekpoma, Ohordua, Irrua, Igueben and Ilushi. Parameters and the linguistic evidence provided for proposing that Esan consisted of more than one dialect were as presented:

(1). **Diaphonic evidence**

Results of comparison of the sound systems of twelve Esan speech forms classified them into eight dialect groups (see 4.1.1). A further examination of phonetic processes prevalent across the speech forms under study revealed finer levels of relatedness between them. Phonostatistical evidence from this level of analysis also substantiated the identification of some speech forms – Udo, Ugboha and Ubiaza – as probable earlier forms of Esan. Geographical location of the speech areas of those three speech forms in the part of Esan land adjudged more naturally endowed was suggested as a probable reason for this early settlement pattern.

(2) **Lexicostatistical and tonostatistical evidence**

At this level of comparison, Esan speech forms were examined along three parameters. These and the deductions which emanated from analysis of available data were:

- (a). Lexicostatistical comparisons between the twelve Esan speech forms under focus in this work, identified each as an autonomous dialect of Esan, since all the speech forms attained below the 86% cut off for linguistic relatedness adopted for this work (see 4.2.1, 4.2.2).
- (b). Tonostatistical comparisons between the twelve Esan speech forms grouped them into two dialects (see 4.2.3). However, the argument that tone alone could not constitute language countered this verdict, since tones in tone languages did not occur in isolation without the complementing roles of the segments which actually bore them. This argument opens up probable research areas for tone languages.

The findings in this work clearly fault Okojie and Ejele(1987) that the 35 clans of Esan speak various dialects and that phonological and phonotactic processes are very similar in all Esan dialects (see chapters one and two). Analysis of that separated Esan into a specific number of dialects already stated, depending on the specified linguistic indices. The 35 clans of Esan as enumerated in that work fell within the twelve speech forms identified by the subjects for this work as follows:

Ekpoma: Egoro, Ekpoma, Urohi, Idoa.

Ewatto: Emu, Ewatto, Okhuesan.

Igueben: Ebelle, Igueben.

Ilushi: Ilushi, Oria, Uzea, Onogholo.

Irrua: Ewu, Opoji, Irrua.

Ogwa: Amahor, Ujiogba, Ogwa, Ugun.

Ohordua: Ewohimi, Ohordua.

Ubiaza: Ubiaza.

Udo: Ekpon, Udo.

Ugbegun: Ewossa, Ugbegun.

Ugboha: Emu, Oria, Ifeku, Ugboha.

Uromi: Uromi, Uzea.

3. Other grammatical evidence

A comparison of micro-grammatical markers in pronoun and lexical counting systems across Esan speech forms, emphasized certain observations from preceding comparisons while revealing new insights about them. These observations are:

- (i). Igueben and Ogwa dialects showed consistent isolation from other Esan speech forms, and close relatedness to Edo language, their closest neighbours, in pronominal forms.
- (ii). Illushi and Ugboha exhibited relatedness with Igbo language spoken across the Niger River, which borders Esanland to the East. This occurrence was attributed to long standing socio-economic interactions between speakers of Esan and Ibo.
- (iii). An additive lexical counting system was shown to dominate across Esan varieties, as far as available data revealed. The popular market based economy of the Esans was proffered as a probable explanation for this linguistic situation.
- (iv). Levels of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms was shown to be correlated with the grouping of Esan dialects as Esan speech forms which shared a high level of mutual intelligibility fell into the same dialect group while those whose level of mutual intelligibility was low fell into separate dialect groups.
- (v). Esan exhibited structural differences in sound and tonal inventories that distinguished her from her closest linguistic neighbours of Edo and Ora.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDIES

5.0 Introduction

This work is brought to a conclusion in this chapter, with an overview of research procedures, questions and problems, findings, implications for theory, policy and practice in this area of study.

5.1 Conclusion

This research effort is a study in dialectology. Its main aim was to empirically evaluate the common claim that Esan is multidialectal. Sub-goals of this effort included identifying Esan dialects by determining the levels of relatedness between twelve Esan speech forms and their levels of mutual intelligibility. This dialect study which was based mainly on the lexicon of Esan, was three dimensional – structural – historical – geographical – with precedence given to the structural dimension of the study. Thus the present study is basically a structural dialectology of Esan in line with the structural framework within which it was conducted. The speech forms identified were Ekpoma, Ewatto, Igueben, Ilushi, Irrua, Ogwa, Ohordua, Ubiaza, Udo, Ugbegun, Ugboha, Uromi. Data which were elicited from twelve adult Esan native speakers with the Ibadan word list of 400 basic items as the main instrument. This data were transcribed in phonetic tradition using the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) format. Comparative analyses of these speech forms were conducted within the limits of available data for this work. In this regard, the following grammatical levels of the identified speech forms came into focus – phonetics, phonology, tonology and micro grammatical features. Other areas of research included the determination of levels of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms under focus. The linguistic relatedness between Esan and her closest linguistic neighbours of Edo and the dialect cluster of Ora-Emai-Iuleha were also examined to determine probable peculiarities of Esan. Analysis of available data were conducted using some principles of lexicostatistical glottochronology, an approach to the historical study of languages, used to determine linguistic relatedness and distances between languages thought to be related.

Results which emerged from the selected levels of analysis of available data, provided empirical evidence in favour of the claim that Esan comprises more than one dialect. Specifically, a diaphonic examination of the twelve Esan speech forms under

focus in this work separated them into eight dialect groups; three dialects emerged from a consideration of phonological processes; lexicostatistical analysis of Esan speech forms revealed them as autonomous Esan dialects when segmental and tonal constitution on lexical items on the one hand and only segmental constitution of lexical items on the other hand, formed the basis for analysis; two Esan dialects were identified when only tonal constitution on lexical items was used as a parameter for comparison. The levels of mutual intelligibility which Esan speech forms exhibited correlated directly with their dialectal status, as speech forms belonging to the same dialect group featured a higher level of mutual intelligibility when compared with those which fell into different dialect groups. Esan featured structural peculiarities in sound and tonal inventories among her closest linguistic neighbours of Edo and the dialect cluster of Ora-Emai-Iuleha. These features as highlighted (see 4.4.2) revealed the "Esanness" of Esan.

This study therefore gave insights into the dialectal status of Esan. Specifically in this regard, Esan speech forms shared higher levels of relatedness when linguistic principles of comparison were lowered than when they were raised. Socio-economic activities, geographical location, as well as geopolitical affiliations were shown to be at play in some of the relationships exhibited by Esan speech forms. Phonological analysis provided evidence in favour of the postulation that Ubiaza, Ugboha and Udo speech forms predated others.

Settlement patterning indicated an Easternly beginning towards the Niger River – the areas earlier described as Esan B (Okojie 1994) - as the earliest settlement locations. This verdict is based on the evidence from available data which showed Esan speech forms spoken in this area as possessing more complex linguistic forms than others. Speech forms lost more sounds, and lexical forms became less complex with movement Westwards and Northwards – the area comprising the waterless plateau, earlier described as Esan A. This situation favours the argument that speakers of the speech forms spoken in these parts may have settled later than the former. Similarities in some linguistic features between the Easternly Esan speech forms and the Igbo across the Niger, was a pointer to the effects of contact situations, arising from socio-economic activities and geographical proximity.

Our analyses further revealed that although identical tonal configurations on lexical forms suggested a high level of mutual intelligibility between Esan speech forms, when both tonal and segmental constitution of lexical forms were used as parameters of

comparison, the language presented as a cluster of dialects. This position was strengthened by the individuality which emerged from the sound systems of most of the speech forms.

5.2 Suggestions for further studies

A major hindrance to a study in dialectology, as was encountered in the course of the present work, is in the methodology and theoretical framework for analysis. Experience gained from the present work revealed that, in spite of controversies which have existed over the years about the longstanding approach to comparative studies, as provided in the lexicostatistical glottochronology of Swadesh and Lees in the 1950s, scholars, as well as their mentors continued to employ its principles and insist on their use, even for studies which are not totally historical (see chapter three). In view of the recorded handicaps of these methods, especially for studies in dialectology, for which they were not originally built, the suggestion that more suitable methods be adopted could be explored. Dialectometry, a method which permits the measurement of linguistic distances between languages and dialects of a given geographical area, is one such method which could fill the gaps created by other methods, for dialectal studies.

The pioneering status of this work leaves unattended, many researchable areas in determining more comprehensively, the linguistic status of Esan. Further comparative research on other areas of grammar such as sentence structure, tense and aspect, may yet provide further evidence for making more far reaching statements about the dialectal status of Esan.

This work has opened a field of research in a novel way, not just for Esan but for other Nigerian languages. Unlike most previous studies in dialectology on other languages which did not give adequate considerations to the relevance of tone in tone languages in this field of linguistic research, an attempt was made to fill that gap in the present effort. This study has also provided an avenue for the documentation of probable varieties of Esan, an exercise relevant, not just for further linguistic research in this area but for the protection and sustenance of the language. The results of this work would act as input to further linguistic studies on Esan and other related languages.

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APPENDIX

Body of data for structural dialectology of Esan

S/N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
	Ebhoato	Ugbegun	Uromi	Udo	Ogua	Ugboha	Ubiaza	Ekpoma	Okhuedua	Iguebe	Irrua	Illushi	Edo/Bini	Englis
1.	úhɔwɔmɔ	úhɔmɔ	úhɔmɔ	úhɔmɔ	úhɔmɔ	úhɔmɔ	úhɔmɔ	úhúmmù	úhɔmɔ	úhúmmù	úhɔmɔ	úhɔmɔ	úhú	head
2.	étò	étò	étò	étò	étò	étò	étò	étò	étò	étò	étò	étò	étò	hair
3.	èlò	úkpéìlòlò	èlò	èlò	èlò	e ò	e l òlò	èlò	èlò	èlò	èlòlò	èlò	ào	eye
4.	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	èhɔ	ear
5.	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	ihwé	nose
6.	únú	únú	únú	únú	únú	únú	únú	únú	únú	únú	únú	únú	únú	mouth
7.	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	ákɔ	tooth
8.	úkpórám̩ é	ólám̩é	ólám̩é	ólám̩é	úkpórám̩ é	óám̩é	úkpórám̩ m̩é	ólám̩é	ólám̩é	ólám̩é	úkpórám̩ é	ólám̩é	áám̩é	Tongue
9.	āgbā	āgbā	āgbā	āgbā	āgbām̩é	éxwám̩á únú	ékpúnú	āgbā	āgbā	āgbām̩ é	āgbā	āgbā	irò	Jaw
10.	—	āgbā	āgbā	āgbā́á únú	āgbām̩é	āgbā	āgbā	irò	āgbā	āgbām̩ é	āgbā	īī	chin	
11.	íwāgbā	étwāgbā	étwāg bā	étwāg bā	étwāgbā	ítwāgbā	étwāgb à	étwāgbā	étwāgbā	étwāg bām̩é	étwāgb à	íwāgb à	bear	
12.	úrú	úrú	úrú	āxɔ	éjāi m̩é	úrú	úrú	úrú	úrú	úrú	úrú	úrú	neck	
13.	éjé	éwélé	íjé	íjé	éwé	íjé	íjélé	éwé	éjé	éwé	íjé	íjé	breast	
14.	—	údu	údu	údu	údu	údu	úkpúd ú	úkpúdú	údu	údu	údu	údu	heart	
15.	éke	ékélé	ékéé	éke	éke	ékéé	ékélé	éke	éke	ékó	ékélé	éke	belly (cat)	
16.	éke	íbié	ékéé	ékpòx	ékéke	ékéé	ékélé	éke	éke	ékó	ékélé	éke	Stomac	

			ékélé	òrò	éxurwék	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	h (ant navel)
17.	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	éxurwék	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	ùxɔ	h (ant navel)
18.	íkē òdíké	íkēké	íkèkè	íkèkè	íjèkè ^é	íkèkè	òdíké	íkèkè	íkèkè	íkèkè	íkèkè	íkèkè	ékpíjèké òdíjèké	ékpíjèké òdíjèké	ékpíjèké òdíjèké	back
19.	ójíáxòb ɔ	ízábɔ	óbɔ	íḍzábɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	arm
20.	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	óbɔ	hand
21.	éñjé	íñié	íñié	íñié	íkpeñjó bɔ	íñjé	íñié	úkpiñjé	íñié	íñjé	íkpiñié	íñjɔbɔ	íñié	íñié	íñié	nail
22.	ɔkpū	úwédi	úwédi	úgédi	úgédi	ɔkpū	ɔkpū	úwédi	ɔkpū	úwédi	ɔkpū	úwédi	íkèbè	íkèbè	íkèbè	buttock ^s
23.	ékié	ékwé	éxwé	ékwé	ékwé	éxwé	òpā	úkpekw ^é	éxwé	ékiá	ékwé	éxwé	ékiá	ékiá	ékiá	penis
24.	ójíòxòé	—	íkpróxí	éxí	áxìòé	etāxā	etāxā	īāxā	éki	úkègèb ^é	érāwé	etāxā	ékwáwé	ékwáwé	ékwáwé	thigh
25.	òé	òé	òé	òé	òé	òé	òé	òé	òé	òwé	érāwé	òé	òwé	òwé	òwé	leg
26.	édí	édí	édí	édí	édí	úddè	édí	édí	édí	úhè	édí	òxòì	úhè	úhè	úhè	vagina
27.	ígógò	ígógò	úgwé úgwél w	ígógò	ígógò	ígwóé	ígwóé	ígógò	ígwóé	ígógò	ígwóé	ígógò	ígwé	ígwé	ígwé	knee
28.	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	body
29.	óhíégbè	óhñā	úkínég bè	íñjámé gbè	íkprákpré gbè	óhñā	óhíégbè	óhíégbè	óhíégbè	égbè	égbè	égbè	íkprákpré gbè	íkprákpré gbè	íkprákpré gbè	skin
30.	úgwé	úgwé	úgwé	úgwé	úgwé	ígwé	ígwé	ígwé	úgwé	úgwé	úgwé	ígwé	úgwé	úgwé	úgwé	bone
31.	árā	árālè	árālè	árā	árāé	árāé	árālè	èságjé	árā	èságjé	árālè	árāé	èságjé	èságjé	èságjé	blood

	ási	ési	ikpèxijé	ási	ási	ési	ási	ási	ési	ási	ási	ási	ási	ési	ási	ási	ési	ási	ási	ési	ikasi	
51.	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	íxjàβɔ	pepper okra Plantain
52.	ɔgédérā	ɔxede	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔgédérā	ɔgédérā	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔgédérā	ɔgédérā	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔgédérā	ɔgédérā	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	
53.	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔgédérā	ɔgédérā	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔgédérā	ɔgédérā	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔgédérā	ɔgédérā	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	bannan a
54.	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔgédérā	ɔgédérā	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔgédérā	ɔgédérā	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔgédérā	ɔgédérā	ɔxédé	ɔxede	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	ɔxédé	
55.	àl omí	átè	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	ànùnù	orange
56.	isàèwé	èhjàwé	izâwé	sâwé	isàèwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	isâwé	ground nut
57.	éβjé	éβélé	éβélé	éβjé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	éβé	kolanut
58.	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	tábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	ítábà	tobacco
59.	òlú	òlúlu	òlúlu	ikpòlú	ikwòlú	òwú	òwú	òwú	òwú	òlú	òlú	òlú	òlú	òlú	òlú	òlú	òlú	òwú	òwú	òwú	òwú	cotton
60.	údi	éβilú	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	údi	Oil palm
61.	ikpé	ikpé	úkpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	ikpé	seed
62.	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	ilúmú	grass
63.	érā	órā	òkpòr	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	érā	tree
64.	ébbè	úkpebbè	ébbè	ébbè	Ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	ébbè	leaf

65.	ikpàkpé rà	ikpàkpé rà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkpé rà	ikpàkpé rà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkpé rà	ikpàkpé rà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkp érà	ikpàkpé rà	ikpàkpé rà	bank of tree	
66.	inje inje	injóra injóra	úli	inje inje	injéà injéà	ifjéà ifjéà	injéà injéà	inje inje	injéà injéà	inje inje	injéà injéà	injéà injéà	root								
67.	igbe igbe	úgbe úgbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	igbe igbe	thorn
68.	úkpròkp ò	úkperà úkperà	úkprúx úkpròk pò	éà éà	úkpròkp úkpròkp ò	úkpròkp úkpròkp ò	úkpròk úkpròk pò	úkperà úkperà	úkpròkp úkpròkp ò	úkpròk úkpròk pò	úkperà úkperà	úkpròkp úkpròkp ò	stick								
69.	éranàrék pɔ	éranàrék pɔ	òrà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	firewo od
70.	ígjébi ígjébi	ídɔmúb i	ídɔmjí bí	ídɔébi éà	íbi éà	úɔɔmɛ bí	úɔɔm úbi	ígjmbi éà	ígjébi éà	ídɔámí bí	ídɔmí i	ídɔmí i	íbi éà	íbi éà	íbi éà	íbi éà	íbi éà	íbi éà	íbi éà	íbi éà	charco ol
71.	éà éà	éàlé éàlé	éàlé éàlé	éà éà	éàlé éàlé	éàlé éàlé	éàlé éàlé	éàlé éàlé	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	éà éà	fire
72.	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	ixòxò ixòxò	smoke
73.	émú émú	emɔ emɔ	émɔ émɔ	émú émú	émwɛ émwɛ	èmɔɔ èmɔɔ	emɔle emɔle	emò emò	emò emò	émɔɔ émɔɔ	emɔ emɔ	émɔ émɔ	émɔ émɔ	émɔ émɔ	émɔ émɔ	émɔ émɔ	émɔ émɔ	émɔ émɔ	émɔ émɔ	émɔ émɔ	ashes
74.	áxámé áxámé	áxé áxé	áxé áxé	áxé áxé	áxé áxé	áxé áxé	áxé áxé	áxé áxé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	áxámé áxámé	Waterp ot
75.	áxé áxé	úwàwà úwàwà	égé égé égé	égé égé	égé égé	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	áxé áxé	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	úwàwà úwàwà	Cookin g pot
76.	úkòkò úkòkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò úkò	kòkò kòkò	ēbā ēbā	úgbà úgbà	úgbà úgbà	úkò úkò	úkòkò úkòkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	úkò úkò	calabas h
77.	údonàré lémi	ónɔ ónɔ	údoná rénási údo	ónɔ ónɔ	ólɔ ólɔ	údo údo	údo údo	údonàré némi	údo údo	ólɔ ólɔ	údo údo	údo údo	grindin g stone								

93.	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	cloth mitca	
94.	éwúáɔɔ oɔ	égbú	éwúàg bádéw ù	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	úkpɔ	robc
95.	áru	úkpéru	áru úkpár ù	úkpér ù	úkpéru	úkpàru	úkpàru	úkpàru	úkpàru	úkpéru	áru	úkpér ù	úkpéru	úkpár ù	éru	hat/cap					
96.	óhjówé	íbatà	íbatà	íbatà	íbatà	óhjà	óhjà	íbatà	íbatà	óhjà	óhjówé	íbatà	íbatà	óhjà	íbatà	shoe					
97.	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	íxó	money					
98.	únuúró	éxú	ódé	ódé	éxú	ódé	ódé	éxú	ódé	éxú	ódé	ódé	éxú	ódé	éxú	door					
99.	ídjeké	égbúwá	égbúw á	égbúw á	égbúwá	égbóà	égbúw á	égbúwá	égbúwá	égbúwá	égbúwá	égbòw á	égbúwá	égbúw á	égbéké	wall					
100.	ùxà	ékɔwá	ékɔwá	ùxà	ùxà	ékɔgwá	ékɔwá	ùxà	ùxà	ùxà	ùxà	ùwúxà	ékɔgwá	ékòà	ùwówá	room					
101.	úwá	úwá	úwá	úwá	úwá	óà	úwá	úwá	úwá	úwá	úwá	òwá	úwá	óà	òwá	house					
102.	úkídúm ù	ídmi	éko ígwe ò	ágbáéβ ò	ígwe	éko	—	ígwe	úduúmù	úkídu mù	éβómá	éko	ígwe	village							
103.	úkílwé βò	ókpréβò	ágbáéβ ò	ódiwé nà	ísi	ágbádéβ ò	—	éβò	éβò	éβò	éβò	—	ókpréβò	town							
104.	ómi	úhjàmé	ómi	ómi	úhjómi ómi	ómi	úhjàmé ómi	úhàè	ómi	ɔgɔɔɔ	—	ómi	úhàè	well							

117	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	éké	sand	
118	íkù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	itɔ	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	èbùbù	dust
119	ékénàrɪ ò	èxwɔɪɔ	éké	èxwèr é	èxwɔɪɔ	égbɔ	èxwɔɪɔ	èxwéáɪɔ	òvɔɪlé	òvwéénɔɪ é	mud														
120	áhòhò	éhòhò	èfi áhòhò	áhòhò	éhòhò	áhèhè	áhòhò	áhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	éhòhò	wind
121	áménɔɪɔ	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	ámé	rain
122	òvéáɪɔ	òvɔɪ	òvɔɪ	òvwééɪɔ é	òvézé	òvwééáɪɔ é	òvɔɪ	òvééáɪɔ	òvɔɪ	òvwéénɔɪ é	òvé	sunshine													
123	òvé	òhélé	òvɔɪ	òvwé	òvé	òvɔɪ	òvé	òvɔɪ	òvɔɪ	òvwéénɔɪ é	òvɔɪ	òvɔɪ	òvé	sun											
124	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	úkì	moon
125	áhjà	áhjéhié	áhjàh à	áhjà	áhjéhié	íkphàhjà	áwáwò xù	áhjà	áhjéhié	áhjéhié	áhjéhié	áhjà	áhjéhié	star											
126	édé	ódámé	ódámé	úkpéd é	édé	éfià	édéwé	úkpédé	ódámé	édé	day														
127	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ɔsáɔɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ɔsáɔɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	ásɔ	night
128	édéwé	éwjéɔkp á	éwéwj é	ɔsèwje á	éwjéɔkp á	éfià	ɔsèwjeéfi ó	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	édéwé	dawn
129	ébjúki	òdjiòbjúk i	ébjúki	ékpòbj úki	ògjiòbí	ébjúki	ébjúki	ébjúki	òdjiòbí	ébjúki	darkness														

130	óβwè	ówè	ówè	ówè	óβè	ówè	óβé	sleep												
131	íɔɔɔɔ	ésɔ	iwénà	iwénà	ésɔ	és'ɔ	iwénà	iwénà	iwénà	ésɔ	iwénà	iwínà	work							
132	òkúìò	óxcɔlè	óxcɔlè	óxcɔ	óxcɔ	òkúìò	òkúìò	òkúìò	óxcɔ	òkúìò	òkwó	war								
133	ófè	ófemū	ófè	ófè	ófè	ófè	ófè	ófemū	ófè	ófè	òhá	ófemū	ófè	ófè	òhá	òhá	òhá	òhá	òhá	fear
134	òhwámjé	òhámé	òhámjé	òhámjé	òhámjé	òhámjé	òhámjé	òhámé	òhámjé	òhámé	òhámjé	hunger								
135	òhámjâ mè	òβámé	òhámjâ mè	òhámé	òhámjâ mè	thirst														
136	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	úkpe	year
137	éxéámé	òɔɔ	írɔámé	éxóɔɔ	éxóɔɔ	òɔɔ	éxɔɔɔɔɔ	òɔɔ	éxóɔɔ	rainy season										
138	ókà	ókàlè	ókàè	éxókà	éxókàè	okae	éxókàlè	ókàè	ókà	ókà	ókà	ókà	ókàlè	ókàè	éxóhúù	éxóhúù	éxóhúù	éxóhúù	éxóhúù	dry season
139	ìlò	ìlòlò	ìlò	ìò	ìlò	ìò	ìlòlò	ìlò	ìlò	ìlò	ìhwhá	ìlòlò	ìlò	ìlò	ìhwhá	ìhwhá	ìhwhá	ìhwhá	ìhwhá	song
140	óxà	ɔxcà	ɔxcà	óxà	ɔxcà	óxà	óxà	óxà	ɔxcà	óxà	story									
141	úkɔɔɔ kpá	ɔtá	ɔtá	ɔtá	émjɔ	ɔtá	úkɔɔɔtá	ɔtá	émjɔ	word										

180	úhjäëkpr é	áhjäëkpr é	áhjäëk pé	áhjéié kpé	áhjäëkpr é	úhjäëkpr é	úhjäéék pé	áhjéiéékpr é	úhjäëkpré	áhwá	áhjéiéék pé	áhjäëk pé	áhwá	hawk
181	áxwòxw á	úr	úr	áxòxw á	úr	áxòxwá	úr	áxòxwá	áxwòxwá	á	úr	úr	á	guinea fowl
182	áβiβi	ɔwɔ	úβú ákògá	áβiβiá sɔ	áβiβi/ɔ wɔ	áβiβi/ ákògá	ákògá áβiβií	ákògá	—	ékwâx á	ákògá	áβiβi	égwé	bat
183	ɔjɔ	ɔjɔ	ɔjɔ	ɔjɔ	ɔjɔ	ɔhà	ɔjɔ	ɔjɔ	ɔjɔ	ɔmâ	ɔjɔ	ɔhà	ɔmá	person
184	éíí	énjɔjɔ	éíí	éni	éni	éi	éni	éíí	óní	éni	éíí	éni	éni	name
185	òkpiá	ɔkpiɔbà	òkpiá	òkpiá	òkpiá	ɔmɔhè	òkpiá	òkpiá	òkpiá	òkpiá	òkpiá	òkpiá	òkpiá	man
186	òkpiá	òkpiá	ɔmòkpr já	òkpiá	òkpiá	ɔmɔhè	ɔmòkprj á	òkpiá	òkpiá	òkpiá	ɔmɔè	òkpiá	òkpiá	male
187	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔ	husband
188	óxwò	ɔxwɔbà	óxwò	óxwò	óxwò	óxwò	óxwò	óxwò	óxwò	óxwò	óxwò	óxwéɛg bé	óxwò	woman
189	óxwò	óxwò	ɔmóx wò	óxwò	óxwò	óxwò	ɔmóxw ò	óxwò	óxwò	óxwò	ɔmámé	óxwò	óxwò	female
190	ámjé	óxwɔjɔ	ámjé	óxwò	óxwɔbà	ámjé	óβiáhà	óβiáhà	ámjé	ámjé	óβiáhà	ámjé	ɔβóɔwɔm á	wife
191	ɔɔɔmáé	ɔɔɔmáé	ɔɔɔmá é	ɔɔɔmá	éɔjɔmâ	ɔɔɔmáé	ɔɔɔmáí é	éɔjɔmá	ɔɔɔmá	éɔjɔmâ á	éɔɔɔɔ	ɔɔɔmá é	ɔmáè	old person
192	ɔwáíé	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔɔɔ	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔjɔ	ɔɔjɔ	senior/older

204	òrwǎ	irwɛɛɛɛɛɛ	òrwǎ	òrwǎ	òrwɛ	òrwǎ	òrwǎ	òrwɛ	òrwǎ	òrwǎ	òrwɛ	òrwǎ	òrwɛ	òrwǎ	òrwǎɛ	In-law
205	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	òrúmmù nɛ ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛɛɛɛ	ɛ̀rúnnɛ	Guest(s) tronger
206	ùgɛbǎlù	ɔmmɛ	ɔmmɛlɛ	ùkòlù	ɔɛɛɛ	ɔɛɛ	ɔɛɛ	ɔmmɛ	ùkòlù	ɔɛɛɛ	ùkòlù	ɔɛɛɛ	ɔmmɛ	ɔɛɛ	ɔsɛ	friend
207	ɔnnòɔɛ	òɔɛ	òɔɛ	òɔɛ	ògɛ	ɔbà	òɔɛ	òɔɛ	ògɛ	ògɛ	òɔɛ	ògɛ	òɔɛ	òɔɛ	ɛ̀nògɛ ɔbà	king
208	òhwɛ	òhwɛ	òhwɛ	ɛ̀nɛgɛ ɛ̀lamɛ	òhwɛ	òhwɛ	hunter									
209	óɔɛ	óɔɛ	óɔɛ	óɔɛ	óɛ	óɔɛ	óɔɛ	thief								
210	ɔbɛwíkɛpà kɛpɛrà	ɔbɛwɛrà	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	ɔbò	Doctor (native)
211	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	àzɛ	wich
212	ɔxǎɛɛɛɛ	ɔxǎɛɛɛɛ	ɔxǎɛɛɛ ɔ	ɔxǎɛɛɛ ɔ	ɔxǎɛɛɛɛ	ɔxǎɛɛɛɛ ɔ	ɔxǎɛɛɛɛ	chief								
213	ɛ̀bò	ùxúmm wɛbɛ	ɛ̀bò ùxúmm ù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ìxúmmù	ùxù	Medici ne cham
214	ɛ̀bɔ	ɛ̀bɔ	ɛ̀bɔ	ɛ̀bɔ	ɛ̀bɔ	ìzòbò	ɛ̀bɔ	ɛ̀bɔ	ìxúmmù	ìzòbò	ɛ̀bɔ	kòkòlɛ	ɛ̀bɔ	ɛ̀bɔ	ɛ̀bɔ	fetish sign
215	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	òlmmì	corpse

216	òsɛ̀nɔ̀b wà	òsɛ̀nɔ̀bù lwà	òsɛ̀nó bùlwà	òsɛ̀nó blà	òsɛ̀lɔ̀b w	òsɛ̀nɔ̀b wà	òsɛ̀nɔ̀b tùl	òsɛ̀nɔ̀bù là	òsɛ̀nɔ̀bùl wà	òsɛ̀lɔ̀b wà	òsɛ̀nɔ̀b tùlwà	òsɛ̀nó bùlwà	òsàlɔ̀b w	God
217	ɔ̀kpá	ɔ̀kpá	ɔ̀kpá	ɔ̀kpá	ɔ̀kpá	ɔ̀kpá	ɔ̀kpá	òó	ɔ̀kpá	òwó	ɔ̀kpá	ɔ̀kpá	òwó	one
218	èv	èv	èv	èv	èv	èv	èv	èv	èv	èv	èv	èv	èv	two
219	éà	éà	éà	éà	éà	éà	éà	éà	éà	éà	éà	éà	éà	three
220	éne	éne	éne	éne	éne	éne	éne	éne	éne	éne	éne	éne	éne	four
221	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	ísé	five
222	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	éhá	six
223	ihú	ihlɔ̀	ihlɔ̀	ihlɔ̀	ihlɔ̀	ihlɔ̀	ihlɔ̀	ihlɔ̀	ihú	ihlɔ̀	ihlɔ̀	ihlɔ̀	ihj	Seven
224	ééré	èlélè	èlélè	èlélè	èlélè	èlélè	èlélè	èlélè	èréré	éélè	èlélè	èlélè	èèé	eight
225	ísiri	ísiri	ísiri	ísiri	ísiri	ísiri	ihiri	ísiri	ísiri	ihiri	ísiri	ísiri	ihú	nine
226	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ìgbé	ten
227	ùgbóro	ùgbóro	ùgbóro	ùgbóro	ùgbóro	ùgbóro	ùgbóro	ùgbóro	ùgbóro	òwɔ̀	ùgbóro	ùgbóro	òwɔ̀	eleven
228	ìgbéva	ìgbéva	ìgbéva	ìgbéva	ìgbéva	èvánaig bé	ìgbéva	ìgbéva	ìgbéva	ìwéva	ìgbéva	ìgbéva	ìwéva	twelve

229	igbèrà	igbèlèà	igbèlè à	éààṅàì gbé	—	Ìgbéβéà	igbèà	igbèlèà	igbèà	iwèrà	igbèà	—	iwèhà	thirteen
230	igbèrèx	igbèné	igbèné	énèṅàì gbé	—	igbèβén é	igbèné	igbèné	igbèhà	iwèné	igbèné	—	iwèné	fourteen
231	igbèhè	—	igbèhè	isèṅàì gbé	—	igbèβìs é	—	ifésùdž é	igbèhè	ikjésù gje	igbìsè	—	késùgje	Fifteen
232	—	—	—	éhāṅàì gbé	—	—	—	—	igbèhà	éhāṅàì gbé	igbèhà	—	—	sixteen
233	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	seventeen
234	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	eighteen
235	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	Nineteen
236	ɔgbɔ	ùdžé	ùdžé	ùdžé	ùdžé	ùè	ùè	ùdžé	ùè	ùgje	ùdžé	—	ùgje	twenty
237	ɔkpáṅàɔ gbɔ	—	—	—	—	ùèβɔkp à	ɔkpáṅà ùè	—	ɔkpáṅàùè	ɔkpáṅ áùgè	ùdžéɔk pà	ùèβɔk pà	—	Twenty -one
238	évāṅàɔg bɔ	—	—	—	—	ùèβèvà	évāṅàù è	—	évāṅàùè	évāṅà ùgje	ùdžébjè vā	ùèβèv à	—	Twenty -two
239	ɔgbixó	ɔgbà	ɔgbà	ɔgbà	ɔgbà	ùèβìgbè	ɔgbà	ɔgbà	ɔgbixó	ɔgbà	ɔgbà	ùèβìgb è	èkésugje	thirty
240	ijévà	égbɔèvà	égbɔèv á	ɔgbɔèv á	ɔgbɔèvà	égbɔèvà	égbɔlèv á	égbɔèvà	ɔgbɔèvà	ijévà	ɔgbɔèvà	égbɔèv á	ijévà	forty
241	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	fifty

242	ijéh'é	égbwáà	égbwáà	ɔgbwáà	ɔgbwáà	égbwáà	égbwáà	égbwáà	égbwáà	égbwáà	égbwáà	ɔgbwáà	ijéhá	égbóléá	égbwáà	ijéhé	sixty
243	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	Seventy
244	ijéné	égbwáà	égbwáà	ɔgbwáà	ɔgbwáà	égbwáà	égbwáà	égbólé	---	ɔgbwáà	ijéné	égbólén	égbwáà	égbwáà	ijéné	eighty	
245	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	ninety
246	ijísé	ijísé	égbwáà	ɔgbwáà	ɔgbwáà	égbwáà	égbwáà	égbólís	égbwáà	ɔgbwáà	ijísé	égbólís	égbwáà	égbwáà	ijísé	hundred	
247	---	---	égbwáà	---	---	égbwáà	égbwáà	égból	égbwáà	ijígbé	ijígbé	égbwáà	égbwáà	égbwáà	urí	Two hundred	
248	---	---	égbwáà	---	---	égbwáà	égbwáà	égból	égbwáà	ijíngbé	ijíngbé	égbwáà	égbwáà	égbwáà	---	Four hundred	
249	βihí	βi	βi	βihí	βi	βihí	βihí	βihí	βi	βihí	βihí	βi	βihí	βihí	éxwí	Black	
250	fwà	fwà	fwà	fwà	fwà	fwà	fwà	fwà	White								
251	gjà	ɔgjà	ɔgjà	ɔgjà	gjà	ɔgjà	ɔgjà	ɔgjà	ɔgjà	gjà	ɔgjà	gjà	ɔgjà	ɔgjà	bá	Red	
252	kpɔɔ	gbà	kpɔɔ	kpɔɔ	kpɔɔ	kpɔɔ	kpɔɔ	kpɔɔ	xwà	Big							
253	tá	tá	tá	tá	tá	tá	tá	tá	Long								

254	mǎǎ	úxjɔmɛ	túkɛ xɛrɛ	xɛrɛ	kpɛkɛ	kpúkɛ	túkúpú	ǂǂǂ	hí	xɛrɛ	xɛrɛ	xɛrɛ	xɛrɛ	Small short
255	dɔmǎɛ	ɪɔ	dɔmǎ ɛ	dɔmǎ	dɔmǎɛ	dɔmǎɛ	dɔmǎ	fǂfǂ	dɔmǎ	dɔmǎ	dɔmǎɛ	bwɛ	dómǎɛ	Old
256	bwɛ	ɪɔ	—	fǂfǂ	—	wɛjǂ	tɛ	ǂǂǂ gbɔ	ǂwɛjǂ	dɔmǎ	ɣɔ	bwɛ	xǂɔmǎɛ	Old(top p new)
257	ɔsɔgb ɔ	dɔgbɔ	ɔgbɔ	ɔsɔg bɔ	ɔgbɔ	ɔgbɔ	ɔsɔgb	ɔgbɔ	ɔsɔgbɔ	ɔgbɔ	ɔsɔgb	ikɔgb	ɔɣɔgb	New
258	fwɔfwɔ	—	fwɔsɛ	fwɔfw	rwɔrw	fwɔfw	fwɔfw	ɪɪɪ	—	fwɔfw	fwɔfw	βɔká	fwǎmɛ	Met
259	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	Dry
260	tò	xwǎ	ɣǎ	tò	twɛ	xwǎ	xwǎ	twɛ	tò	gǂɛ	xwǎ	xwǎ	ɪɔ	Hot(fir e)
261	fú	fwɔfwɔ	fwɔfw	fwɔfw	fwɔfw	ú	úfǂ	fwɔfwɔ	fwɔfwɔ	fwɔfw	fwɔfw	fwɔfw	fú	Cold
262	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ rǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	ǂbɛrǎ	Right (side)
263	ǂbǂɪɪɪ	ǂbǂgǂb	ǂbǂgǂb	ǂbǂgǂb	ǂbǂdǂɟ bɔ	ǂbǂgǂb	ǂbǂgǂb	ǂbǂgǂb	ǂbǂɪɪɪ	ǂbǂgǂb	ǂbǂgǂb	ǂbǂgǂb	ǂbǂɪɪɪ	Left
264	ɔmɛ	ɔmɛx	ɔmɛ	ɔmɛ	ɔmɛ	émǂɛsǂ	émǂɛsǂ	émǂɛsǂ	émǂɛx	ɔmǎ	òmǂɛ	ɔmɛ	ɔmǎ	Good
265	ɔǂmǂɛ	ǂbɛxɔ	ɔbɛ	ɔǂmǂɛ	—	ǂbɛxɔ	émǂɛbɛ	ɔǂrǂǎ	ǂbɛxɔ	—	ɔǂmǂɛ	ɔbɛ	émǎ	Bad

266	rjerjé	mjemjé	lélé	njenjé	rjerjé	léḡúnú	lélé	méḡúnú	rjerjé	rjerjé	lélé	lélé	mjemjé	Sweet
267	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	xwǎ	Heavy
268	vw▷	vw▷	vw▷	vw▷	vw▷	vw▷	vw▷	vw▷	vw▷	v▷	vw▷	v▷	v▷	Full
269	wò	tòtò	zézé	kàkà	zjé	wò	wò	wò	kàkà	kàkà	kàkà	kàkà	kàkà	Strong
270	kàkà	zé	rò kàkà	kàkà	kàkà	zézé kàkà	zézé	kàkà	zézé	kàkà	kàkà	kàkà	toto tòtò	Hard
271	lè	lè	lè	lè	▷	lè	lè	lè	lè	lè	lè	lè	rjèḡzé	Eat
272	dà	w▷	mw▷	w▷	w▷	h▷	▷	w▷	w▷	w▷	mw▷	h▷	w▷	Drink
273	mī▷	sò▷▷	mī▷	mī▷	mī▷	mī▷▷	mī▷▷	mī▷	mī▷	mī▷	mī▷	mī▷	mī▷	Swallow w
274	xùlé	xùlé	xùlé	xùlé	xùlé	xùlé	xùlé	xùlé	xùlé	fjǎ	xùlé	xùlé	fjǎ	Bite
275	lǎ▷	nàn▷	nàn▷	lǎ▷	lǎ▷	nàn▷	nàn▷	nàn▷	lǎ▷	lǎ▷	nàn▷	nàn▷	lǎ▷	Lick
276	d▷m▷	dámé	d▷mé	fèxé	dámé	fèúmé	dámé	rèsúnú	d▷m▷	dámé	fèxé	d▷mé	dámé	Taste
277	túfǎ	gjiéfiǎ	húfiǎ	túfiǎ	túfiǎ	túfiǎ	túfiǎ	ḡjéfiǎ	túfiǎ	túfiǎ	húfiǎ	túfiǎ	túfiǎ	Spit
278	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	kpǎ	Vomit

279	feá	feá	fè	feá	fè	fè	feá	hɔ	fè	Urnate
280	nè	hɔhɔ	nè	nèá	nè	nè	nèá	nè	nè	Defecate
281	bjè	bjè	bjè	bjè	bjè	bjè	bjè	bjè	bjè	Give birth
282	ù	ù	jù	ù	ù	ù	ù	ù	jù	Die
283	kpàlɔm ùdjá	mùdjá	mùdjá	kpànɔ	kpàòtɔ	mùdjá	kpànɔ mùdjá	kpànò	mùdjá	Stand (up)
284	tètjã	dòtwã	dòtwã	tètá	tètá	dòtwdá	dòtwã	dòtwã	tùtã	Sit
285	dìgwé	dìgwé	dìgwé	dè dìgwé	dìgwé	dìgwé	dè dìgwé	dìgwé	dè dìgwé	Kneel
286	lòwé	nòwé	nòwé	nòwé	lòβjé	nòwé	nòwé	lòwé	lòβjé	Lie (down)
287	wé	wé	wé	wé	βjé	wé	wé	lòwé	βjé	Sleep
288	βòhjé	βòhjé	βòhjé	βòhjé	βòhjé	βòhjé	βòhjé	βòhjé	βòhjé	Dream
289	áxjá	áxjá	áxjá	áxjá	áxjá	ájã	áxjá	áxjá	ájã	Go
290	βàré	vàé	vàé	vàré	vàé	vàré	vàé	vàé	ádè	Come
291	kjèré	—	tjèràé	ftjèré	vàé	ftjèré	ftjè	vàé	—	Return

292	gàré	vàé	vàé	fiŋferé	vàé	vàré	ŋferé	vàé	sé	rè	vàlé	gàré	rè	Arrive
293	lǎβ▷	nǎβ▷	nǎβ▷	lǎβ▷	lǎβ▷	nǎβ▷	nǎβ▷	nǎβ▷	lǎβ▷	là▷	nǎβ▷	nǎβ▷	là▷	Enter
294	hè	hèlè	hè	h▷	h▷	hè	hè	hè	h▷	hijèlè	hèlè	hè	hijè	Climb
295	hwéré	hwéré	hwéré	hwéré	twéré	hwéré	hwéré	hwéré	hwéré	twéré	kpòndòv òé	hwéré	twòré	Descen d
296	dè	déré	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	déré	déré	dè	déré	dè	dè	Fall
297	xjà	xjà	xjà	ǰǎ	xjà	ǰǎ	xjà	xjà	xjà	xjà	ǰǎ	ǰǎ	xjà	Walk
298	zũlè	rúnè	rjũnè	rũlè	tũlè	zũnè	zũnè	rjũnè	rũlè	rũlè	rjũnè	nè	lè	Run
299	sǎ	sǎ	sǎ	sǎóxũ	sàxòxũ	sǎ	sǎ	sǎ	sǎ	sǎ	sǎóxũ	sǎ	sǎ	Jump
300	tĩ	tĩ	tĩ	tĩβòxũ	tĩ	tĩ	tĩ	tĩ	tĩ	tĩ	tĩ	tĩ	tĩ	Fly
301	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	gbèrá	Pass (by)
302	—	—	—	gbèlèg á	lèlègá	—	gbènèg á	—	—	—	dènègb è	nègá	lègá	Turn round
303	rèxǎ	rèxǎ	rèxǎ	rèxǎ	rèxǎ	rèxǎ	rèxǎ	rèxǎ	rèxǎ	lèlè	rèxǎ	rèxǎ	lèlè	Follow
304	yé	yé	dàyé	dàyé	dàyé	dàyé	dàyé	dàyé	yé	yé	dàyé	yé	bèyé	See

305	h▷	h▷	kàèh▷	àèh▷	hèmh▷	h▷	h▷	h▷	h▷	h▷	h▷	h▷	h▷	h▷	h▷	h▷	Hear
306	ròb▷sw ò	ròb▷sw ó	ròb▷s wó	ròb▷s wó	ròb▷sw ò	ròb▷sw ó	ròb▷s wó	ròb▷sw ó	ròb▷sw ó	ròb▷sw ó	ròb▷swó	ròb▷s wó	ròb▷sw ó	ròb▷s wó	ròb▷s wó	job▷kã	Touch
307	rè	lè	lè	j▷h▷	l▷lè	lè	lè	lè	lè	lè	lè	rè	rè	lè	è	Know	
308	jèré	jèlé	jèré	jèré	jèré	jèré	jèré	jèré	remem ber								
309	jèlèá	jégbèá	jèá	jèlèá	jèlèá	jèá	jèlèá	jèlèá	jèlèá	jèlèá	jèlèá	jèlèá	jèlèá	jèá	mjàmjã	Forget	
310	rjã	zilórijã	rjã	rjã	rjã	rjã	rjã	ò	Think								
311	lwè	lw▷	lwè	lwè	lwè	rwè	Learn										
312	gjè	djìè	gjè	gjè	djìè	djè	djè	djè	djè	djè	gjè	gjè	djè	djè	gjè	Laugh	
313	vjè	vjè	vjè	vjè	vjè	vjè	Weep										
314	swiló	swiló	swihw á	swilóré	swiló	swihwá	Sing										
315	gbixjé	gbixélé	gbixjé	gbixw é	gbè	gbijjé	gbixélé	gbixé	gbixjé	gbixjé	gbixjé	gbúkè	gbixé	gbixjé	kú	Dance	
316	xjè	xèlè	fsé	fsé	xjè	fsé	xilè	xèlè	fi	fi	ku	ku	fsé	átójur ó	kú	Play	
317	ófé	ófé	óhá	ófé	ófé	óhá	Fear										

331	múfǎ	rǎfǎ	rǎfǎ	rǎulwǎ	rǎfǎ	rǎjwǎ	rǎulwǎ	rǎfǎ	rǎfǎ	wǐ	rǎfǎ	—	rǎ	Loose
332	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	mǎ	Get
333	dòrè	rà	dòrè	dòrjé	rǎ	rà	dòrjé	rà	dòrjé	rǎ	dòrjé	rà	dòrjǎ	Steal
334	rè	rjè	rè	rè	rjè	jè	rè	rjè	rè	rjè	rjè	rè	rjè	Take
335	mù	mù	mù	mù	du	du	mù	mù	mù	mù	mù	mù	mù	Carry
336	rémǎ	rémǎ	rémǎ	mǎ	mǎ	rémǎ	rémǎ	rémǎ	rémǎ	jǎmǎ	rémǎ	rémǎ	rjémǎ	Show
337	rènǎ	rènǎ	rènǎ	rènǎ	rjénǎ	jénǎ	rènǎ	rènǎ	rènǎ	rjénǎ	rjénǎ	xjénǎ	rjénǎ	Given
338	xjè	xjè	xjè	xjè	xjè	jè	xjè	xjè	xjè	xjè	jè	xjè	xjè	Sell
339	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	zè	Choose
340	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	dè	Buy
341	hǎsǎ	hǎsǎ	hǎsǎ	hǎsǎ	hǎsǎ	hǎǎ	hǎsǎ	hǎsǎ	hǎsǎ	hǎsǎ	hǎsǎ	hǎ	hǎsǎ	Pay
342	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	kǎ	Count
343	yǎlǎ	gbèyǎé	yǎ	yǎ	yǎllé	yǎé	yǎlǎ	yǎé	yǎ	yǎ	yǎlǎ	yǎ	yǎé	divide

344	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	fò	Finish	
345	mū	mū	gwà mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	mū	catch
346	fì	fì	fì	fì	sà	Sà	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	fì	shoot
347	gbɔlǎ	gbɛ́á	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ́á	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	gbɛ	kill
348	xjàrǎ	kpóhǎ	tjè	kpàlɔ	xjàxǎ	hjàhǎ	xjàxǎ	kpóhǎ	và	kpàlɔ	kpàhǎ	và	xjàxǎ	skin							
349	ɲé	ɲé	ɲé	ɲé	ɲé	é	ɲé	ɲé	ɲé	lè	ɲé	ɲé	lè	cook							
350	rámǎ	lámé	lámǎ	lámǎ	lámǎ	lámǎ	lámé	lámǎ	lámǎ	rámǎ	kà	lámǎ	ámǎ	Fry							
351	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	tɔ	roast							
352	rùmǎ	lùmǎ	lùmǎ	lùmǎ	lùmǎ	lùmǎ	lùmǎ	lùmǎ	lùmǎ	dùmǎ	lùmǎ	lùmǎ	dùmǎ	pound							
353	lɔ	nɔ	gwɔɔɔ ɔ nɔ	lɔ	lɔ	nɔ	nɔ	nɔ	lɔ	lɔ	nɔ	nɔ	lè	Grind							
354	bùrù	biri	xèhǎ	biri	sǎɔ	gbɛ	biri	sǎɔ	biri	biri	biri	gbɛ	twè	pour							
355	rèfifì	rèfì	rèfì	rèfifì	fì	jèfì	rèfì	rèfì	rèfì	fì	rèfì	fì	fì	Throw							
356	gbɔlɔ	gbɛ́nɔ	gbɔn	gbɔl	kpóló	gbɛ́nɔ	gbɔn	gbɔnɔ	gbɔlɔ	kpóló	gbɔnɔ	gbɔn	kpóló	sweep							

381	rèwót▷	rét▷	rét▷	gbèḡwót▷	rèt▷	rét▷	gbèḡwót▷	rèwót▷	gbèḡwót▷	rét▷	gbèḡwót▷	rèwót▷	gbèḡwót▷	rét▷	wéè	Bury
382	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	b▷	Build
383	má	má	má	má	má	má	má	má	má	má	má	má	má	má	má	Mould
384	kál▷	kàn▷	kàn▷	kál▷	kál▷	kàn▷	kál▷	kàn▷	kàn▷	kàn▷	kàn▷	kál▷	kàn▷	kàn▷	má	Carve
385	lù	lù	má	lù	lù	lù	lù	lù	lù	lù	lù	lù	lù	lù	má	Make
386	gbà	djè	gbà	djè	gbà	djè	gbà	gbà	gbà	gbà	gbà	djè	gbà	gbà	gbà	Tie
387	tálá	tā	fàn▷	tàn▷	hwītā	tàn▷	tā	tálá	djè	djè	rá	tā	fàn▷	rá	Unite	
388	gwè	gwè	gwè	Gwè	gwè	gwè	gwè	gwè	gwè	gwè	gwè	gwè	gwè	gwè	Cover pot	
389	tùgjiè	biá	tùdžè	Biá	biá	tùdžè	tùdžè	tùgjiè	tùgjiè	tùdžè	tùgjiè	tùdžè	we bi	we bi	Open door	
390	bigbé	bigbé	gwè	xwè	xwè	bigbé	bigbé	xwè	xwè	xwè	xwè	xwè	bigbé	bigbé	Close	
391	wè	s▷X▷è	wè	Wè	kéké	wè	wè	wè	wè	wè	wè	wè	s▷X▷è	kéké	Be rotten	
392	jà	jà	jà	jà	wjā	jà	jà	jà	jà	jà	wjā	jà	jà	wjā	Stink	
393	hwè	hwéré	hwéré	huré	hùmjù	hùmjuré	h▷	wé	jòré	hwé	màré	h▷	hwé	hwé	Swell	

394	hòhò	hehe	fiè	fiè	hòhò	fiè	hòhò	fiè	fiè	hòhò	fiè	hòhò	Blow with mouth						
395	là	nà	fi	fi	là	nà	fi	nà	là	hòhò	fi	fi	hòhò	hòhò	hòhò	hòhò	hòhò	hòhò	Blow of wind
396	gbèrà	né	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	gbèrà	Surpass
397	èrè	èlè	né	jè	jà	né	èlè	né	èlè	né	èlè	né	ni	nèlè	djà	djà	djà	djà	Dwell
398	lèkókó	hèkókó	kókó	sikókó	hèkùgbé	sikókó	sikókó	kókó	lèkókó	kókó	kókó	sikókó	Gather up						
399	mùmᵛ	rjèmᵛ	mùmᵛ	mùmᵛ	rjèmᵛ	mùmᵛ	mùmᵛ	mùmᵛᵛ	mùmᵛ	mùmᵛ	mùmᵛ	mùmᵛ	mùmᵛ	mùmᵛ	dají	dají	dají	dají	Hold
400	imé	imé	imé	imé	mé	imé	imé	mé	imé	imé	imé	imé	mé	imé	mé	mé	mé	mé	I
401	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	wé	ùwé	ùwé	wé	ùwé	wé	ùwé	wé	wé	ùwé	wé	wé	wé	wé	you
402	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛ	ᵛè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	ᵛlè	He/she
403	imā	imǎ	imǎè	imǎ	mǎᵛᵛ	imǎ	imǎ	mǎ	imǎ	imǎ	imǎ	imǎ	imǎ	imǎlè	imǎ	imǎ	imǎ	imǎ	We
404	ìᵛà	ìᵛà	ìᵛà	ìᵛà	ᵛà	ìᵛà	ìᵛà	ᵛà	ìᵛà	ìᵛà	ìᵛà	ìᵛà	ùwà	ìᵛà	ìᵛà	ìᵛà	wà	wà	you
405	àlè	è	èlè	èlè	jà	è	èlè	nǎi	àlè	àlè	àlè	àlè	ìrà	èlè	èlè	èlè	ǎ	ǎ	They

406	ímétòbí mè	mènà	ímétòb òmjè	ímétòb ímè	métòbí mè	ímétòb mjè	métòbí mè	ímétòbímè	mèβ▷	métòb▷ mè	métòb ▷mjè	métòb▷ mjè	By myself
407	úwétòb úwé	ùmènà	úwétò b▷é	úwétò búwé	wétòb▷ é	úwétòb ▷é	wétòbú wé	wétòbú wé	wéβ▷	wétòb▷ é	wétòb ▷é	wétòb▷ wé	By yourself
408	▷léto▷ ▷	▷lènà	▷léto▷ ▷lè	▷léto▷ ▷lè	▷léto▷ ▷	▷éto▷ è	▷léto▷ ▷lè	▷léto▷▷lè	▷rè β▷	▷léto▷ ▷lè	▷léto▷ ▷	▷jètò▷é	By himself
409	ímjatóbí mjà	ímànà	ímjató bímjà	ímjató bímjà	máj▷to bómà	ímjatóbí mà	mjatóbí mjà	ímjatóbímj	máj▷ ▷	ímáto▷ ▷mà	ímjató b▷mjà	mátòbín à	By ourselves
410	íβátòbíβ à	íβànà	íβátòbí βà	íβátòbí βà	βátòb▷ βà	íβátòbí βà	βátòbíβ à	íβátòbíβà	wàβ▷	íβátòb▷ βà	íβátòbí βà	wátòbú wà	By yourselves
411	álétòbál è	èlènà	élétòb éle	élétòb éle	íátòbíà	étòbé	élétòbél è	álétòbálè	íràβ▷	élétòbél è	élétòb è	íátòbíà	By themselves
412	ímè	ímè	ímè	ímè	mè	ímè	ímè	ímè	mè	ímè	mè	mè	Subject
413	ímè	mè	mjè	mjè	mè	ímjè	mè	ímè	mè	mè	mè	mè	Object
414	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	wé	ùwé	ùwé	ùwé	wé	ùwé	wé	wé	Subject you
415	ùwé	é	é	é	wé	é	wé	ùwé	wé	é	wé	wé	Object you
416	▷lè	▷lè	▷lè	▷lè	▷	▷è	▷lè	▷lè	▷rè	▷lè	▷lè	▷jè	Subject he
417	à	à	▷lè	▷lè	é	àé	lè	lè	▷rè	lè	à	à	Object him

418	imà	imà	imàè	imà	màβ	imà	imà	mà	imà	mà	imà	mà	imà	mà	imà	mà	imà	imà	imà	Subject we
419	imà	mà	imàè	mà	màβ	imà	imà	mà	imà	mà	imà	mà	imà	mà	imà	mà	imà	imà	imà	Object us
420	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	wà	ipà	ipà	ipà	wà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	wà	Subject you
421	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	wà	ipà	ipà	ipà	wà	ipà	ipà	ipà	ipà	wà	Object you
422	àlè	è	èlè	èlè	ia	è	èlè	nàj	àlè	àlè	irà	èlè	èlè	ia	èlè	èlè	èlè	èlè	ia	Subject they
423	àlè	è	èlè	èlè	ia	è	èlè	nàj	àlè	àlè	irà	èlè	èlè	ia	àlè	àlè	àlè	àlè	ia	Object them
424	simé	sémé	sémé	sémé	mé	ikéme	simé	rsémé	simé	simé	mé	sémé	sémé	imé	ikéme	ikéme	ikéme	ikéme	imé	Mine
425	sùwe	sé	sé	sé	wé	iké	sùwe	sé	sùwe	sùwe	wé	sé	sé	iké	iké	iké	iké	iké	yóé	Yours
426	sòlè	sò	sòlè	sòlè	sòlè	ikòé	sòlè	sòlè	sòlè	sòlè	sòlè	sòlè	sòlè	ikòé	ikòé	ikòé	ikòé	ikòé	yíjé	His
427	símā	sémāé	sémā	sémā	símā	ikāmā	símā	sémā	símā	símā	mā	sémā	sémā	ikāmā	ikāmā	ikāmā	ikāmā	ikāmā	yímā	Ours
428	sípā	sépā	sépā	sépā	sépā	ikápā	sípā	sépā	sípā	sípā	wā	sépā	sépā	ikápā	ikápā	ikápā	ikápā	ikápā	yúwā	Yours
429	sàlè	sé	sélè	sélè	yíā	iké	sélè	sénāi	sàlè	sàlè	yírā	sélè	sélè	ikélé	ikélé	ikélé	ikélé	yímā	Theirs	
430	bòxí	béxí	bélá	béxí	bén	bén	bén	bélá	bòxí	bòxí	báxí	bélá	bélá	bé	bé	bé	bé	bé	βòxí	What?

431	ɔnɛ́lá	nɛ́lá	ɔnɛ̀	nɛ́lá	dɛ̀nɔ́xí βɔ	ɔnɛ̀á	ɔnɟá	ɔnɛ́lá	ɔnɛ̀á	dɛ̀nɔ́xí í	ɔnɛ́lá	nɛ́lá	dɛ̀nɔ́xí	Which ?
432	ɔlá	hɔlá	ɔà	kɔnɔ	dɛ̀nɔ́xí βɔ	kɔnɔ	kɔnɔ	ɔβɔlá	ɔlá	ɔβnɔ	ɔβɔlá	kɔnɔ	ánɔ	Who?